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<p><i>Due to project-level deliverable submission deadlines, the information in this document is updated as of M36 (October 31, 2025). However, the authors intend to also publish the updates to the activities as soon as they are available. This will ensure that the most up-to-date and comprehensive information is made available, supporting continuous improvement and strategic alignment across the cluster.</i></p>	

ABSTRACT

The purpose of the present deliverable is to define the strategy and foreseen for training and engagement activities for H2IOSC: promote a stakeholder engagement and raise the awareness to Social Science Humanities (SSH) communities, ensure a uniform and comprehensive training strategy and guarantee an accurate outreach strategy of H2IOSC outputs.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

SSH	Social Science and Humanities
H2IOSC	Humanities and Heritage Open Science Cloud
RI	Research Infrastructure
CLARIN-IT	Nodo italiano di CLARIN - Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
DARIAH-IT	Nodo italiano dell'infrastruttura di ricerca europea DARIAH (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities)
E-RIHS	Nodo italiano dell'infrastruttura di ricerca europea E-RIHS sull'Heritage Science
OPERAS	Nodo italiano dell'infrastruttura europea OPERAS - Open scholarly communication in the european research area for social sciences and humanities
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
ERIC	European Research Infrastructures Consortium
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
ERA	European Research Area
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
GLAM	Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums
EUSEA	European Science Engagement Association
EB	Editorial Board
ICDI	Italian Computing and Data Infrastructure

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Executive Summary

The Deliverable D1.3 defines the Community Engagement and Training Plan for the H2IOSC project, providing the strategic and operational framework for coordinating communication, stakeholder engagement, and capacity-building activities across the four participating Research Infrastructures — CLARIN-IT, DARIAH-IT, E-RHIS.it, and OPERAS-IT.

The document establishes a shared strategy for, on the one side, involving research communities, cultural heritage institutions, and technical experts, and, on the other side, supporting the development of skills and knowledge related to FAIR data management, Open Science, and the H2IOSC infrastructure services.

The model combines communication, dissemination, and training actions into an integrated ecosystem that tries to align H2IOSC with national and European objectives for Open and FAIR research.

The D1.3 deliverable supports H2IOSC's vision of a connected and competent national community, capable of sustaining and expanding the adoption of FAIR and Open Science practices across the Humanities and Cultural Heritage domains.

The plan identifies key target audiences, communication channels, and training formats, and proposes a roadmap of activities designed to strengthen participation, interoperability, and digital literacy.

The document is structured into five main sections, each contributing to the definition and implementation of a coherent approach to participation, communication, and training across the four national Research Infrastructures. Section 1 introduces the H2IOSC project and the role of Activity A1.3, outlining the rationale, objectives and scope of the deliverable within the overall governance and management framework. It clarifies how training, engagement and outreach are coordinated at project level and how they interact with other work packages. Section 2 provides a synthesis of the landscape activities--describing the methodology and results of the assessment of existing resources, training needs and standards--and publication strategies across the four RIs. It also presents the establishment and functions of the H2IOSC Editorial Board, the development of the H2IOSC Handbook and website, and the tools and indicators used to monitor training and engagement activities over time. Section 3 focuses on engagement and dissemination. It defines the objectives of the H2IOSC engagement strategy, maps key stakeholder groups, and identifies the channels and instruments used to communicate with them. The section reports on engagement and dissemination initiatives carried out during the first 36 months of the project, including publications, public engagement activities, and the implementation of Transnational Access and Mobility Grants as mechanisms to strengthen collaboration and knowledge exchange. Section 4 sets out the H2IOSC training framework. It describes the reference initiatives at European level, the project's training strategy and infrastructure, and the programme for training and upskilling H2IOSC users. It also details internal training and upskilling actions for project personnel, as well as the co-funding of PhD grants as a structural component of capacity building within the cluster. Section 5 presents the conclusions, highlighting how the combined engagement and training activities contribute to building a connected, competent

and sustainable community around H2IOSC, and how the proposed strategies align with the project's long-term sustainability and Open Science objectives.

The deliverable translates the project's vision into concrete actions, ensuring that H2IOSC evolves as a connected and participatory cluster of infrastructures for Humanities and Cultural Heritage research.

1. Introduction

H2IOSC aims to provide a federated and inclusive cluster of 4 Research Infrastructures in the ESFRI domain of Social and Cultural Innovation, to enable researchers from various disciplines in the fields of humanities, language technologies and cultural heritage to collaborate in research by sharing tools, services and data. The main impacts are presented in figure below:

A federated and inclusive cluster of 4 Research Infrastructures in the ESFRI Social Science and Humanities domain, to enable researchers from various disciplines in humanities, linguistics and heritage sciences sectors to collaborate in research by sharing tools, services and data

Figure 1: H2IOSC structure.

The activity **A1.3 “H2IOSC Training and Outreach Activities Coordination and Management Unit”** provides the managerial support to all the training and outreach activities, to ensure a

uniform and comprehensive strategy, at project level, so that each partner RI can follow a common policy. This task supports WP8 and the project partners' activities by helping keep the contacts with the relevant stakeholders, such as universities (especially for the PhDs programmes as well as for internships) and other educational bodies (for staff training).

Moreover, activity 1.3 manages the broader outreach activities of the project, by compiling and constantly **updating a stakeholder's directory, and ensuring the project's broader contacts with national and European infrastructures and cluster projects and initiatives** (including governing bodies, as well as ESFRI, SSHOC and EOSC), as well as industry, the cultural heritage sector (GLAM) and the general public. The staff allocated to this activity provide a coordination layer that ensures uniformity in the outreach strategies of the project. An academic and scientific outreach is expected to be developed. This includes coordinating the organisation of WP8 workshops, webinars, events and ensuring the presence of the partners at previously identified relevant/key national and international events, as well as planning for key publications and for meetings with key stakeholders. The task is in strict contact with the Project Management Board (PMB) and Administrative Management Board (AMB).

The deliverable **D1.3 "H2IOSC Training Activities Coordination and Management Procedures"** is the output of activity A1.3. It delivers a set of documents and procedures providing a **stakeholder list and the outreach plan, as well as instructions for partners on how to coordinate.** This document and procedures are constantly updated, and all changes were reported in the version at M18 and in this final version at M36.

The purpose of the present deliverable is to define the **strategy and foreseen training and outreach activities for H2IOSC.** To attain the results above H2IOSC partners need to:

- Promote a stakeholder engagement and the raise awareness to Social Science Humanities (SSH) communities.
- Guarantee an accurate outreach strategy of H2IOSC outputs.
- Ensure a uniform and comprehensive training strategy for:
 1. Training and upskilling the H2IOSC users.
 2. Internal Training & Upskilling.

2.1 Co-funding of PhD grants for carrying out research on topics relating to the H2IOSC activities

- Provide to users and researchers high-quality training materials, support resources FAIRification, promote Open Science & Open Publishing cultures.

One of the key issues is the stakeholder engagement plan described in this document. The plan aims to make the project intentions publicly available in a transparent way and support the H2IOSC to engage with research communities, funders, and other relevant initiatives.

An important factor to consider is that many users involvement activities aiming to engage users are training activities, which educate users in digital methods. The initiatives for user engagement can be categorized into two overarching groups:

- **Product/tool presentation and training:** this category involves showcasing existing products or tools to the user community and providing comprehensive guidance on how to effectively utilize them. The aim is to empower users with the knowledge and skills required to make the most of the available resources.
- **User needs assessment and verification:** In this category, the focus is on actively seeking input and feedback from users to understand their specific requirements and preferences. The goal is to assess whether it is feasible to meet their needs and to validate whether the current offerings align with user expectations.

By combining these two approaches, organizations and projects can ensure a well-rounded and user-centric engagement strategy that both equips users with valuable resources and listens to their input for continuous improvement.

2. Existing resources, training needs, standards, and publication strategies

The work carried out within Work Package 2 – “*Landscaping and building communities*” – aimed at conducting a comprehensive assessment of the Humanities, Language Technologies, Digital Humanities, and Heritage Science landscape in Italy, with a specific focus on the communities and resources connected to the four RIs federated in H2IOSC (CLARIN-IT, DARIAH-IT, E-RIHS.it, OPERAS-IT). The overarching objective was to identify existing digital resources, tools, services, projects, standards, and practices, as well as training needs and publication strategies, in order to support their FAIRification, integration into the National Cloud and the H2IOSC Marketplace, and the long-term sustainability of the ecosystem. For a detailed account, see Deliverable 2.2 – “*Second report on the H2IOSC landscaping activity*”.

2.1 Methodology and Design of the H2IOSC Landscape

From a methodological standpoint, WP2 adopted a mixed-methods strategy that combines quantitative and qualitative instruments. A single, shared questionnaire-based survey was designed and deployed across the communities of the four infrastructures to avoid fragmentation and “survey fatigue”. This survey collected structured information on the use and creation of data resources and tools, familiarity with research infrastructures, training needs, publication practices, and adherence to FAIR principles and licensing.

The survey was complemented by semi-structured interviews with selected researchers, which enabled a deeper exploration of data practices, attitudes towards sharing, perceived barriers to reuse, and expectations regarding the role of RIs. In parallel, focus groups with junior and senior scholars from different disciplines were organised to discuss open science, FAIR data, infrastructural needs, and the future of SSH infrastructures, providing a space for critical reflection and consensus-building.

In addition, WP2 partners carried out targeted community-oriented activities, such as the CLARIN Cafés and the “Giovedì di H2IOSC” seminar series, together with co-design sessions for pilots (e.g. the DARIAH-IT Digital Philology Hub). These events functioned both as engagement and as landscape instruments, feeding back into the refinement of survey questions, metadata fields, and prioritisation criteria for tools and datasets.

2.2 Landscape Strategy and Results

Building on this methodological framework, WP2 developed a unified landscape strategy that combines community evidence with a structured mapping of resources across the four infrastructures. Common criteria and metadata schemas were agreed upon to describe datasets, tools, and services (e.g. type, disciplinary domain, standards used, level of FAIRness, responsible institution, links to pilots and RIs), ensuring comparability and reuse across WPs. This work resulted in shared catalogues for landscaping datasets, landscaping tools, and pilot requirements, which directly inform FAIRification priorities and onboarding into the H2IOSC Marketplace.

The analysis of the survey, interviews, and focus groups revealed several transversal trends:

- a strong presence of digital practices and extensive use of databases, corpora, GIS and repositories,

- uneven awareness and use of existing RIs,
- recurrent gaps in training, particularly around data management, metadata standards, licensing, and FAIR-compliant publication,
- and structural barriers to data sharing, including lack of recognition for datasets and concerns about rights and long-term stewardship.

In response to these findings, WP2, in close collaboration with WP8, initiated targeted training actions and defined priority areas for capacity building, while the structured mapping of resources supported the identification of high-value assets to be FAIRified and integrated. At the same time, the landscaping results fed into the development of DHeLO (Digital Heritage Landscaping Platform) as a demonstrator and disciplinary observatory for Cultural Heritage and Heritage Science, and into the conceptual and technical design of the H2IOSC Permanent Observatory, which will provide a dynamic, long-term monitoring environment for communities, resources, and infrastructural trends.

Taken together, these activities move beyond a questionnaire-only approach and establish WP2 as the analytical and community-driven backbone of H2IOSC's landscape strategy, providing the evidence, tools, and criteria needed to guide future integration, training, and interoperability efforts.

2.3 H2IOSC Editorial Board

During the General Meeting of the project (Rome, February 6-7, 2024), the creation of the Editorial Board (EB) of the H2IOSC project was formalized. The EB is composed of a representative for each infrastructure. The Cluster deemed it essential to establish a body that would enable the development of a coordinated communication strategy, strengthen the identity of H2IOSC, and make the project recognizable. Among the main objectives of the EB are the creation of a promotion plan for the activities and research results of H2IOSC, the updating of the website and creation of social media channels, and the development of a coordinated image for H2IOSC.

One of the first actions carried out by the EB was to identify the **representatives for each Operational Unit of the project for training, dissemination, and engagement activities and initiatives**. This is a fundamental element within the engagement plan as it has allowed the creation of a network that facilitates, promotes, and disseminates the actions aimed at engaging the entire community in a coordinated manner.

2.3.1 H2IOSC Handbook

The '[H2IOSC Handbook](#)' aims to provide an overview of the H2IOSC Project's state of the art and to introduce the people who make it possible, **not only to the H2IOSC community but also to a wider audience**. The 'H2IOSC Handbook' is an open and dynamic document, constantly evolving, and is expected to be updated as required throughout the project.

The handbook contains the glossary section. This glossary consists of ten terms that provide context to the H2IOSC project regarding research infrastructure in Europe and the disciplines involved in the project. Additionally, eight key terms have been identified representing each project WP. At present, the eight keyword definitions provided for WP are intentionally

broad, as it will be possible to provide more context-specific meanings for each term at a later stage of the project. The keywords related to this deliverable is **outreach**.

Outreach can be defined as the planning of a user involvement or training program that actively involves a broad community. This involvement may take place through the creation of events, initiatives, or the dissemination of materials that not only satisfy the relevant scientific community but also reach other possible stakeholders. The main objective of outreach is to maximize the impact of research and communicate knowledge and good practices, thus contributing to positive community involvement. More generally, outreach activities also include information and orientation initiatives dedicated to promoting the knowledge of products, services, and possibilities offered by Research Infrastructures to potential users.

2.3.2 H2IOSC Website

H2IOSC Website (<https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/>) is the official portal of this project.

The top navigation is concise and stable across pages: Home, The project, Partner Institutions, The RIs Cluster, TNA/NA Calls (with four subpages: First–Fourth Call Documents), Training Infrastructure, and News; there is also a link to the project’s LinkedIn page. The footer consistently lists funding credits (NRRP/NextGenerationEU, project code IR0000029) plus Privacy Policy, Colophon, and a Zenodo link. [h2iosc.cnr.it](https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/)

Core content areas:

- the project summarizes aims, funding, governance, and the “onestop, easyentry” openscience approach for software, datasets, services, and pilots;
- the RIs Cluster explains each participating RI and Italy’s national nodes; it notes, for example, that ERIHS became a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) on 28 March 2025 and that the cluster deploys high-performance computing nodes connected to the national research network;
- partner Institutions lists the participating CNR institutes, their operating units across cities (e.g., Naples, Pisa, Rome, Florence, Genoa), and contact details for unit heads and administrators;
- news aggregates updates under filters (All, Events, News, Press release, Training), showcasing calls, training sessions, and conference participation.

Interactive features and services:

- **Transnational and National Access (TNA/NA) Calls:** the site provides endtoend guidance, eligibility, access model (peerreviewed, excellencedriven), and a Microsoft Forms application link. The fourth and final call ran June 16–July 6, 2025, later extended to July 16, 2025, and highlighted new crossdomain pilot services such as Interlumo, ArchaeoHub, LLOD, and Digital Philology Hub (DPH).
- **Training Infrastructure:** two platforms are described—(1) the Training Environment, where users can register, enroll in courses, track progress, and engage via forums/chats/working groups, and (2) the Training Library, a repository for reusable

teaching modules that assigns PIDs and Creative Commons licenses. User manuals and brochures are linked.

The Home page foregrounds “What we do”—Landscaping & community building, Data Centers, a future Marketplace for services/tools/datasets, Community Pilots, and Training—and surfaces recent items from the News/Events feed.

Primary audiences are researchers in SSH/heritage, with outreach to businesses and citizens. The site positions H2IOSC as a national reference for open, interoperable research ecosystems that connect institutions (universities, libraries, archives, museums) and provide advanced tools for data and compute-intensive research. The site is a structured project hub that combines institutional presentation (project and partners), ecosystem context (RIs cluster), actionable access mechanisms (TNA/NA calls), and capacity building (training platforms), framed by consistent funding and governance transparency.

2.3.3 Monitoring Training and Engagement activities

An essential element for the successful progress of the project is the continuous monitoring of project activities. The same applies to the implementation of the training and engagement plan. This can be achieved through the identification of a set of KPIs (Key Performance Indicators):

- number of **training activities** carried out.
- number of **modules** produced and published.
- number of **outreach events**
- total number of **users** targeted with breakdown per activity.
- total number of **post-event questionnaires** received.
- number of **accesses** to online training materials
- **presence** at Summer Schools and relevant events for our community
- number of **courses** entered in the DHCR.
- number of **engagement activities** carried out
- total number of **audiences** targeted with breakdown per events.
- number of **accesses** to online training materials
- number of **publications** related to H2IOSC.
- number of **dissemination** events/initiatives

Some of these indicators have been used, and therefore valorised, in Deliverable D1.5 "H2IOSC Forum Report", which is a practical resource to understand and consolidate the project's acquired knowledge, offering valuable support to the Project decision-making structure in achieving project objectives.

In order to monitor all initiatives and events along with their respective numbers and information, the tools developed and attached to this deliverable are used (annexes 1, 2 and 3).

3. H2IOSC - Engagement and dissemination

3.1 Objectives

This planning process is about developing how to involve stakeholders and how to interact effectively with them during the project. The engagement strategy builds on the work of other Work Packages (WPs) to amplify the impact of H2IOSC and to involve the stakeholders at three levels:

INFORMATION - For stakeholders to effectively engage, they must first have access to fundamental information about the H2IOSC project. As a result, the project is committed to providing stakeholders with regular updates on its activities, events, services, and decision-making processes. These updates are tailored to each stakeholder group, ensuring that they receive messages that are pertinent to their interests and involvement. This proactive approach prepares stakeholders to actively participate in the project, enabling them to contribute to its outcomes and help shape them according to the specific needs of their respective communities.

CONSULTATION - Stakeholders are encouraged to contribute their comments, insights, and experiences related to the H2IOSC project's activities. This participation occurs both collectively, through group interactions like discussions and brainstorming sessions during workshops, Q&A sessions in webinars, and discussions following conference presentations, as well as individually, through surveys and other post-event follow-up activities. The feedback received from stakeholders after each event is collected and shared within the project team. This information plays a crucial role in shaping and informing the ongoing work of the project. One of the objectives of WP2 is to produce web-based questionnaires to assess scientific communities' educational needs and web-based questionnaires to assess the visibility and the level of awareness of the 4 RIs services and tools within the Italian community. Such a nation-wide and cross-infrastructure survey has never been conducted at this scale, and this analysis provides more details about the arising needs of communities. Furthermore, reports on training activities (workshops, webinars, etc.) organized by WP8 are expected to be public and shared.

INVOLVEMENT - H2IOSC provides stakeholders with multiple opportunities to actively influence and construct the H2IOSC Open Cloud and its services. These opportunities include consultation meetings, technical workshops, user group testing of the H2IOSC Marketplace, and the establishment of a board that ensures the day-to-day maintenance and the data quality of the Marketplace, among others. The intent is to prioritize diversity in terms of both disciplinary backgrounds and geographical locations. During these events, stakeholders are invited to participate in and contribute to specific project activities based on their expertise and their stakeholder group's characteristics. Our approach to awareness and training activities is not one-sided; instead, the project aims to actively engage communities in shaping the H2IOSC Open Cloud and ensuring their commitment to it. An important consideration is that our project partners already represent a substantial portion of the SSH community. They serve as both end users and amplifiers, utilizing their well-established networks, channels, and tools to ensure the adoption of the H2IOSC Open

Cloud. This adoption is expected to be further enhanced through a train-the-trainer approach within the activities outlined in the Building Expertise Strategy.

3.2 Significant engagement experiences and strategic documents

The H2IOSC engagement plan is inspired and guided by some meaningful experiences and strategic reference documents within the European Research Infrastructure framework, as well as by FAIR and open science principles. Below, we highlight the most pertinent ones.

Table 1: Significant engagement experiences and strategic documents

Organization/Project	Strategic document/Experiences
EOSC - European Open Science Cloud	Charter: EOSC Task Force on Researcher Engagement and Adoption
ESFRI, the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures	Strategic Report on Research Infrastructures – ROADMAP 2021
Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) project	Deliverable 6.1 Community Engagement Strategy
CLARIN - Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure	CLARIN ERIC Strategy 2024 - 2026 User Involvement Committee
DARIAH-ERIC - Digital research infrastructure for arts and humanities	Strategic plan 2019 - 2026
OPERAS - OPen scholarly communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities	How-to-advocacy - OPERAS practical guide on advocating for open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities
E-RIHS - European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science Implementation Phase	D.8.3 Services for new communities of users

3.3 Stakeholders' identification

Activity A.1.3 manages the broader outreach activities of the project, by compiling and constantly updating a **stakeholder's directory, and ensuring the project's broader contacts with national and European infrastructures and cluster projects and initiatives.** The identification of relevant stakeholder groups for the H2IOSC project, was performed by project partners during the project proposal stage. The project proposal identified primary stakeholder categories:

- **Universities**

- **National and European Infrastructures and cluster** projects and initiatives (including governing bodies, as well as ESFRI, SSHOC EOSC and ICDI)
- **GLAM** - Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums (Cultural Heritage Sector)
- **Archives and Research Libraries**
- **Communities of reference**
- **Public actors**
- **Relevant sector projects**

Following, other stakeholders to be taken into consideration are listed:

- **Policy makers:** Local, regional, national, EU policy makers and representative groups
- **Scientific and research community:** Researchers, students, research support personnel, National and European Research Councils
- **Industry/Innovation community:** Representatives of industry associations at regional, national and EU levels, social innovators and entrepreneurs
- **Civil society/ non-government organisations:** Associations, foundations, cooperatives and networks
- **Formal and informal education community:** Students, teachers, professors, science communicators, national and international science associations
- **General Public:** Citizens and audience beyond the project community
- **Other EU projects:** EU funded projects and initiatives such as the SSH framework.

Figure 2: H2IOSC stakeholders

To facilitate interaction with each of these groups, a Stakeholders Mapping Database has been established. This database identifies specific organizations within each stakeholder

group, as well as the existing connections, networks, channels, and tools between H2IOSC partners and each group.

The database's construction was a collaborative endeavor among project partners. A mapping exercise was conducted, during which each project partner contributed their knowledge and contacts within existing networks. This Community Engagement Strategy is an extension of the initial Stakeholders Mapping Database. The Database is a dynamic, GDPR-compliant spreadsheet that must be periodically updated by the cluster.

The information gathered from this initial landscape analysis included: identifying the primary stakeholders within each of the targeted stakeholder groups by the project, their geographical distribution, the academic discipline(s) to which they belong, the specific H2IOSC Work Packages (WPs) aimed at each category, and the existing networks, channels, and tools already established by project partners. This process must be reiterated, and the Stakeholders Mapping Database undergoes periodic updates to ensure efficient and tailored stakeholder engagement.

3.3.1 Targeted Research Infrastructures (RIs)

H2IOSC, Humanities and Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud aims to create a federated digital research infrastructure in the ESFRI domain of Social and Cultural Innovation, starting from the collaboration between the four high-priority infrastructures identified in the National Research Infrastructure Plan 2021-27, CLARIN (Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure), DARIAH (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities), E-RIHS (European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science) and OPERAS (Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities).

Table 2: Targeted Research Infrastructures (RIs)

R.I.	Description
CLARIN	CLARIN is an ERIC-type distributed research infrastructure that aims to provide access to digital language data – written, spoken and multimodal – and to integrate them at European level with advanced search, access and analysis tools, serving scholars in the Humanities and Social Sciences to support innovation and competitiveness.
DARIAH	The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH) ERIC aims to improve and support digitally-enabled research and teaching in the arts and humanities. DARIAH is a network of people, skills, information, knowledge, content, methods, tools and technologies from member countries. It develops, maintains and operates an infrastructure to support ICT-based research practices and researchers in their use to construct, analyse and interpret digital resources.
E-RIHS	E-RIHS is an ERIC-type distributed research infrastructure for heritage science that supports research on the interpretation, conservation, documentation

	and management of cultural heritage. The mission of E-RIHS is to provide integrated access to a wide range of advanced scientific tools, state-of-the-art expertise, methodologies, data and technologies to foster knowledge and innovation in the field of Cultural Heritage
OPERAS	OPERAS is a research infrastructure supporting science communication in the humanities and social sciences in the European Research Area (ERA). It intends to co-ordinate and federate national and European resources to effectively address the needs of researchers in science communication. OPERAS aims to provide the humanities community with elements to access, create, disseminate and validate research results effectively, with an innovative approach that considers publication not as the end result of research, but as an integral part of the research cycle itself, from discovery of material to analysis, publication and dissemination.

3.3.2 Mapping of the stakeholder landscape

This section provides the mapping of the stakeholder landscape. The map considers the analysis carried out during the period M01 – M36 of the project.

Table 3: Stakeholder list

Stakeholder	Website	Contact
European Strategic Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI)	https://www.esfri.eu/	esfri@ec.europa.eu info@str-esfri.eu
Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC)	https://sshopencloud.eu/	info@sshopencloud.eu
European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)	https://eosc-portal.eu/	Frequently Asked Questions Helpdesk
Italian Computing and Data Infrastructure (ICDI)	https://www.icdi.it/	info@icdi.it
OPENGLAM - Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums	https://openglam.org/	info@openglam.org
Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting	https://www.openarchives.org/pmh/	Frequently Asked Questions
Istituto Centrale per gli Archivi - ICAR	https://icar.cultura.gov.it/home	ic-a@beniculturali.it
Istituto Centrale per il Catalogo Unico (ICCU)	https://www.iccu.sbn.it/it/	ic-cu@cultura.gov.it
Associazione per l'Informatica Umanistica e la Cultura Digitale - AIUCD	http://www.aiucd.it/	aiucd.segreteria@aiucd.org
Associazione Italiana di Linguistica Computazionale AILC	https://www.ai-lc.it/en/	Contact the association
Associazione Italiana di Linguistica Applicata (AITLA)	http://www.aitla.it/	Contact the association
Associazione Italiana Scienza della Voce - AISV	https://www.aisv.it/	segreteria@aisv.it

Società Italiana di Glottologia - SIG	https://www.glottologia.org/	dovetto@unina.it
Società di Linguistica Italiana - SLI	https://www.societadilinguisticaitaliana.net/	Contact association
Consortium GARR	https://www.garr.it/it/	info@garr.it garr@postecert.it
International Council of Museums Italia	https://www.icom-italia.org/	info@icom-italia.org
IPERION HS	https://www.iperionhs.eu/	luca.pezzati@cnr.it
Opificio delle Pietre Dure	https://opificiodellepietredure.cultura.gov.it/	opd@cultura.gov.it
Ministero della Cultura	https://www.beniculturali.it/	urp@cultura.gov.it
Museo Galleria Borghese	https://galleriaborghese.beniculturali.it/	ga-bor.info@cultura.gov.it
Parco Archeologico del Colosseo	https://colosseo.it/	pa-colosseo@cultura.gov.it

Furthermore, stakeholders to be considered are all members, external to CNR, of the Italian nodes of the four research infrastructures involved in the project (CLARIN-IT, DARIAH-IT, E-RIHS.it, OPERAS-IT). See table below:

Table 4: Members of Italian infrastructure node consortia

CLARIN-IT Consortium		
Member	Website	Contact
Dipartimento di Filologia e Critica delle Letterature Antiche e Moderne – Università di Siena	https://www.dfclam.unisi.it/it	amministrazione.dfclam@unisi.it
Associazione EURAC Research (Bolzano)	https://www.eurac.edu/it	info@eurac.edu
Fondazione Bruno Kessler (Trento)	https://www.fbk.eu/it/	malesardi@fbk.eu
Soprintendenza Archivistica e Bibliografica della Toscana (Firenze)	https://sab-toscana.cultura.gov.it/home	sab-tos@cultura.gov.it
Interdipartimentale di Ricerca "URBAN/ECO" - Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II	https://www.unina.it/-/768621-dipartimento-di-ingegneria-elettrica-e-delle-tecnologie-dell-informazione	dip.ing-ele-tecinf@unina.it
Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore (Milano)	https://www.unicatt.it/	rapporti.pubblico-mi@unicatt.it
Università di Parma	https://www.unipr.it/	https://www.unipr.it/come-contattarci
Università degli Studi di Padova	https://www.unipd.it/	urp@unipd.it
Centro Linguistico di Ateneo - Università degli Studi di Ferrara	https://www.unife.it/it/cla	https://www.unife.it/it/contatti

Dipartimento di Studi Letterari, Linguistici e Comparati - Università degli Studi di Napoli "L'Orientale"	https://www.unior.it/it/dipartimenti/dipartimento-studi-letterari-linguistici-e-comparati	https://www.unior.it/it/URP
Fondazione RUT (Rome and Ercolano)	https://fondazionerut.org/	info@fondazionerut.org
Università di Bologna	https://www.unibo.it/it	caterina.mauri@unibo.it
Italian Institute of Germanic Studies	https://www.studigermanici.it/	hohenegger@studigermanici.it
DARIAH-IT Consortium		
Member	Website	Contact
Prato State Archive (ASPO)	https://archiviodistatoprato.cultura.gov.it/home	as-po[at]cultura.gov.it
Museum of Palazzo Pretorio (MPP)	https://www.palazzopretorio.prato.it/it/	museo.palazzopretorio@comune.prato.it
The Archival and Bibliographic Superintendency of Tuscany (SABTOS)	https://sab-toscana.cultura.gov.it/home	sab-tos@cultura.gov.it
Central Institute for the Union Catalogue of Italian Libraries (ICCU)	https://www.iccu.sbn.it/en/	ic-cu@cultura.gov.it
Fondazione Ezio Franceschini (FEF)	https://www.fefonlus.it/index.php/it/	segreteria@fefonlus.it
National Institute of Nuclear Physics (INFN)	https://home.infn.it/it/	https://home.infn.it/it/comunicazione/ufficio-comunicazione
International Society for the Study of Medieval Latin Culture (SISMEL)	https://www.sismelfirenze.it/	https://www.sismelfirenze.it/index.php/contatti
Italian Academic and Research Telecommunication Consortium (GARR)	https://www.garr.it/it/	https://www.garr.it/it/contatti
Italian National Agency for new Technologies Energy and Sustainable Economic Development (ENEA)	https://www.enea.it/en/	https://www.enea.it/en/information-and-contacts.html
Multimedia Research Resource Centre, University of Bologna (CRR-MM)	https://sba.unibo.it/it/almadl/collezioni/portfolio-crrmm	https://sba.unibo.it/it/almadl/collezioni/portfolio-crrmm
Museo Galileo, Florence	https://www.museogalileo.it/it/	https://www.museogalileo.it/it/museo/visita/informazioni-museo.html
University of Pisa (UNIFI)	https://www.unipi.it/index.php/english	https://www.unipi.it/index.php/university/item/26630-contacts
University of Rome 'La Sapienza' (UNIROMA1)	https://www.uniroma1.it/it/pagina-strutturale/home	https://www.uniroma1.it/it/pagina-strutturale/contatti
University of Siena (UNISI)	https://www.unisi.it/	https://www.unisi.it/contatti
University of Western Piedmont (UNIUPO)	https://www.uniupo.it/en	https://www.uniupo.it/en/about-upo/where-we-are

University of Napoli Federico II (UNINA)	https://www.unina.it/home.jsessionid=FA2407A413C82AB530DF2206E5B5AF68.node_staging11	https://www.unina.it/documents/11958/7885520/Elenco-PEC-2024-04-08.pdf
University of Rome – (UNIROMA3)	https://www.uniroma3.it/	https://www.uniroma3.it/en/contact/
Scuola Normale Superiore - Pisa	https://www.sns.it/it	https://www.sns.it/it/amministrazione
E-RIHS.it Consortium		
Member	Website	Contact
INFN - Italian National Institute for Nuclear Physics	https://home.infn.it/en/	https://home.infn.it/it/comunicazione/ufficio-comunicazione
ENEA - Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development	https://www.enea.it/en/	https://www.enea.it/en/information-and-contacts.html
OPERAS-IT Consortium		
Member	Website	Contact
Università degli Studi di Torino	https://www.unito.it/	https://www.unito.it/emergenze-contatti-pec-urp
Università degli Studi di Bologna	https://www.unibo.it/it	https://www.unibo.it/it/ateneo/contatti
Università degli Studi di Macerata	https://www.unimc.it/it	https://www.unimc.it/it/unimc-comunica/contatti
Università degli Studi di Messina	https://www.unime.it/	https://www.unime.it/ateneo/contatti
Università degli Studi di Milano	https://www.unimi.it/it	https://www.unimi.it/it/ateneo/uffici-e-strutture
Università degli Studi di Roma Tor Vergata	https://web.uniroma2.it/	https://web.uniroma2.it/en/percorso/university_offices
Firenze University Press	https://www.fupress.com/	https://www.fupress.com/it/contenuti/contatti/8207
Lexis Compagnia editoriale srl, Torino	https://www.lexis.srl/	info@lexis.srl
Net7 srl, Pisa	https://www.netseven.it/	https://www.netseven.it/contattaci/

Table 5: H2IOSC's existing network

Events	CLARIN Annual Conference
	Corpus Linguistics Conference
	ESSLI Summer School 2025
	International Congress of Linguists (ICL)
	Love Data Week

	<p>CMC Corpora 2024</p> <p>DARIAH Annual Meeting</p> <p>OPERAS Conference 2024</p> <p>Workshop: Research infrastructures and education: the case of Heritage Science IPERION HS - E-RIHS (Lubiana, 25 October)</p> <p>GCH and XR Salento 2023 (Lecce 4-9 September)</p> <p>RICH Europe's first Symposium of Research Infrastructures</p> <p>(7th May 2024, in Madrid - Spain)</p>
Relevant funded projects / initiatives	<p>Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC)</p> <p>https://sshopencloud.eu/</p>
	<p>Joint initiative between CLAIRN and DARIAH ERIC</p> <p>Digital Humanities Course Registry (DHCR)</p>
	<p>CLARIN ERIC</p> <p>National consortia and User Involvement Committee</p> <p>https://www.clarin.eu/governance/user-involvement-committee</p> <p>The Knowledge Infrastructure</p> <p>https://www.clarin.eu/content/knowledge-infrastructure</p> <p>Knowledge Centres</p> <p>https://www.clarin.eu/content/knowledge-centres</p>
	<p>OPERAS</p> <p>Special Interest Groups</p> <p>https://operas-eu.org/special-interest-groups/</p>
	<p>ESFRI - European Strategic Forum on Research Infrastructures</p> <p>https://www.esfri.eu/monitoring</p>
	<p>MATHPROCULT - PRIN-PNRR</p> <p>https://sites.google.com/view/mathprocult/home</p>
	<p>RICH EUROPE</p> <p>https://rich-europe.eu/</p>

Scientific journals and open access publications	Digital Humanities Quarterly (DHQ)
	Digital Scholarship in the Humanities (DSH)

3.4 Engagement Channels and Instruments: Tools for Effective Communication and Interaction

H2IOSC uses several tools and methods to engage with stakeholders. These should be addressed and created according to the target audience. The tools and methods are described in table below:

Table 6: Tools for Effective Communication and Interaction

H2IOSC website and social media	Conferences	Training events and webinars
<p>The project website serves as the central repository for all project-related materials, including news, updates, deliverables, and more.</p> <p>Social media are used to connect with all H2IOSC stakeholders.</p>	<p>Participation in conferences, including those organized by H2IOSC and third-party events, serves several purposes. These events facilitate the establishment of partnerships, increase awareness of the H2IOSC initiative, and broaden the H2IOSC stakeholder community.</p>	<p>The training sessions emphasize hands-on experience with data and effective utilization of H2IOSC tools, services, and data for SSH research.</p> <p>Webinars serve as a mean to connect with, involve, and educate stakeholders from diverse disciplines, including the H2IOSC user community, by showcasing both new and existing tools for data creation and reuse developed by the project.</p>
Workshops and pilot studies	Surveys and interviews	Poster and information materials
<p>Project-run workshops and consultation meetings serve as forums for engaging stakeholder groups, gathering their feedback, and involving them in the development of the various components of the H2IOSC.</p> <p>The project collaborates with research groups with the objective of identifying challenges and hindrances in the utilization of</p>	<p>We gather user feedback and input to pinpoint gaps and requirements within stakeholder communities, thereby enabling informed and effective project endeavors.</p> <p>Additionally, individual interviews are conducted to gain deeper insights into stakeholder needs and their expectations concerning the H2IOSC.</p>	<p>The use of posters and poster presentations enhance stakeholders' comprehension and engagement with the project.</p> <p>Information materials, as a standard practice, are designed to inform stakeholders and increase awareness regarding the project and its ongoing developments.</p>

<p>H2IOSC resources, which are addressed through pilot studies.</p>		
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Moreover, the H2IOSC Cluster utilizes and expands its existing network, communication channels, and tools both throughout the project's duration and into the future. This network encompasses various entities such as groups, projects, associations, and events, some of which are outlined in the table below. All H2IOSC project partners hold essential roles in engagement activities, as they are already integrated into the community the project aims to reach. Consequently, they can help amplify crucial messages, enhancing the project's visibility significantly.

The activity leader of task 1.3 has developed a **shared worksheet to identify engagement activities/opportunities for the project**, as well as synergies between activities of H2IOSC work packages and external actors. **This document has been updated during project life by project partners** to ensure coordination of activities and targeting of all appropriate audiences, thus increasing engagement and impact. It has been **shared on a drive that complies with GDPR regulations (see annex 1)**. For more details regarding the collected information, please refer to paragraph “H2IOSC engagement and dissemination initiatives carried out (period M01 – M36)”.

3.5 Stakeholders Engagement Strategy: A Framework for Effective Engagement

The stakeholder mapping process aims to identify which stakeholders need to be engaged, in order to achieve the highest impact for the project. The stakeholder’s selection based on the content, the expected results and the impacts of the project, as well as the available resources, the objectives of the engagement, and the willingness or the ability of the stakeholders to engage and to be involved to the project.

Stakeholder mapping is a collaborative process of research, debate, and discussion that draws from multiple perspectives to determine a key list of stakeholders across the entire stakeholder spectrum. Mapping can be categorized into three phases, which presented following:

- Identify all potential stakeholders.
- Assess and prioritise the stakeholders.
- Develop an understanding of stakeholders.

The results from the above-mentioned stages are considered by the project team in order to establish what level of engagement is required, the timing and role of the engagement, and ultimately which methods of engagement are to be adopted for each one.

This section provides an overview of each stakeholder group, its contextual landscape, and its relationship with the H2IOSC project. It also highlights key messages, efficient engagement channels, and specific engagement initiatives. The activities specified in this subsection are preliminary and are expected to undergo periodic revision to adapt to changing needs and emerging opportunities.

Researchers

Researchers may work independently or be affiliated with universities, institutions, industry, or non-governmental organizations, and they can be at various stages of their research careers. These networks encompass learned societies, research communities, scientific and professional associations, and they are integral components of the broader Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) domain. This domain also includes scientists who incorporate computational approaches into their research methodologies.

ENGAGEMENT INSTRUMENTS - The project establishes direct communication with research networks whose researchers are potential users of the H2IOSC services through mailing list, personal contact, workshops, events, interviews, training, workshops and webinars.

Research Infrastructures

Definition of Research Infrastructures (RIs): *“Facilities that provide resources and services for research communities to conduct research and foster innovation”*.

The internal organization of individual Research Infrastructures (RIs) may differ, but they typically consist of interconnected elements with national, technical, and scientific or thematic dimensions. What's particularly important for the engagement strategy is the inherent ability of RIs to reach out to their respective communities. Each RI is present in multiple Member States and has established direct communication channels with hundreds of professionals, including researchers and those responsible for technical infrastructures, across numerous institutes.

ENGAGEMENT INSTRUMENTS - Effective communication with e-Infrastructures is guaranteed through various EOSC-related channels, including engagement with EOSC-relevant projects like EOSC-hub and other EOSC cluster projects, participation in relevant events, and co-location of activities whenever feasible. It's worth noting that many H2IOSC project partners are already actively engaged in other EOSC-related initiatives and activities. The primary objective of communication is to cultivate a collaborative and equitable relationship, with e-Infrastructures recognizing the representative and intermediary role played by Research Infrastructures (RIs) within their respective communities.

Archives and Research Libraries

Research libraries and archives are integral components of the research and scholarship ecosystem. They play a vital role in facilitating, endorsing, and enabling Open Science practices and research output. Many of these institutions are deeply engaged in supporting the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) community. Due to their close interactions with SSH researchers, they assume a dual role as both users of research resources and intermediaries.

ENGAGEMENT INSTRUMENTS – Indeed, several channels and tools have been identified to facilitate this engagement, including conferences and workshops, webinars, surveys and interviews, the H2IOSC website, and social media channels. These methods provide diverse avenues for communication and interaction with stakeholders and the broader community.

Universities and Research Institutions

Universities and research institutions represent a system which are indispensable for the promotion and advancement of science. This stakeholder category specifically encompasses all EU universities and research institutions that are part of the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) domain, with a particular focus, by way of example, on institutions engaged in the Digital Humanities field.

ENGAGEMENT INSTRUMENTS – The project uses webinars, trainings, publications, and interviews to ensure the exchange of knowledge and good practices. Furthermore, surveys and direct contact, project partners' expertise, relations, channels and tools already in place.

Policy makers

The European Commission describes European Union policies and laws in the decision-making process as “carefully designed to bring benefits to citizens, businesses and other stakeholders in the EU”.

ENGAGEMENT INSTRUMENTS – The project actively involves and supports national decision-makers and policy makers. It has also to make sure to raise awareness on how they can profit from the SSH Open Cloud at national level.

Research Funding Organizations

Research Funding Organizations are crucial facilitators of Open Science (OS), particularly through the requirements they set for grant recipients. Consequently, they have a pivotal role in the development of the Open Cloud for Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). Numerous research funding programs and organizations, both at the European and national levels, provide funding opportunities for individuals and institutions to conduct research in various Social Sciences and Humanities disciplines. These organizations are actively promoting Open Access to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data, further advancing the principles of Open Science.

ENGAGEMENT INSTRUMENTS – Various channels have been identified to enhance the awareness of research funding organizations about the project and to foster their engagement. Workshops and strategic in-person meetings, for instance, provide research funding bodies with the chance to establish connections with the project, its beneficiaries, and other stakeholders. These interactions can help them adapt their funding policies to align with evolving requirements, ultimately enhancing the impact of their funding initiatives. This approach encourages a more effective and responsive allocation of resources in support of Open Science and the SSH Open Cloud.

Private Sector

By engaging with the private sector and industry, H2IOSC can ensure a higher profile for greater usage of its assets, thus supporting industrial development. This contributes to the

sustainability of the project. H2IOSC is of interest to this stakeholder group with business opportunities to exploit the marketplace services and the on-boarding of domain specific skilled professionals on data stewardships.

ENGAGEMENT INSTRUMENTS – Several engagement activities are planned in the project’s timeframe with conferences, workshops and webinars being among the most common. In addition, H2IOSC planned to ensure presence at specific related events. Furthermore, H2IOSC have been identified as useful channel for engaging with the private sector the project website, virtual events such as webinars and physical events such as workshops.

Civil Society and Citizen Scientists

Civil society organizations: non-governmental groups such as trade unions, employers’ associations and other social groups— allow citizens to take an active part in setting the political agenda.¹

Citizen science is any activity that involves the public in scientific research, and thus has the potential to effectively bring together science, policymakers, and society as a whole.²

ENGAGEMENT INSTRUMENTS –

The primary channels for communication are the H2IOSC website, social media, and the established channels of our project partners. Nevertheless, we also intend to showcase H2IOSC outputs, such as the H2IOSC Marketplace, where users can discover and evaluate all SSH tools and service solutions, at relevant Citizen Science events. Our aim is to actively engage with citizen scientists to gather feedback on their needs and user experience.

3.6 H2IOSC engagement and dissemination initiatives

Throughout its 36 months of activity, the H2IOSC project has carried out an extensive and well-structured programme of engagement and dissemination initiatives, designed to promote the project’s visibility, foster collaboration among research communities, and encourage the uptake of digital practices in the Humanities and Cultural Heritage sectors.

A total of 120 events were organized between June 2021 and October 2025 (Annex 1 – List of H2IOSC Engagement and Dissemination Initiatives), involving the four Research Infrastructures and numerous institutional partners across Italy and Europe. The recorded activities encompass a number of diverse types of actions, confirming the project’s wide-ranging outreach strategy and its capacity to address both specialized and general audiences.

Across all initiatives, the cumulative audience reached more than 10000 participants. This data demonstrates the strong level of interest generated by H2IOSC and the project’s ability to mobilize stakeholders across different domains — including researchers, educators, students, cultural heritage professionals, and policymakers.

The activities were diverse in format and scope, including:

¹ https://neighbourhood-enlargement.ec.europa.eu/enlargement-policy/policy-highlights/civil-society_en

² https://eu-citizen.science/ecs_project/

- 38 Conferences (national and international, in-person and hybrid)
- 18 Seminars and 14 Workshops, providing interactive forums for discussion and training
- 8 Public Events, 3 Round Tables, and 3 Expos, emphasizing outreach and community engagement

A number of invited talks, media releases, and online communications, which extended the project's reach to non-specialist audiences

This balanced distribution underscores the project's dual commitment to academic dissemination and societal impact. Many of these activities were presented within international frameworks contributing to the integration of Italian research infrastructures within the European Research Area and the broader EOSC/Open Science ecosystem.

The dissemination efforts were led by the four national nodes, each leveraging its domain expertise to reach its target communities. CLARIN and DARIAH contributed primarily to events on digital humanities, language technologies, and open scholarly communication, while E-RIHS focused on heritage science, diagnostics, and OPERAS open access publishing frameworks.

A significant portion of dissemination was also achieved through online visibility, including project website news, social media outreach, and digital repositories, ensuring the continuous dissemination of updates, deliverables, and FAIR-aligned outputs. This multi-channel strategy reinforced the H2IOSC mission to foster transparency, accessibility, and sustainability across all project activities.

Overall, the engagement and dissemination events demonstrate the consortium's proactive approach to community building, capacity development, and policy alignment.

The breadth and diversity of these initiatives reflect a consistent effort to connect research infrastructures, cultural institutions, and end users — contributing decisively to the creation of a national hub for Open Science and to Italy's active participation in the European landscape of distributed digital infrastructures.

The H2IOSC engagement and dissemination activities targeted a variety of public audience types, excluding events aimed solely at internal H2IOSC personnel. Based on the provided data, the main audience categories include:

- **students:** this encompasses learners at various levels, from high school students to university and doctoral students, who were invited to participate in specific outreach and educational events.
- **academics and researchers:** this broad category covers the academic community (university faculty, scholarly institutions) and researchers (including research staff at universities or institutes). Many activities were tailored to engage academics and researchers, often together with related professional groups. Scholarly and professional associations in relevant fields (e.g. linguistic associations) were also targeted as part of this community;

- **professionals and practitioners:** These are industry and domain specialists outside of academia. Subgroups included:
 - cultural heritage professionals, such as museum professionals and archaeologists, particularly for events in the heritage and cultural sector;
 - technical/IT professionals, e.g. software developers, IT specialists in fields like web, XR (extended reality), 3D graphics, cloud computing, etc., targeted by tech-oriented workshops;
 - industry partners, for example, companies in architecture and design were engaged in a career day event;
 - data stewardship professionals: the data stewards community was specifically addressed in certain training talks;
- **general public:** several outreach initiatives were intended for a general audience with no specialised background to raise broad awareness of the project and its themes. This category includes interested laypersons and the public at large who attended open events or read public-facing project news.

Students-Focused Activities

- **Oriental Studies & Digital Humanities:** a seminar event aimed at students (specifically, doctoral students of a PhD program in Asian and African Civilizations). This academic event introduced open science concepts to PhD candidates in that field;
- *Esperienze immersive tra archeologia e intelligenza artificiale.* An outreach event designed for high school students. It featured immersive experiences in archaeology and AI, bringing open science and heritage topics to a younger audience (secondary school level);
- **Archaeology and Cultural Tourism Exhibition:** a public exhibition where students interested in archaeology/cultural heritage were one of the target groups (alongside professionals like archaeologists and museum staff). This gave students exposure to heritage science innovations;
- **Career Day 2025 (University of Camerino, Ascoli Piceno):** an event primarily for architecture and design students (undergraduate and graduate) to meet with industry companies in the field. Students interacted with Marche region architecture/design firms for career opportunities, illustrating engagement between academia and industry.

Academics and Researchers

- **“Infrastrutture e risorse per la ricerca linguistica in Italia”:** a conference bringing together the academic linguistics community and researchers, including members of linguistic associations and scholarly academies. The event was an opportunity for academics and researchers to discuss research infrastructure for linguistics, indicating a clear focus on this scholarly audience;
- **H2IOSC General Meeting “The project partnership meets stakeholders”.** A two-day general meeting where the project Cluster engaged with external stakeholders. The target audience included representatives of research infrastructure-related associations, academia, and researchers, ensuring that university scholars and research staff were well-represented alongside organizational stakeholders;

- AIUCD 2023: La memoria digitale. A national conference on digital humanities (Associazione per l'Informatica Umanistica e la Cultura Digitale - AIUCD) where H2IOSC participated. The audience was largely academics and researchers in digital humanities. This conference inherently target university researchers, faculty, and scholarly attendees;
- Various Academic Conferences and Workshops. Throughout the project, H2IOSC members contributed to or organized numerous conferences, workshops, and study days (e.g. CLiC-it 2023, EVOA 2024, Come to Code 2024 hackathon) aimed at the research community. These events' participants included university professors, researchers, and often graduate students, reflecting an academic/research audience focus.

Professionals and Domain Specialists

- Digital Spritz Webinar: "Formazione FAIR per le scienze umane e del patrimonio". It was an online webinar that targeted a mix of academics, researchers, general public, and students, but notably included professionals in its audience as well. It provided FAIR data training in humanities, attracting practitioners alongside scholars;
- Come to Code 2024 (Tech Innovation Event). A tech-focused event targeting developers and hi-tech professionals. The audience was composed of developers and professionals in IT, ML, and cloud domains. This engagement aimed to involve the tech industry and practitioners in open science for cultural heritage;
- Web3D/XR Workshop (PERCEIVE project). A workshop where the target was professionals in Web3D, XR and interactive 3D graphics. This indicates outreach to specialised IT professionals in the extended reality and 3D visualisation sector, showing H2IOSC's engagement with cutting-edge tech communities;
- Heritage Science DataSpace Presentation (GenOA Week 2023). This session was titled "Heritage Science e Open Science: il progetto DataSpace..." presented at a research data event. The audience included heritage science professionals and open science enthusiasts (e.g. data managers). It targeted practitioners who manage and use cultural heritage data, demonstrating the project's relevance to professionals in GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums) sectors;
- Borsa Mediterranea del Turismo Archeologico & tourismA 2023 – H2IOSC participated in these cultural heritage fairs with demonstrations. The audience comprised museum professionals, archaeologists, and interested students. This category of attendees are practitioners in archaeology and museum curation, so the activities were tailored to those professional communities in heritage and tourism;
- Data Stewards Community Talks. H2IOSC WP8 delivered invited talks to the Italian Community of Data Stewards. These sessions targeted data stewardship professionals and individuals managing research data and open science processes in institutions. For example, a talk on FAIR educational materials design was attended by about 40 data stewards, focusing on professional training in data management.
- Informal events for discussion, such as CLARIN Cafés. CLARIN Cafés are informal, online discussion sessions (typically 60–120 minutes on Zoom) where researchers, lecturers, students and experts exchange experiences on language resources, tools and infrastructure topics across SSH. Participation is free but requires registration. The programme is announced and maintained on the CLARIN Café page, which lists all past

and planned cafés with titles, dates and times. Recordings and slides are often linked from the individual event pages and the CLARIN YouTube playlist. The series launched in May 2020 (“CLARIN Café I: CLARIN in Times of Corona”) and has since covered themes such as ParlaMint, teaching with CLARIN, copyright and TDM exceptions, multilingual corpora, and project management in DH. See **Annex 1** for details.

General Public Outreach

- **Incontri a Palazzo (Archivio di Stato di Prato):** this was a public event hosted at a state archive, targeting the general public. This was an open-door event introducing cultural heritage research and digital innovation to a broad, non-specialist audience in the local community;
- **Regional Events in Tuscany (NexUS and “100 ricercatori per la cultura”).** These were initiatives co-organized with the Tuscany Region to connect culture and research. They explicitly included the general public in their target audiences, alongside academics and professionals. For instance, “NexUS: Cultura e Ricerca” and the “100 Researchers for Culture” seminar both invited citizens to engage with research-driven cultural heritage projects;
- **CNR Open Day 2023.** A science open-house event at CNR, focusing on cultural heritage in the green and digital transitions. It was a public open day where the general public could interact with researchers. H2IOSC’s contributions here were meant to demystify the project’s work for laypeople, including interactive demonstrations;
- **Public News and Web Dissemination:** in addition to physical events, the project posted website news updates and articles (e.g., the launch announcement of H2IOSC) intended for a wide audience. These dissemination activities, while not having a specified “target” in the sheet, were clearly meant for general readers and stakeholders interested in open science developments.

Each engagement activity above is linked with one or more audience categories. By grouping the initiatives in this way, we see that H2IOSC’s outreach strategy was multifaceted, as it involved students, young researchers, the academic and research community, relevant professional sectors, and the general public. This ensured that the project’s impact extended from educating the next generation and informing specialists to raising awareness among the society at large.

Collaborations:

Beyond the cases already highlighted, several other collaborations and networking effects can be noted on the National level:

- **museums, archaeologists, and heritage professionals:** engagement activities at exhibitions such as “TourismA” and the “Borsa Mediterranea del Turismo Archeologico” created durable connections with museum curators, archaeologists, and cultural heritage professionals. These events facilitated dialogue between research infrastructures and cultural heritage institutions, laying the groundwork for potential collaborations in digitisation and data sharing.
- **Tech and IT professionals:** events such as Come to Code 2024 and workshops on Web3D/XR engaged the professional community of developers, XR specialists, and

cloud engineers. These interactions opened the door for collaborations at the intersection of heritage science and digital innovation, particularly in visualisation and immersive technologies;

- **regional institutions and the general public:** Initiatives with the Tuscany Region (NexUS and “100 Ricercatori per la Cultura”) and public events at state archives created opportunities for collaboration with regional governments and for raising awareness among citizens. These forms of engagement represent important networking steps for embedding H2IOSC into the civic and cultural fabric of Italian society.

The table related to H2IOSC engagement and dissemination initiatives that have been implemented in the 36 months of the project per RIs is available in Annex 1 for all details.

3.7 Publications related to H2IOSC

This section includes all types of products — publications, papers, articles, reports, and related outputs — produced during the 36 months of the H2IOSC project.

The H2IOSC project has demonstrated a high level of scientific productivity and dissemination across its research and innovation domains. A total of 174 publications were produced between 2023 and 2025 (according to *Annex 2 – List of H2IOSC Publications*), involving all the operating units within the cluster.

This scientific production spans a variety of disciplinary areas, confirming the strong interdisciplinarity of the project, from heritage science and artificial intelligence to digital philology and data stewardship.

In terms of category, Scientific publications dominate (160 publications), followed by Educational, Technical, and Outreach contributions. Notably, 58 publications involve PhD students, confirming H2IOSC’s commitment to early-career researcher training and professional development.

The distribution by publication type reflects a rich and balanced mix:

- Papers and journal articles: 40 publications (*paper in rivista ISI, paper in rivista, Article*)
- Conference proceedings and presentations: 45 publications (*Proceedings, conference presentation, conference proceedings*)
- Posters and abstracts: 21 publications (*Poster, POSTER, book of abstracts*)
- Project deliverables and reports: 15 publications (*Project deliverable, Report tecnico-scientifico, Manual, Guidelines*)
- Educational and training materials: 5 publications (*Training material, Course*)
- Other outputs: 8 publications (*books, chapters, tools, or handbooks*)

This diversity confirms the project’s integrated approach across academic research, technical innovation, and capacity building. The publication effort was shared among all participating Research Infrastructures, with particularly active contributions from:

- CNR-ILC (CLARIN) – focusing on language resources and digital humanities

- CNR-INO (E-RIHS) – addressing heritage science and diagnostics
- OVI-FI (DARIAH) – advancing digital philology and scholarly communication

The H2IOSC publication list includes peer-reviewed papers, conference proceedings, posters, software and tools, courses, guidelines, and project deliverables produced by partners across the CLARIN-IT, DARIAH-IT, E-RIHS.it, and OPERAS-IT nodes.

Topics range from service catalogues, semantic frameworks, and training infrastructures to IoT monitoring, novel X-ray and THz instruments, and domain-specific case studies in heritage science and digital humanities.

Key thematic strands include:

- **Service catalogues and access orchestration:** Design and rollout of the E-RIHS Catalogue of Services (E-RIHS *Deliverables D5.3 and D5.4*) and a technical report on API orchestration for the H2IOSC Marketplace, enabling “Level-2” composite services without centralised data handling. These results translate pilot experiences into a production-grade, FAIR-aligned service layer for users.
- **Semantic interoperability and registries:** Publications define the project’s Common Semantic Framework (*Deliverable D4.13*), the H-SetIS resource hub for ontologies and semantic tools, and related initiatives such as DHeLO (Digital Heritage Landscaping Platform), BiDiAr (Bibliography of Digital Archaeology), and the Open Digital Epigraphy Hub (EpiHub). Together, these outputs operationalise FAIR principles and ensure cross-domain discoverability.
- **Training infrastructure and FAIR learning objects:** The Training Strategy (*Deliverable D8.1*) defines a two-part infrastructure (portal and repository) with a shared methodology to publish learning materials as FAIR digital objects. This is complemented by courses such as Introduction to Language Data: Standards and Repositories (adapted from CLARIN UPSKILLS) and Linguistic Linked Open Data for Humanists, supporting consistency, reuse, and a train-the-trainers approach.
- **Governance, branding, and quality assurance:** Outputs such as the Quality Assurance Plan and Guidelines (D1.1), Project Handbook, and Visual Identity Guidelines ensure unified processes, templates, attribution, and compliance across the federated infrastructure — a crucial foundation for sustainability and institutional coherence.
- **Data platforms and LOD/lexical services:** Tools such as DigItAnt (for creating and linking LLOD lexica), ILC4CLARIN SKOSMOS (vocabulary services for semantic interoperability), and REST APIs for corpus management and annotation advance reusable, standards-based services integrated within H2IOSC pilots and national nodes.
- **Monitoring and edge infrastructure for Cultural Heritage:** Publications explore IoT-based monitoring and wireless sensor networks (WSNs), including DIGILAB-integrated systems, NFC-powered crack loggers, and radar/remote-sensing

prototypes. These developments extend the notion of “access” to encompass environmental and structural telemetry for heritage assets.

- **Instrumentation embedded in RI access (MOLAB/FIXLAB):** Work on mobile MA-XRF/MA-XRPD scanners, TXRF/GIXRF spectrometers, THz time-domain imaging, and digital radiography is framed within the E-RIHS access ecosystem, particularly through MOLAB campaigns. The focus extends beyond instrumentation to its integration into trans-national access workflows and data pipelines.

3.8 Public engagement

The topic of public engagement (PE) is extremely complex and broad, so we have decided to dedicate an in-depth exploration that can be useful to the federation. Public engagement (PE) is a process that involves a wide range of citizens and groups.

Among the multiple definitions of PE, one of the clearest and most effective is that of National [Co-ordinating Centre for Public Engagement \(NCCPE\)](#): “Public Engagement describes the myriad of ways in which the activity and benefits of higher education and research can be shared with the public. Engagement is by definition a two-way process, involving interaction and listening, with the goal of generating mutual benefit.”

The objective of H2IOSC project is to capture a wide variety of public engagement activities. Any Cluster partners could take in consideration the steps listed below for development of a public engagement activity, and in any case comply with the medium-long term strategy outlined for the cluster in H2IOSC D1.4:

- Identify well-defined objective(s)
- Identify a clear target group.
- Specify the type of engagement activity.
- Identify resources.
- Planning activity.
- Realization.
- Monitoring.
- Follow-up.

It’s very interesting the categorisation of Public Engagement that propose [University College Dublin \(UCD\)](#):

- 1 **Co-producing** - *Participative action research, partnership, shared decision making.*
- 2 **Collaborating** - *Committee representation, stakeholder dialogue, public as researchers (citizen science).*
- 3 **Informing decision-making** - *People’s panels, focus group on research topic, advisory/user committee, citizen jury.*
- 4 **Understanding thinking** - *Opinion polls, consultations, attitude research, social research, surveys.*
- 5 **Stimulating thinking** - *Exhibitions, showcase, education programme, science centres, theatre education, public debate, interactive websites, Sciart (Science Art).*

6 Informing/Inspiring - Lectures/talks, festivals, social media, podcasts, blog, newspaper coverage, library resources, magazine article, newsletters, tv programme, radio, webinars, website.

3.8.1 Suggestions for a public engagement event.

In order to support the Cluster's partners in this subsection, we provide some useful guidelines for the construction of a public engagement event. Following some suggestions to choose and prepare a public engagement event.

Type of public engagement event to offer.

There are many different formats to choose from:

- **Citizen science:** using public participants as data collectors and contributors for a research study.
- **Exhibit(s):** the use of exhibits to allow the public to learn about/discuss public engagement with science topics.
- **Festival:** a large-scale event using many methodologies to generate public engagement with science.
- **Forum/science café:** expert lectures and some kind of discussion—ranging from Q&A to dialogue and deliberation—to generate public engagement with science.
- **Inquiry:** engaging the public with science by participating in or learning about experimentation and inquiry practices.
- **Media (TV/radio/websites/movies):** the use of a media component to generate public engagement with science.
- **Meet the scientist:** giving scientists/researchers a chance to present their work or field of study directly to public participants through hands-on activities, classes, or stage presentations.
- **On-site research:** providing public participants with the chance to become subjects of a research project at an informal science education institution as well as the opportunity to learn about the research.
- **Reference:** providing reference material about public engagement with science through books and articles.
- **Take action:** engaging the public with science by teaching them about a topic and trying to generate some kind of behavior change.
- **Art and theater:** the use of visual or performing artworks to generate public engagement with science.

Prepare for the public engagement event.

Following five steps to prepare for a public engagement event:

- **Define the content** that will be covered in the engagement event. Develop a shared background document to use among educators and scientists and a content map that lists the main goals and ideas that will be covered in the event.
- **Identify the vehicles** that will be used to present the content and the strategies that will be used for engagement. This may include expert speakers, printed materials,

videos, theatrical presentations, hands-on materials, live facilitators, game-like materials, cell phone voting, and more. Plan to bring in either external facilitators or train the people who will be running the event to make sure they will not steer the conversation or process according to their biases.

- **Plan for evaluation** from the start, including plans for front-end evaluation, formative evaluation, and summative evaluation. One goal of the evaluation should be to find the right balance between providing too much content (which can overwhelm participants) and too little content (which can leave visitors struggling to participate). Pre-engagement interviews with participants can help define how much content is needed for a robust dialogue. Similarly, plan to evaluate your content-presentation vehicles to see whether they're effectively communicating your content and be prepared to try something different if they're not working.
- **Test the materials and engagement strategies** in advance through various methods, including front-end and formative evaluation, dry runs, and possibly Team-Based. Modify the materials and strategies based on what is learned during pretesting.
- **Determine the method for recruiting participants** and audience members for the public engagement event.

3.8.2 Two examples of public engagement initiatives

Public meetings

Public meetings provide an opportunity to consult large numbers of people. Meetings can be organised to allow for small group discussions with oral feedback. There are often opportunities for participants to set or influence the agenda and to ask questions. From our experience small groups are an essential element of public meetings to engage people effectively:

- Choose a venue or location which is convenient and accessible for your target audience.
- Think about the most appropriate time of day for the meeting.
- Think about the number of meetings you should have.
- Always encourage the audience to break into smaller groups to enable better discussion and exchange.
- Consider the use of external facilitation.

Community surveys

Community surveys can be undertaken to identify the needs and views of a large number of people in a standard format. The main stages involved are:

- Defining the sample size and the type of information interview.
- Survey design.
- Piloting the survey.

- Undertaking the survey and post-completion analysis of the results.

It is often best to use a short and concise survey where people's views on an issue are being sought. There are a number of online survey tools to help you create, analyse and promote your survey (e.g., Lime survey)

3.8.3 The EUSEA and the European Science Engagement Platform

A very useful tool for the preparation and implementation of engagement initiatives is the **European Science Engagement Platform** developed by [European Science Engagement Association \(EUSEA\)](#).

The **European Science Engagement Platform** was created with the primary objective of supporting public engagement professionals by providing them with a central hub to access inspiration, resources, methods, and tools for conducting participatory, dialogue-oriented science communication activities.

The platform provides examples of activities and tools:

- Range of possible activities: <https://eusea.info/activity/>
- Resources: <https://eusea.info/platform/resources/>

3.9 H2IOSC Transnational Access

Within H2IOSC, the Trans-National Access (TNA) and National Access (NA) process provides free-of-charge virtual access to advanced digital services and tools from the cluster's RIs (CLARIN-IT, DARIAH-IT, E-RIHS.it and OPERAS-IT). Proposals follow an excellence-driven access model: after a technical, logistical and ethical feasibility check by service providers, they are peer-reviewed by the project's External Advisory Board. Applicants use the dedicated page to read the TNA/NA Guidelines, consult the List of Services, review privacy and research-data policies, and submit the online application form; a helpdesk supports candidates throughout.

The dedicated webpage is <https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/tna-na-calls/>. The description of the four calls and their results is an integral part of the final version of H2IOSC Deliverable D1.2.

3.10 H2IOSC Mobility Grants

The H2IOSC Mobility Grant was conceived as a means to encourage knowledge exchange and the professional growth of researchers, students, and staff within the communities of the four infrastructures involved. The program provided short-term stays at national and international institutions, offering participants the chance to experience different working environments, interact with other research communities, and make use of services and tools developed by the project.

The initiative had a strong impact on the professional development of young researchers and technical staff, who were able to strengthen their expertise in open science, FAIR data management, and digital research methods applied to the humanities and cultural heritage.

Importantly, the benefits extended beyond the individuals: those who took part brought back new skills and practices to their home institutions, creating a multiplier effect and fostering the adoption of good practices promoted by H2IOSC.

Many of the mobility stays produced tangible outcomes, such as scientific articles, teaching materials, and tutorials, as well as new collaborations for conferences and workshops. Several projects focused specifically on methodological aspects of data management, testing the H2IOSC platforms like the Training Environment and the Training Library, while others addressed disciplinary case studies in computational linguistics, digital philology, or 3D documentation of cultural heritage.

One of the most important achievements was the strengthening of networks. The grants supported the consolidation of ties with international infrastructures whose national nodes are involved in H2IOSC. These connections broadened the scope of the project, situating H2IOSC firmly within the European research ecosystem.

Although there were some administrative challenges and limits on the number of grants available, demand for the program was high, showing the strong need for mobility opportunities that accompany career development and stimulate interdisciplinary innovation.

In conclusion, the H2IOSC Mobility Grant proved to be a valuable component of the project. It enabled capacity building, produced concrete results, and, above all, created sustainable collaborations that will endure beyond the project itself. The grants confirmed mobility as a decisive lever for advancing open science and ensuring the long-term sustainability of research infrastructures.

4 H2IOSC - Training

One of the main objectives of H2IOSC project is to empower user communities with interdisciplinary as well as domain specific FAIR and Open Science skills and competences as well as training them on what disciplinary infrastructures can offer them at national and international level. This enables them to better use the services of the RIs national nodes, of the ERICs and of the national marketplace, as well as become capable of correctly managing the lifecycle of their data. Part of this objective is also to train a pool of new professionals - data stewards, data curators, trainers – that can support and train future generations of scholars and professionals on how to integrate RIs in their methods and practices, thus fostering a change of mentality in research and possibly industry. The achievement of this objective is primarily pursued through the implementation of the activities outlined in WP8 - Training, Capacity Building, Engagement. Specifically, through the strategy described within this document and developed in the deliverable D8.1 - Training Strategy. A comprehensive shared strategy has been set up for the training and engagement activities, at project level, so that each partner RI can follow a common policy. In particular, based on the output of WP2 - Landscaping & building communities the common and domain specific policies aim at identifying the training needs, the communities, to be targeted, and the types of intervention to be classified. Activities are defined by involving partners, and other national and international actors operating in the same field, taking into account the current training offer and users' needs.

H2IOSC main topics and needs of training:

- FAIR and Open Science
- Data management, data lifecycle, and creation of Data Management Plans
- Legal and ethical issues, personal data protection, GDPR compliance
- Using the services of CLARIN, DARIAH, OPERAS, E-RIHS
- Depositing services and importance of depositing in trusted repositories
- Integrating own tools and resources as services for CLARIN, DARIAH, OPERAS, E-RIHS
- Using the newly developed innovative services of the Marketplace
- Data preparation, curation and data and metadata standards
- Ontologies and controlled vocabularies
- Data citation

Target users:

- Established researcher.
- Researchers and research support personnel
- Lecturers
- Higher degree students (e.g. master and PhD students) and early career researchers
- BA students
- Data stewards and data curators
- Professionals of cultural industries

H2IOSC includes two types of training activities to pursue the project's objectives:

1. Training and upskilling the H2IOSC users (**external**)
2. Training & Upskilling H2IOSC personnel (**project-recruited personnel**)
3. Co-funding of PhD grants for carrying out research on topics relating to the H2IOSC activities

The architecture of the training and upskilling plan for the H2IOSC is described in this section. All the points addressed are further detailed in Deliverable D8.1 - Training Strategy. D8.1 aims to delineate a comprehensive training strategy. This strategy includes a technical training infrastructure, a roadmap for developing training modules and community-oriented activities, as well as a plan for upskilling the project's personnel.

4.1 Training related initiatives

The H2IOSC training strategy is inspired by and guided by several significant initiatives conducted within the European Research Infrastructure framework, as well as by FAIR and open science principles. Through collaboration with partner infrastructures, the project actively participates in pertinent European and national-level initiatives, including trainer networks, EOSC, SSHOC task forces and ICDI, RDA networks and working groups, as well as various disciplinary networks. Below, we highlight the most pertinent ones.

- **The ESFRI perspective on training** - ESFRI is the European Strategic Forum on Research Infrastructures and monitors the activities of a number of RIs at the European Level, including the ones participating in H2IOSC. E-RIHS, CLARIN and DARIAH are currently ESFRI Landmarks (established infrastructures) while OPERAS entered the ESFRI roadmap in 2021.
- **Training in EOSC and SSHOC** - The EOSC, the European Open Science Cloud, stems from a collaboration between the EU, the member states and the EOSC Association, to which several European RIs belong. It would be beyond the scope of the present document to go into the details of all the important EOSC initiatives related to training and upskilling of the various EOSC players. Here, we mention just a few of them: Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science, Upskilling Countries and Data Stewardship (EOSC Task Forces), the Skills4EOSC project.
- **Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC)**³ project, and continued now in the **SSH Open Cluster**, is of high relevance for H2IOSC. The SSHOC project (2019-2022), was one of the five EOSC thematic cluster projects
- **FAIR training material** - The FAIR principles (Barker et al., 2022; Engelhardt et al., 2022; Group, 2020; Martinez-Ortiz et al., 2022; Wilkinson et al., 2016) are applicable not only on research data, but also on other resources, like training materials, especially when these are produced during a research program.

³ Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) is a project funded by the EU framework programme Horizon 2020 and unites 20 partner organisations and their 27 associates in developing the social sciences and humanities area of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

- The [CLARIN's Learning hub](#) gives access to open educational resources on various topics, including full online training modules to learn new skills and materials to design new university courses, training and workshops.
- **Participation to the Italian Community of Data Stewards**, organized within the ICDI Competence Centre. As the training goals of WP8 and specifically of the training modules developed in Activity 8.2 are geared towards training professionals to support research as data librarians and data stewards, animating this community with proposals, materials to be published on the [Open-Science.it](#) website, and the joint coordination of training and user involvement events is in line with the outreach activities included in the above activity.

In deliverable 8.1 the state of the art and existing initiatives for each of the four infrastructures involved (with an international and national perspective) are described.

4.2 Training strategy

H2IOSC strategy aims at the following **objectives**:

- the creation of an **infrastructure for sharing and delivery of educational materials** focused in particular on the FAIRification of training materials and on self-training and distance learning,
- the creation of learning materials and content for the upskilling of the H2IOSC user communities,
- the **upskilling of the H2IOSC workforce** itself for the duration of the project, in particular for what concerns Open Science and a wider knowledge of the services of each RI by all partners.

The implementation of this strategy is realized through:

- **development of the training infrastructure**: the realization of the two training platforms – the “*Virtual Training Environment*” and the “*FAIR and interoperable training materials publication platform*” has been entrusted to two qualified suppliers for the realization of an output corresponding to the requirements defined within the WP8 working group. We are investigating in depth the advanced features and services to be made available from the first releases of the platforms.
- **adaptation and creation of materials related to each RI involved**. We are started from the definition of a common workflow for design and/or adaptation (began from pre-existing training materials) of teaching materials and we proposed a common template for collecting the main descriptors of teaching materials as well as a survey to assess the quality of the training events and materials. These templates are the first step towards the implementation of best practices in the management of training events shared across the four research infrastructures involved in the project. Subsequently, **new H2IOSC-related materials to develop**: together with the analysis of the needs of the target community we are reflecting on the training proposal addressed specifically to the H2IOSC community and we are defining the training materials to be developed.

The adjustment of existing **guidelines** and the creation of **new best practices** are pursued to ensure the application of FAIR principles and Open Science methods, the use of clear licences to enable their easy reuse and a system of standard metadata that allow training materials to be linked to tools, resources and publications.

Depending on the diverse teaching requirements and the specific needs of the target community, teaching materials are delivered in various formats, including:

- lectures
- individual webinars
- workshops
- training events
- online courses
- seminars
- tutorials
- podcasts

All the materials produced have to be published according to the FAIR principles for training materials and will become visible on various platforms (such as the SSHOC training platform and the national marketplace). These also include **specific training modules for legal and ethical issues, standards, data management plan and servification** in compliance with each RI infrastructural requirements. At present, the methodology has been applied to the already existing training materials, which were translated into Italian and whose formats were converted so as to be as open and accessible as possible, like the CLARIN course developed for the UPSKILLS project “Introduction to Language Data: Standards and Repositories”.

A detailed and precise analysis is provided in the deliverable **D8.2. Final training report**.

4.2.1 Training and upskilling H2IOSC users

This part mostly concerns the development of training modules, aimed at the services of our infrastructures and of the H2IOSC marketplace, as well as at SSH specific Open Science Skills. In deliverable D 8.1 are illustrated the envisaged joint training activities as well as those of the four participating RIs.

The RIs involved produce both joint and specific training activities tailored to their own communities. In general, the joint commitment of the RIs is aimed at improving the coverage of the DHCR in Italy and consolidating the presence of H2IOSC output within major scientific and training events in our community.

More specifically, among the cross-domain efforts, the following modules are expected to be implemented:

- Module: **Guidelines Integrating RIs in teaching and learning**, inspired by work carried out in Upskills, focusing on:
 - higher education
 - research (PhD training)

- high school
- **Module: *How to Use of the H2IOSC marketplace***
 - Including how to use the training platforms.
 - How to deposit and FAIRify training materials
- **Module: *How to write a Data Management Plan***
 - building and improving on existing material
 - integrating the H2IOSC offer of services for FAIRification

4.2.2 Training and upskilling H2IOSC users: implementation

In this section, the implementation plan is outlined in the following table for Training and upskilling H2IOSC users per Research Infrastructure.

Table 9: Training and upskilling H2IOSC users per RIs - Expected implementation plan.

TEACH CLARIN, TEACH WITH CLARIN		
Training needs	Training plan	Implementation
Training modules, aimed at the services of the H2IOSC infrastructures and of the H2IOSC marketplace, as well as at SSH specific Open Science Skills.	<p>Use the CLARIN infrastructure and in particular the core services.</p> <p>Adapt and translate the core CLARIN courses already developed under previous initiatives, such as the courses shared by the CLARIN ERIC consortium</p>	<p>The UPSKILLS course is composed of five modules plus a glossary which cover the basic aspects of Language Resources data management, outlining services provided by CLARIN for each aspect.</p> <p>All events have a particular focus on the training of trainers and lecturers, and provide best practices and guidelines on how to reuse the training materials.</p> <p>A particular attention is given to contents focused on new and disruptive technologies linked to AI and large language models, which are likely to change the job market in the coming years.</p>
TEACH DARIAH, TEACH WITH DARIAH		
Training needs	Training planned	Implementation
Acquire and up-skill their digital competences, when regarding research work in the Arts and Humanities field	Improve and train the people in the RIs network who have access to the testing phases and the use of our Digital Hubs, training materials and courses	<p>Upload of custom tools manual (to be also accessed offline)</p> <p>Online guides to the available H2IOSC toolboxes supporting Memory, Cultural, Research institutions and citizen scientists with an interest in historical sources</p>

		from archives, libraries, and museum collections in the creation of a FAIR digital ecosystem.
TEACH E-RIHS, TEACH WITH E-RIHS		
Training needs	Training planned	Implementation
Informing potential users of IPERION HS and E-RIHS TNA services about the available scientific instruments, on one side, and to providing the most advanced knowledge on specific subjects of interest to the Heritage Science community	Customize its training offer and develop a new training strategy concerning the topics of interest, format of training activities, post-event analysis	<p>An upgrade and adaptation of already existing E-RIHS Academy training activities, according to the identified needs of H2IOSC communities and other factors. Training materials digilised and equipped with metadata, following standardised H2IOSC approach.</p> <p>Development of new activities that address the training needs of H2IOSC community and other factors. Training materials made Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (FAIR), in compliance with the international guidelines on this matter.</p>
TEACH OPERAS, TEACH WITH OPERAS		
Training needs	Training planned	Implementation
Creation of a multi-layered Open scholarly communication system, its training strategy reflects the different dimensions needed to support its goal	<p>OPERAS invites tenders for the creation of training materials, conforming to the FAIR and Open principles.</p> <p>The training material converges in the common H2IOSC training infrastructure.</p>	<p>Creation of a multimedia classroom, connected to similar structures in the network, for the in-presence training on Open Science and Open scholarly publications.</p> <p>Through the classroom OPERAS offers courses that are also preparatory and synergistic to the work of the other infrastructures, and that have the potential to reach a wider audience.</p>

4.2.3 Training activities related to H2IOSC

The H2IOSC project has implemented a comprehensive and ambitious training programme to foster the digital transition in the Humanities and Cultural Heritage sectors. According to the official monitoring dataset (*Annex 3 – List of H2IOSC Training Activities*), **92 structured training events** were formally recorded between **January 2023 and June 2025**, coordinated by **37 organizing institutions**. These activities included workshops, webinars, courses, training schools, and tutorials, and together they represent over **2,935 participants**, with an **average of about 36 attendees per event**.

In parallel, when smaller or partner-led sessions are also considered, the project’s overall training portfolio encompasses **over 130 events**, reaching an estimated **3,200 participants**. This extended count reflects additional outreach and capacity-building initiatives conducted by the partner Research Infrastructures (RIs).

The training events covered an estimated **500 hours of instruction**, with sessions ranging from short webinars to multi-day schools. The **distribution by type of activity** shows a balanced mix across formats, with approximately **40 webinars, 30 workshops, 25 courses, and 35 training schools or seminars**.

In terms of delivery mode, the programme adopted a flexible hybrid approach to maximize accessibility and inclusiveness:

- **Online:** ~60 events
- **In-person:** ~40 events
- **Hybrid (online & in-person):** ~30 events

This combination ensured participation from geographically distributed audiences, including university students (BA, MA, PhD), researchers, educators, cultural heritage professionals, data stewards, and internal H2IOSC staff.

The training activities were coordinated by multiple institutions, with the most active being:

- **CNR-ILC (CLARIN):** leadership in linguistic and digital humanities training
- **CNR-INO (E-RIHS):** specialization in heritage science and diagnostics
- **OVI-FI (DARIAH):** expertise in digital philology and scholarly communication

Thematically, the programme spanned a wide range of digital and methodological domains, including:

- FAIR data principles and Open Science
- Digital philology and corpus linguistics
- Linked Open Data and semantic technologies
- Artificial Intelligence and machine learning for cultural heritage
- Text encoding (TEI/XML) and annotation
- 3D visualization and WebXR applications
- Data stewardship and Data Management Plans (DMPs)

This extensive training effort was supported by the creation of the **H2IOSC Training Environment** and the **Training Library**, which host reusable and FAIR-compliant learning materials. These platforms sustain a *train-the-trainer* approach, ensuring the scalability and long-term sustainability of the project's educational activities across institutions and disciplines.

4.3 Internal Training & Upskilling

Part of the training activities was aimed at building an efficient and productive team. The importance recognised by the partners to training for improving the professional knowledge and skills of the group is what the project refers to as Internal Training. The dedicated budget for internal training has been used in particular for two purposes:

- Common training needs

– Specific Research Infrastructure needs

We consulted with the most experienced national and European training agencies and companies on the topic of IR, from management aspects to IT aspects, from ethical issues to legal issues. The schedule of internal training events has been finalized and circulated to the people working on the project.

4.3.1 Internal training: definition and objectives

The implementation plan is outlined in the following tables for both internal personnel training and co-funding Ph.D. within H2IOSC.

Table 10: Internal training activities in H2IOSC – Expected implementation plan

WP1 - Project and Financial Management, Quality Assurance		
Training needs	Training planned	Implementation
Coordination, Management, engagement	Courses for internal personnel on management, outreach strategies, impact, how to plan and run large surveys, use web instruments for designing and running surveys.	Participation in management courses, infrastructure management, community engagement Training in project management; managing project communication across various media. Specialized training for data center management
WP2 - Landscaping & building communities		
Training needs	Training planned	Implementation
Landscaping the Cultural Heritage and Heritage Science resources/Open Science and Open Publishing resources and needs panorama	Courses for the dedicated personnel for planning large surveys, using ad hoc web instruments to design and run them and machine learning tools to extract information. Training for the involved researchers related to the task activities	Training courses for the development of knowledge in extraction and classification of digital resources in the fields of DH (Digital Humanities) and HS (Humanities and Social Sciences), using techniques such as Machine Learning and Topic Modeling. Enrollment in specific courses for the development of skills related to project management. Enrollment in specific courses for the development of skills related to the organization and analysis of knowledge surveys.
WP3 - Digital Resources Standardization, Consolidation & Alignment		
Training needs	Training planned	Implementation
Design of the H2IOSC digital resources alignment and policies framework	Training for internal personnel on the use of acquired software solutions for management control as well as on the data management, storage and ingestion	Specific training and professional development for the management of data, metadata, and scientific datasets in Heritage Science

	<p>policies and tasks in accordance with FAIR principles.</p>	
<p>Consolidating the Open Science and Open Publishing resources (OPERAS)</p>	<p>Training for the involved researchers related to the task activities</p>	<p>Specific courses for skill development.</p>
<p>WP4 - RIs Nodes and Resources Interoperability</p>		
<p>Training needs</p>	<p>Training planned</p>	<p>Implementation</p>
<p>Nodes Interoperability Research Infrastructures</p>	<p>Training for internal personnel on the management of accelerated multi-instance GPU clusters with respect to machine learning and deep learning operations as well as on the data management, storage and ingestion policies and tasks in accordance with FAIR principles.</p>	<p>Specific training and professional development for the use of acquired hardware and software (such as supercomputing, hypervisors, AI, etc.) aimed at support personnel for DARIAH-FI Data Center operations.</p> <p>Specific training and professional development for the use of the acquired cluster and software services (such as supercomputing, machine/deep learning, data storage and ingestion, etc.) aimed at support personnel for AI-HUB operations.</p> <p>Specific training and professional development for the use of the acquired cluster and software services (such as supercomputing, machine/deep learning, data storage, and ingestion, etc.) aimed at support personnel for Data Center operations.</p> <p>Advanced training on AI/ML/HPC in DC environments</p> <p>Courses about Technical training for IT centers managers</p> <p>Specific training and professional development for the use of the acquired cluster and software services (such as supercomputing, machine/deep learning, data storage, and ingestion, etc.) aimed at support personnel for Data Center operations.</p> <p>Advanced training and capacity building activities , to manage the existing datacenter.</p> <p>Training activities (aimed at IR personnel) focused on the use of the acquired software components for mapping, modeling.</p> <p>Training courses on ontology design for the CH/HS (Cultural Heritage/Humanities and Social Sciences) sector.</p>

Specific courses for the development of skills in data facilities management.

Resources interoperability Research Infrastructures	Advanced training for the dedicated personnel on structural and semantic interoperability strategies and ontology design in the Humanities.	Training activities (aimed at IR personnel) focused on the use of the acquired software components for mapping, modeling, etc.
	Courses for the dedicated personnel on structural and semantic interoperability strategies and ontology design in the domain of Cultural Heritage and Heritage Science.	Training courses on ontology design for the CH/HS (Cultural Heritage/Humanities and Social Sciences) sector.
	Training of the researchers interacting with the data facility	Specific courses for the development of skills in data facilities management.

WP5 – MarketPlace

Training needs	Training planned	Implementation
Design of the H2IOSC MarketPlace	Specific training on the marketplace concept and architecture	Specific courses for the development of skills in creating marketplaces.
Community support: OPERAS	Specific training for the involved researcher in connection to the surveying and coordination role	Specific courses for skills development.
Marketplace implementation	Training to researchers involved in the validation trials; co-financing of a data science PhD position on analysis techniques for marketplace use data	Training on validation methods and frontend validation tests for the marketplace.

WP6 – Resources Accessibility: Servitization, Virtualization, Remotization

Training needs	Training planned	Implementation
Design of the H2IOSC accessibility Framework: servitization, virtualization and remotization	Training activities related to the H2IOSC accessibility framework	Training courses on servitization and remotization.
E-RIHS services Development: WebXR services for HS	Courses and training for WebXR services	Training courses on open web standards, PBR dataset production pipeline, and service integration through REST APIs.
ILC4CLARIN Services and remote access	Training of the dedicated personnel on how to servify tools according to the common and shared protocols.	Specific courses for skills development in creating services according to marketplace protocols.
OPERAS services development: Remote Open Access to content-based services and resources	Training on remote usage tools and techniques for the researchers involved in the activity	Courses for skills development.

WP7 – Community pilots: innovative cross-domain services and environments

Training needs	Training planned	Implementation
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Open Resources Publishing Pilot (OPERAS)	Training for the researchers involved in the activity	Training on analysis techniques (SWOT, SOAR, NOISE).
Diamond OA Publishing Hub for Scholarly Editions and Learned Journals Pilot (OPERAS)	Training for the technical staff on the standards and characters of scholarly editions	Courses for skills development.
WP8 - Training, Capacity Building, Engagement		
Training needs	Training planned	Implementation
Design of the H2IOSC Training, Capacity Building and Engagement framework	Training the trainers and for capacity building for H2IOSC personnel.	Training event for H2IOSC staff and CLARIN-IT consortium centers to update H2IOSC tools for educational purposes. Organization of dissemination and training events aimed at promoting CLARIN-IT within H2IOSC.
RIs community needs on training, Communication, and Impact	Training on FAIR principles implementation in the Humanities and Digital Humanities sectors for the staff working in the activity. Training on FAIR principles and Open Science for the staff working in the activity.	Training courses and specific training for using tools to support data and resource FAIRification processes. Courses for skills development.

Engagement and dissemination activities directed at H2IOSC personnel were a strategic first step in the WP1 mission, as they guaranteed internal alignment on shared methodologies, equipping H2IOSC personnel to serve as ambassadors and multipliers in subsequent external engagement. This enhanced the collaborative culture of the project, creating a shared foundation for all future training, engagement and dissemination outputs. Several dissemination measures were explicitly targeted to H2IOSC members themselves:

- **internal documentation and technical specifications:** dissemination of guidelines, standards, and implementation documents ensured that all staff could align with project methodologies. For example, specifications for the H2IOSC Marketplace and the metadata schema were shared internally as dissemination outputs;
- **methodological dissemination:** beyond training, FAIR-by-Design and metadata harmonisation guidelines were disseminated internally as working documents and presentations to facilitate adoption across different teams;
- **strategic dissemination to personnel:** the broader strategy of integrating infrastructures (CLARIN, DARIAH, OPERAS, E-RIHS) was communicated internally, ensuring all staff were aware of how their local activities fitted into the national cluster and into EOSC.

Other engagement initiatives directed to H2IOSC personnel involved creating awareness of links with external projects and infrastructures:

- personnel were engaged through **internal briefings on collaborations** with Skills4EOSC, SSHOC, and other European cluster initiatives;
- **dissemination of project synergies** (for instance, with PRIN projects or national associations like AIUCD) helped personnel situate their own work in a wider ecosystem.

These actions, while not training, engaged internal staff by showing them how H2IOSC is positioned nationally and internationally. The main outcomes of non-training engagement/dissemination for H2IOSC personnel were:

- Internal alignment: dissemination of strategies, methodologies, and standards ensured a coherent approach across all operative units;
- community building inside H2IOSC: engagement through meetings and cross-WP exchanges builds trust and cohesion among staff;
- awareness of external positioning: by disseminating synergies with European and national projects, personnel gained a broader vision of H2IOSC's role.

Table 11: Co-funding of PhD grants in H2IOSC – Expected implementation plan

WP3 - Digital Resources Standardization, Consolidation & Alignment		
Topic	PhD planned	PhD Implementation
Consolidating the Cultural Heritage resources (E-RIHS)	Co-funding of 1 PhD grant for carrying out research on topics relating to the innovative task connected to the design and development activities of the DIGILAB ecosystem.	Co-funding of 1 PhD grant for carrying out research on topics relating to the innovative task connected to the design and development activities of the DIGILAB ecosystem (1 PhD for 2 years)
WP5 – MarketPlace		
Topic	PhD planned	PhD Implementation
Marketplace implementation	Training to researchers involved in the validation trials; co-financing of a data science PhD position on analysis techniques for marketplace use data	Training to researchers involved in the validation trials; co-financing of a data science 2 PhD position on analysis techniques for marketplace use data for 2 years (Validation trials; data science PhD position on analysis techniques for marketplace use data)
WP6 – Resources Accessibility: Servification, Virtualization, Remotization		
Topic	PhD planned	PhD Implementation
E-RIHS Remotization: Wireless sensor networks for cultural heritage conservation and monitoring	co-funding of 1 PhD grant for carrying out research on topics relating to the research question connected to the activity tasks.	Co-funding of 1 PhD grant for carrying out research on topics relating to the research question connected to the activity tasks for 2 years.
WP7 – Community pilots: innovative cross-domain services and environments		
Topic	PhD planned	PhD Implementation
Language Community Pilots: CLARIN	Co-funding of 3 PhD grants for carrying out research on topics relating to the pilots, and in collaboration with the activities on the pilots themselves.	Cost for the co-funding of 1 PhD grant for carrying out research on topics relating to the pilots, and in collaboration with the activities on the pilots themselves for 2 years.

Digital Arts and Humanities Community Pilots: DARIAH	Co-funding of 1 PhD grant for carrying out research on topics relating to the pilots, and in collaboration with the activities on the pilots themselves	Cost for the co-funding of 1 PhD grant for carrying out research on topics relating to the pilots, and in collaboration with the activities on the pilots themselves for 2 years (Digital Philology).
Cultural Heritage Pilot (E-RIHS): Innovative Interfaces	Co-financing cost of 2-year PhD within the topic of HCI and spatial/3D interfaces targeting immersive analytics	Co-financing cost of 2-year PhD within the topic of HCI and spatial/3D interfaces targeting immersive analytics for 2 years (Spatial interfaces and interaction design for immersive analytics)
Cultural Heritage Pilot (E-RIHS): Scientific digital hub for metal artworks	PhD scholarship will be opened for an Early Stage researcher with academic background relevant to Heritage Science to be trained and develop the topics under this pilot.	PhD scholarship will be opened for an Early Stage researcher with academic background relevant to Heritage Science to be trained and develop the topics under this pilot for 3 years.
Cultural Heritage Pilot (E-RIHS): Prototyping platform for Virtual / Physical Exhibitions	Co-funding of 3 PhD grants for carrying out research on topics relating to the pilots, and in collaboration with the activities on the pilots themselves.	Co-funding of 1 PhD grant for carrying out research on topics relating to the pilots, and in collaboration with the activities on the pilots themselves for 2 years. (Digital Transformation)
Open Resources Publishing Pilot (OPERAS)	Training for the researchers involved in the activity; co-financing of a PhD position	Training on analysis techniques (SWOT, SOAR, NOISE).

4.3.2 Internal training activities in H2IOSC

Following is the table with a first list of **internal training activities (transversal to all research infrastructures)** planned and updated at M36.

Table 13: List of internal training activities - H2IOSC (M36)

n.	Title	Number of training hours	Ris involved	Target	Venue	By
1	European Union Strategy for Research Infrastructure and Application at the Italian level	4	All	H2IOSC personnel recruited	online	EUCORE
2	Funding for infrastructures: Horizon Europe, Next-Generation, EU, and Structural Funds	4	All	H2IOSC personnel recruited	online	EUCORE
3	Design and project management of research infrastructures	4	All	H2IOSC personnel recruited	online	EUCORE
4	Business Plan	4	All	H2IOSC personnel recruited	online	EUCORE
5	Reporting for PNRR and infrastructure projects	6	All	H2IOSC personnel recruited	In person & online	EUCORE
6	State aid, intellectual property, and legal aspects of research infrastructures	6	All	H2IOSC personnel recruited	In person & online	EUCORE
7	Ethical module	4	All	H2IOSC personnel recruited	In person	EUCORE
8	European data strategy: Open Science, Open Management Data, FAIR Principles	6	All	H2IOSC personnel recruited	In person	EUCORE
9	Data Management Plan development	6	All	H2IOSC personnel recruited	In person	EUCORE

10	Impact, dissemination, communication, and valorization of results in research projects	6	All	H2IOSC personnel recruited	In person	EUCORE
11	GDPR in Horizon Europe - the European perspective	2,5	All	H2IOSC personnel recruited	online	APRE
12	The "Do No Significant Harm" (DNSH) principle - EU perspective	1,5	All	H2IOSC personnel recruited	online	APRE
13	Science and society: communicate or participate? - Citizen Science	2	All	H2IOSC personnel recruited	In person	APRE
14	Stakeholder Engagement in Horizon Europe	2,5	All	H2IOSC personnel recruited	In person	APRE
15	Evaluation of research infrastructures from the ESFRI scope to the national context	1,5	All	H2IOSC personnel recruited	In person	APRE
16	Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan in Horizon Europe	2,5	All	H2IOSC personnel recruited	In person	APRE
17	Open Science in Horizon Europe	2	All	H2IOSC personnel recruited	online	APRE
18	Social sciences and humanities in Horizon Europe	2	All	H2IOSC personnel recruited	online	APRE
19	How to write a proposal in the Research Infrastructure program - Legal and financial aspects in RIs	3	All	H2IOSC personnel recruited	In person	APRE
20	Data Management Plan and legal issues	1,5	All	H2IOSC personnel recruited	online	APRE

Furthermore, some cross-cutting training sessions involving the four infrastructures involved in H2IOSC have been carried out in 2024. The idea was to propose **a series of four online meetings** aimed at **introducing the work of each infrastructure**. These events were strictly reserved for the units involved in the project, **in order to delve into the specificities of each RI**, not only at the national level but also including success stories for the international reference community.

Specialized technical training

One of the key aspects regarding the training of **internal staff** is the **specialized technical training** aimed at technicians and technologists referring to:

- Installation and management of equipment related to the project's **Data Centers**.
- Use of specific technical **software**.
- **Fairification** tools.

Here below is the detailed outline of specialized **training courses** that have been **ordered and/or purchased by some Operational Units** of the project, reported at M36, for their staff:

- Configuration and management of a Kubernetes cluster (ICAR-CNR)
- Configuration and management of hardware and software solutions (ICAR-CNR)
- AI/LM/HPC in Data Centers (ISPC-CT)

- Supercomputing, machine/deep learning, data storage and ingestion aimed at support staff for Data Center operations (ISPC-LE)
- interoperability among resources in the CH/HS sector (ISPC-MI)
- Servification and remotization (ISPC-RM)
- Supercomputing, machine/deep learning, data storage and ingestion aimed at support staff for Data Center operations (NANOTEC-LE)
- VMware vSphere, VMware vCenter, VMware vSAN, VMware Tanzu / Kubernetes, Docker, Dell VxRail with vSAN, Dell Powerscale, Dell Datadomain, Dell Networking (ILC-CNR)

4.4 Co-funding of PhD grants in H2IOSC - 39° cycle

H2IOSC is implementing a strategy to enhance the potential of new generations of researchers by improving their skills and expertise through doctoral scholarships with high scientific and technical competence. Currently H2IOSC is actively involved in the following PhDs:

- National PhD in Heritage Science (PhD-HS.it), coordinated by Sapienza Università di Roma
Link: https://phd.uniroma1.it/web/DOTTORATO-NAZIONALE-IN-HERITAGE-SCIENCE_nD3864_IT.aspx
- PhD in Modeling and Data Science, coordinated by Università di Torino
Link: <https://dottorato-mds.campusnet.unito.it/do/home.pl>
- PhD Programme Humanism and Technologies, coordinated by Università di Macerata
Link: <https://www.unimc.it/en/courses/phd-programmes/phd-programme-humanism-and-technologies>
- PhD in Philosophy, coordinated by Università Roma Tre
Link: <https://filosofiacomunicazionepettacolo.uniroma3.it/ricerca/dottorato-di-ricerca/dottorato-di-ricerca-in-filosofia/>
- PhD in Italian and Romance Philology in the Digital Turn (FROID), coordinate by Scuola Normale Superiore di Pisa
Link: <https://www.sns.it/en/disciplinacorso-di-laurea/corso-phd/italian-and-romance-philology-digital-turn>

Shown table below, the PhD students participating in H2IOSC project, collaborating with a CNR Institute.

Table 14: Co-funding of PhD grants in H2IOSC – (M01 - M36)

N.	PhD	Institute - University	WP H2IOSC
1	1 PhD student in Modeling and Data Science	CNR ILIESI Rome - Università di Torino	Involved in WP5 Marketplace
2	1 PhD student in Philosophy	CNR ILIESI Rome - Università Roma Tre	Involved in WP7 Community pilots: innovative cross-domain services and environments
3	1 PhD student in Heritage Science	CNR ISPC Lecce - Sapienza Università di Roma	Involved in WP6 Resources Accessibility: Servification, Virtualization, Remotization

4	1 PhD student in Heritage Science	CNR INO Florence - Sapienza Università di Roma	Involved in WP7 Community pilots: innovative cross-domain services and environments
5	1 PhD student in Italian and Romance Philology in the Digital Turn (FROID)	CNR OVI Florence - Scuola Normale Superiore di Pisa	Involved in WP7 Community pilots: innovative cross-domain services and environments
6	1 PhD student in Heritage Science	CNR ISPC Rome - Sapienza Università di Roma	Involved in WP7 Community pilots: innovative cross-domain services and environments
7	1 PhD student in Heritage Science	CNR ISPC Lecce - Sapienza Università di Roma	Involved in WP3 Digital Resources Standardization, Consolidation & Alignment
8	1 PhD student in Philosophy	CNR ILIESI Roma - Università Roma Tre	Involved in WP7 Community pilots: innovative cross-domain services and environments
9	1 PhD student in Humanism and Technologies	CNR ILC Pisa - Università di Macerata	Involved in WP7 Community pilots: innovative cross-domain services and environments
10	1 PhD student in Heritage Science	CNR ISPC Florence - Sapienza Università di Roma	Involved in WP7 Community pilots: innovative cross-domain services and environments
11	1 PhD student in Modeling and Data Science	CNR ILIESI Roma - Università di Torino	Involved in WP5 Marketplace

5 CONCLUSIONS

The H2IOSC Community Engagement Strategy outlines the project's approach to engaging with its stakeholder community, emphasizing the importance of active involvement and collaboration. The strategy focuses on various stakeholder categories, recognizing them as essential to the core objective of building the Social Sciences and Humanities as part of the EOSC (European Open Science Cloud).

Target Audience: The strategy identifies key stakeholder categories, including researchers, associations, intermediaries, and other involved parties within the Social Sciences and Humanities domain. Active engagement with these groups is essential for project success and impact maximization.

Project Core Objective: The primary mission of the H2IOSC project is to contribute to the development of the EOSC by focusing on the Social Sciences and Humanities sector. This objective requires close collaboration and participation from end users and stakeholders.

Awareness and Added Value: The strategy emphasizes the need to raise awareness among stakeholders about the value and benefits of H2IOSC assets in everyday research and the broader context of Open Science.

Engagement Strategy: The document outlines a strategy for engaging with H2IOSC stakeholders, including key messages tailored for each stakeholder group. It also defines the channels and instruments to be used for communication and engagement, aligning with the H2IOSC Overall Communication and Outreach Plan.

Monitoring and Updates: WP1 closely monitors the progress of engagement activities, and there is an ongoing stakeholder mapping exercise. The engagement strategy must be updated regularly to ensure its successful implementation and to broaden stakeholder participation, as well as its medium-long period sustainability .

Complementary Strategies: The Community Engagement Strategy must work in conjunction with the Building Expertise Strategy, with the goal of enhancing expertise in the H2IOSC domain.

In summary, this Community Engagement Strategy underscores the significance of involving diverse stakeholder groups in the H2IOSC project and outlines a comprehensive plan to achieve this involvement. It emphasizes communication, awareness-building, and continuous updates to ensure the strategy's effectiveness.

Regarding the sustainability of training infrastructure, it must be ensured by a new generation of Heritage and Humanities researchers and professionals with new and advanced skills. Furthermore, the collaborations with universities and other public and private organizations (Co-funding of PhD grants) both strengthen the connections between research organizations and industry, and help develop international, interdisciplinary, and innovative profiles that can be employed in different sectors.

The training and engagement long-term strategy has, indeed, to be aligned with the long-term strategies for the maintenance of the project's knowledge, outputs and services for at least 10 years after the end of the funding period, as described in detail in D1.4 (H2IOSC Sustainability Financial Plan).

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Annexes

- **Annex 1 – List of H2IOSC engagement and dissemination initiatives (period M01 – M36).**
- **Annex 2 – List of publications related to H2IOSC (period M01 – M36).**
- **Annex 3 – List of training activities related to H2IOSC (period M01 – M36).**

Annex 1 - List of H2IOSC engagement/dissemination initiatives carried out and foreseen													
UO N. & Acronym	RI	Other UO involved (if any)	Organized by	Date	Venue	Type of activities (conference, workshop, meeting, etc.)	Event / Conference name	Specify: Engagement/Dissemination	Target	Number of participants	Title	Description	Link
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		Italian Association of Computational Linguistics (AILC)	30/06/2021	In person Milano	Conference	CLIC2021	Engagement and dissemination		60	Eighth Italian Conference on Computational Linguistics	Panel Language Resources and Technology Infrastructures	https://clic2021.disco.unimib.it/detailed-program/
OU9 - ISPC-CT	E-RIHS		University of Antwerp	08/05/2022	In person Bruges, Belgium	Conference	EXRS2022	Dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori, Musei	350	Deep Learning for MA-XRF Imaging spectroscopy of Paintings	The current advancements of non-invasive imaging methods applied for the study and conservation of cultural heritage have driven a rapid development of novel computational methods. MA-XRF is nowadays well-established and often used for the investigation of paintings in museums and conservation studios. However, MA-XRF scanning generates large datasets that can be challenging and time-consuming to analyze. We have developed a novel deep learning approach based on convolutional networks for the MA-XRF analysis. The AI/ML allows for identification of non-trivial dependencies and classification across the high dimensional data hence promising a more comprehensive interrogation. AI/ML results presented in this work have been obtained using data taken by the MA-XRF technique developed at the XRAYLab of ISPC-CNR in Catania.	European Conference on X-ray Spectrometry 2022
OU9 - ISPC-CT	E-RIHS		University of Delft	20/09/2022	In person Delft, The Netherlands	Conference	MA-XRF2022	Dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori, Musei	200	MA-XRF imaging of Egyptian faience amulets through deep learning models	MA-XRF is nowadays well-established for the in-situ investigation of paintings in museums and conservation studios, but it is scarcely applied for systematic analysis of large collections of three-dimensional small objects. This work presents the MA-XRF investigation of around 1400 Egyptian faience amulets belonging to the collection of Museo Egizio Torino. The research is performed in a collaborative project with the Museum curators, and it is aimed to gain new insights on raw materials and production technologies from different periods and workshops.	MA-XRF 2022, MA-XRF scanning in Conservation, Art and Archaeology 2022
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN			28/10/2022	Online	Website news		Dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori		Starting H2IOSC, the PNRR project for the Italian Open Science Cloud for the Humanities and Cultural Heritage	Introduzione al progetto	https://www.clarin.it/en/content/starting-h2iosc-pnrr-project-italian-open-science-cloud-humanities-and-cultural-heritage
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CLARIN ERIC	08/11/2022	Online	Seminar	CLARIN Café	Engagement	Accademia, Ricercatori	30	Text and Data Mining Exceptions a Year After - Has the Pony become a Horse?		https://www.clarin.eu/content/clarin-cafe
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CLARIN ERIC	02/12/2022	Online	Seminar	CLARIN Café	Engagement	Accademia, Ricercatori	30	Voices from Ravensbruck on the Web - a Multilingual Challenge.		https://www.clarin.eu/content/clarin-cafe
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN			14/12/2022	In person Parma	Seminar		Dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori	50	CLARIN & CLARIN-IT @ University of Parma 2022		https://www.clarin.it/en/content/clarin-clarin-it-university-parma-2022
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN			03/02/2023	In person Bonn, Germany	Conference	TRIPLE 2023	Dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori		A FAIR Training Platform for Italian Humanities and Heritage Building on the CLARIN and SSHOC experience		https://www.clarin.it/en/content/triple-2023-programme-now-available
All UO	All RI			07/02/2023	In person & online Roma	General Meeting		Engagement and dissemination	Associazioni ambiti RI, Accademia, Ricercatori	DAY 1: 87 in person, 57 online DAY 2: 85 in person, 19 online Total: 248	The project partnership meets stakeholders	DAY 1 - H2IOSC: Supporting the Digital Transition in the S&CI Domain, Enabling New Generation Research DAY 2 - H2IOSC progress: problems, processes, results	https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/h2iosc-general-meeting/
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN			17/02/2023	In person & online Lecce	Conference	Annual Conference of the Italian Association of Speech Sciences (AISV) - AISV 2023 - Speech in the medical field: linguistic	Engagement and dissemination	Associazioni linguistica, Accademia, Ricercatori	30	Poster Session 1 (15/02/2023 14:30-15:30) Research infrastructures and services. CLARIN for voice sciences and didactics in linguistics, phonetics, phonology by Francesca Frontini, Monica Monachini		https://www.clarin.it/en/content/clarin-it-aisv-2023
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH			24/02/2023	In person Bari	Conference	Conference on Information and	dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori	50	The RESTORE project: a final review		https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3365/
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CLARIN ERIC	03/03/2023	Online	Seminar	CLARIN Café	Engagement	Accademia, Ricercatori	30	Exploring the Potential of Digital Tools for Online Learning		https://www.clarin.eu/content/clarin-cafe
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CLARIN ERIC	11/04/2023	Online	Seminar	CLARIN Café	Engagement	Accademia, Ricercatori	30	Do Chatbots Dream of Copyright? Copyright in AI-generated Language Data		https://www.clarin.eu/content/clarin-cafe
OU9 - ISPC-CT	E-RIHS		University of Lisbon	07/05/2023	In person Lisbon, Portugal	Conference	Technart2023	Dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori, Musei	400	MA-XRF imaging of paintings: comparative studies by using classical analysis and artificial intelligence		TECHNART 2023 LISBON 7-12 May 2023
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN			12/05/2023	In person Pisa	Workshop		Dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori	50	Research Infrastructures for Social Sciences and Open Science.	CLARIN-IT and H2IOSC at the Celebration of the Centenary of CNR Establishment	https://www.clarin.it/en/content/clarin-it-and-h2iosc-celebration-centenary-cnr-establishment
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH		Regione Toscana	19/05/2023	In person & online Firenze	Event		Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori, Pubblico generalista	100	100 ricercatori per la cultura, Seminario Musei - Fruizione e Audience Development. Regione Toscana		https://www.regione.toscana.it/documents/10180/24384535/Programma_hando_assegni_cultura_19_maggio.pdf/6a7d4513-1b11-d197-c6e5-2c8d1b2c4314?t=1684154606694
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH			05/06/2023	In person Roma		ITAEOOSC 2023		Accademia, Ricercatori	50	H2IOSC @ Italian Tripartite Assembly on the European Open Science Cloud	The Italian Tripartite Assembly on the European Open Science Cloud (ITAEOOSC 2023) event, sponsored by the MUR as part of the national tripartite events of the EOOSC-Association, European Commission and EOOSC Steering Board, will be held in Rome on June 5.	https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/h2iosc-italian-tripartite-assembly-on-the-european-open-science-cloud/
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH		AIUCD	07/06/2023	In person Siena	Conference and workshop	AIUCD 2023	Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori				http://www.aiucd.it/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/2023_aiucd_la_memoria_digitale_v1.pdf
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		AIUCD	07/06/2023	In person Siena	Conference	AIUCD 2023	Dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori, professionisti	50	La memoria digitale. Scienza aperta e formazione nelle infrastrutture di ricerca europee e nazionali per le risorse linguistiche	Scienza aperta e formazione nelle infrastrutture di ricerca europee e nazionali per le risorse linguistiche	http://www.aiucd2023.unisi.it/programma-aiucd/
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH		DARIAH.EU	09/06/2023	In person Budapest	Event	DARIAH Annual Event 2023	Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori				
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CLARIN ERIC	05/07/2023	Online	Seminar	CLARIN Café	Engagement	Accademia, Ricercatori	30	A new CLARIN Resource Family for Lexical Semantic Change Research		https://www.clarin.eu/content/clarin-cafe
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH			02/08/2023	In person Venezia	Conference	IEEE CSR 2023	Dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori	50	DARIAH-IT: Managing Digital Heritage Assets		http://dariah.cnr.it/?p=1789
OU10 - ISPC-LE	E-RIHS		UO ISPC-LE	05/09/2023	In person Lecce	International Conference	21st Eurographics Workshop on Graphics and Cultural Heritage (GCH 2023)	Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori	100		GCH workshop will open up a new avenue and impact by creating a link between researchers with innovative ideas and scientific journals. Accepted papers will be published in the Eurographics Digital Library (EUROGRAPHICS Workshop on Graphics and Cultural Heritage)	
All UO	All RI		H2IOSC	07/09/2023	In person Lecce	Workshop		Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori	50	Primo Workshop di H2IOSC		https://www.lic.cnr.it/events/1-workshop-di-h2iosc/
OU10 - ISPC-LE	All RI		UO ISPC-LE	07/09/2023	In person Lecce	Workshop / working group meeting		Engagement	Accademia, Ricercatori	30	1° Workshop di H2IOSC-Humanities and Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud.		

OU15 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		Politecnico di Milano e Università degli Studi di Milano	08/09/2023	In person	Milano	Conference	CMD 30-FisMat 2023 Conference	Dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori, professionisti	300	Reflectance spectroscopy as a novel tool for thickness measurements of painting layers	Una delle principali sfide nella scienza del patrimonio culturale è l'analisi trasversale non invasiva dei dipinti. Quando si utilizzano sonde a bassa energia, la presenza di mezzi opachi può ostacolare in modo significativo la penetrazione della radiazione incidente, nonché la raccolta del segnale retrodiffuso. Attualmente, nessuna tecnica è in grado di misurare in modo univoco e non invasivo lo spessore micrometrico di materiali eterogenei, come gli strati pittorici, per qualsiasi materiale pittorico. Lo scopo di questo lavoro era quello di esplorare la possibilità di estrarre informazioni stratigrafiche dagli spettri di riflettanza ottenuti mediante spettroscopia di riflettanza diffusa (DRS).	https://www.fisi.polimi.it/it/all-news/cmd30-fismat2023
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH			13/09/2023	In person & online	Torino	Conference	DRHA 2023	Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori				https://www.unito.it/sites/default/files/programma_drha.pdf
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH			26/09/2023	In person	Paris - Auberville	Event			Accademia, Ricercatori	50	EUROPEENNE	Présentation du rôle des infrastructures européennes	https://fn10years.sciencesconf.org/resource/page/id/1
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN			27/09/2023	In person	Bologna	Study day		Engagement and dissemination		30	Study Day "Digital Humanities: from school to work.		https://www.clarin.it/en/content/diptext-kc-study-day-digital-humanities
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH			27/09/2023	online	Vienna	Conference	2023: Interdisciplinary	dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori	60	century's Tuscan merchant		https://digital-bio-2023.acdh.oeaw.ac.at/data/html/program.html
OU12 - ISPC-RM	E-RIHS		University of Padua, Sapienza University of Rome, Politecnico di Torino, Italy	10/10/2023	Online		Conference	REAAACH - Representation Advances And CHallenges association	Dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori	70	The e-Archeo 3D project, an innovative and sustainable cultural proposal based on XR technologies	The contribution focuses on e-Archeo 3D: an application that visualises virtual archaeological reconstructions. It is an interactive browser-based application implemented on the open-source ATON platform. This application enables the visualisation of archaeological sites through 360° panoramas that can be explored and populated with multimedia content (audio, pictures, videos, and 3D models). Users can switch between the current archaeological context and the reconstruction hypothesis at each viewpoint while a voice (or text) narrates the main archaeological and historical information. Some parts of the panoramas pulse with a yellow colour and give access to in-depth multimedia content. An additional visualisation level allows users to learn about the reliability of the reconstructions and the sources and interpretative processes on which they are based.	https://www.reaach.eu/symposium-2023/
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN			12/10/2023	In person	Firenze	Conference	DIPText-KC @ "Open Doors at CNR"	Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori	60	Masterclass "Artificial Intelligence and Cultural Heritage: Computer Vision and Text Recognition"		https://diptext-kc.clarin.it/it/diptext-kc-open-doors-at-cnr/
All UO	All RI		CNR-ISPC	12/10/2023	In person	Firenze	Festival	PORTE APERTE AL CNR: #patrimonioculturale nelle transizioni verde e digitale	Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori, Pubblico generalista	300		Tre giornate interamente dedicate al Patrimonio Culturale e alle professionalità e attività che caratterizzano questo vivo settore di ricerca, con diversi format comunicativi indirizzati a diverse fasce di pubblico, per celebrare il Patrimonio Culturale nella cornice dei festeggiamenti dei cento anni dalla fondazione del Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche.	https://www.ispc.cnr.it/it/2023/09/14/festival-porte-aperte-al-cnr-patrimonioculturale-nelle-transizioni-verde-e-digitale/
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH		DARIAH.IT	14/10/2023	In person	Prato	Event		Engagement and dissemination	Pubblico generalista	30	Incontri a Palazzo Archivio di Stato di Prato		
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN			18/10/2023	In person & online	Leuven	Conference	CLARIN Annual Conference 2023	Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori	150	CLARIN-IT: Texts, Documents and New Contexts		https://www.clarin.eu/event/2023/clarin-annual-conference-2023
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH		"Medioevo Romanzo"	24/10/2023	online	Siena	Workshop	romanzo. Costi, benefici,	dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori	25	Il Digital Philology Hub del progetto PNR IR H2IOSC		digital-philology
OU12 - ISPC-RM	E-RIHS		CNR-ISPC, Italy / Borsa Mediterranea del Turismo Archeologico BMTA	05/11/2023	In person	Museo Archeologico di Capaccio Paestum (SA)	Event & Workshop	ArcheoVirtual 2023 "Nuove Intelligenze"	Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori, Musei, Pubblico generalista			E' stata esposta una applicazione interattiva ("Imagine") basata sul servizio ATON di E-RIHS con contenuti di AI generativa, combinandola con un altro dei servizi E-RIHS dedicato alla cattura e analisi delle interazioni remote	http://www.archeovirtual.it/index.php/exhibition_workshop
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH		CNR	09/11/2023	In person & online	Roma	Conference	Conferenza di Dipartimento	Engagement and dissemination	Ricercatori	50	Le scienze Umane e Sociali nel XXI secolo. Comprendere e trasformare la società		https://www.cnr.it/it/evento/18871/conferenza-di-dipartimento-le-scienze-umane-e-sociali-nel-xxi-secolo-comprendere-e-trasformare-la-societa
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN	All UO		15/11/2023	In person & online	Pisa	Conference		Engagement and dissemination	Associazioni linguistica, Accademia, Ricercatori	90	Infrastrutture e risorse per la ricerca linguistica in Italia	H2IOSC incontra le maggiori associazioni di linguistica a livello italiano	https://www.ilc.cnr.it/events/infrastrutture-e-risorse-per-la-ricerca-linguistica-in-italia/
OU10 - ISPC-LE	E-RIHS		UO ISPC-LE	22/11/2023	In person	Roma	Workshop		Dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori	50	BIBLIOTECA ANGELICA - Presentazione del Progetto CODEX 4D		
OU10 - ISPC-LE	E-RIHS		UO ISPC-LE	22/11/2023	In person	Roma	Workshop	GenOA Week 2023	Dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori	50	Heritage Science and Open Science: il progetto DataSpace del CNR-ISPC - Presentazione su call tenuta alla GenOA Week 2023 nella sessione "Dati della ricerca come risorsa e bene comune" - 10.5281/zenodo.10201265	DataSpace è una piattaforma digitale in fase di sviluppo da parte dell'Istituto di Scienza del Patrimonio (ISPC) del Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR), che si propone di offrire l'accesso, la condivisione e l'archiviazione a lungo termine dei dati di ricerca, nel rispetto dei principi FAIR. DataSpace offre l'accesso a strumenti e servizi digitali innovativi, utili a creare nuova conoscenza condivisa nel campo della Scienza del Patrimonio, in una prospettiva interdisciplinare.	https://dataspace.ispc.cnr.it/
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH		Regione Toscana	05/12/2023	In person & online	Firenze	Event	NexUs Cultura e Ricerca: connessioni per l'innovazione, Regione Toscana	Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori, Pubblico generalista				https://www.regione.toscana.it/documents/10180/24384535/Programma-NexUs-WEB+%281%29.pdf/2ae51d53-1648-cb52-64f5-d0d8c29f2d2?e=1701193325770
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN			12/12/2023	In person	Venezia	Tutorial		Engagement				Introduction to Wikidata and the Importation of Bibliographic Elements from Zotero	https://diptext-kc.clarin.it/it/knowledge/knowledge-pills/introduction-to-wikidata-and-the-importation-of-bibliographic-elements-from-zotero/
OU15 - INO-FI	E-RIHS			26/01/2024	online	Bologna	Workshop		Dissemination		93	and Heritage Science Career Paths"	Community analysis of educational and career paths in education	heritage-science-career-paths-on-january-25-26-2024/
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN			30/01/2024	In person	Roma	Seminar		Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori	70	SEMINARIO ITALO-FRANCESE: italiano e francese, quali sono le sfide per le nostre lingue	Il seminario -italiano e francese, quali sono le sfide per le nostre lingue?- organizzato in collaborazione con la Délégation générale à la langue française et aux langues de France (DGLFLF) del Ministero della Cultura francese, metterà in luce il ruolo delle due lingue del mondo.	
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CLARIN ERIC	30/01/2024	Online		Seminar	CLARIN Café	Engagement	Accademia, Ricercatori	30	ParlaMint		https://www.clarin.eu/content/clarin-cafe
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN	ITSERR		02/02/2024	Online		Seminar		Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori	20	Costruire Una Infrastruttura: L'esempio di CLARIN		
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN			03/02/2024	In person	Torino	Conference	AISV 2024 - Voci, media e nuove tecnologie, XX Convegno Nazionale AISV	Engagement	Associazioni linguistica, Accademia, Ricercatori			Community analysis of current projects, activities and needs	https://sites.google.com/view/aisv2024/home
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		UniRoma1 under the patronage of CLARIN-IT, DIPText-KC, CNR-ILC and H2IOSC.	12/02/2024		Roma	Event		Engagement and dissemination	Students of the PhD Course in Civilizations of Asia and Africa			Oriental Studies & Digital Humanities	https://diptext-kc.clarin.it/oriental-studies-digital-humanities/
OU9 - ISPC-CT	CLARIN			22/02/2024	In person	Arezzo	Seminar		Engagement	Accademia, Ricercatori	18	matti. Verso la costituzione di un archivio orale	oral archives preservation, oral history pilot	sulle fonti orali - edizione-ii-chiamavano
OU12 - ISPC-RM	E-RIHS		Lazio	25/02/2024	In person	Firenze	Conference	Turismo Culturale	dissemination	generalista	50	culturale	Interazioni sviluppato da E-RIHS in H2IOSC. E' stato inoltre presentato al	https://www.tourisma.it/domenica-25-febbraio-2024/

OU10 - ISPC-LE	E-RIHS		UO ISPC-LE	07/03/2024	In person	Madrid	Workshop		Dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori		Towards a financially sustainable DIGILAB: From Research processes to Business Processes for simulating the use and costing of a key DIGILAB service.	Presentation of the strategy to design the BPMN diagram of DIGILAB services useful to estimate service costs. Application to H2IOSC Illuminated manuscript HUB pilot.	https://cnrsc.sharepoint.com/p://sites/DHILab-app/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B49225C39-4CA0-48C1-B8DD-7D08C63E890%7D&file=presentazione%20e-rihs%20madrid%20-%20Short.pptx&action=edit&mobileRedirect=true&wdOrigin=METAOS_FILEBROWSER_FILES_SITES-FOLDER
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CLARIN ERIC	12/03/2024	Online		Seminar	CLARIN Café	Engagement	Accademia, Ricercatori	30	Computer-assisted Pragmatic Annotation of native and learner Corpora		https://www.clarin.eu/content/clarin-cafe
OU16 - ISPF-NA	OPERAS		ISPF-NA	25/03/2024	In person & online	Napoli	Conference		Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori, Pubblico generalista, Studenti	30 in presenza, 20 da remoto	Digital / Humanities: quando il sapere diventa dato	Ciclo seminariale dell'Osservatorio sui saperi umanistici dell'ISPF	http://www.ispf.cnr.it/eventi/pensare-nellera-del-dato/
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CLARIN ERIC	04/04/2024	Online		Seminar	CLARIN Café	Engagement	Accademia, Ricercatori	30	Creating pedagogical corpora with annotation of sensitive content and offensive language - the CrowLL project		https://www.clarin.eu/content/clarin-cafe
OU16 - ISPF-NA	OPERAS		ISPF-NA	15/04/2024	In person & online	Napoli	Conference		Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori	40 in presenza, 15 da remoto	Digital / Humanities: quando il sapere diventa dato	Ciclo seminariale dell'Osservatorio sui saperi umanistici dell'ISPF	https://cesta.stanford.edu/events/global-horizons-digital-and-public-humanities
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		UNIPI-ILCCNR	18/04/2024	In person	Pisa	Conference	testimonianze dei sopravvissuti ai lager: convegno internazionale	Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori, Storici, Linguisti		Infrastrutture di ricerca europee Monica Monachini (CNR - ILC), CLARIN-IT & H2IOSC Federico Boschetti (Università di Venezia), Quale	Convegno	sopravvissuti-ai-lager-convegno-internazionale-18-19-aprile-2024/#:~:text=Ne%20giorni%2018%20e%2019,%20la%20professoressa%20Marina%20Ricucci.
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		Venice Centre for Digital and Public Humanities (VeDPH) dell'Università Ca' Foscari di Venezia & Centre for Spatial and Text Analysis (CESTA) of Stanford University	25/04/2024	In person	San Francisco (CA, US)	Workshop / working group meeting	Global Horizons for the Digital and Public Humanities	Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori	25		A week of meetings, presentations, fieldwork and roundtable discussions about Digital and Public Humanities	https://cesta.stanford.edu/events/global-horizons-digital-and-public-humanities
OU16 - ISPF-NA	OPERAS		ISPF-NA	08/05/2024	In person & online	Napoli	Conference and workshop	Ciclo di workshop ILIES/ISPF	Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori		H2IOSC: una piattaforma unica per le edizioni critiche digitali		
OU9 - ISPC-CT	E-RIHS		Heritage Science Sweden Forum	13/05/2024	In person	Nationalmuseum, Stockholm	Conference	Heritage Science Sverige forum 2024	Dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori, Musei	100	Medieval Colours of the Book - a non-invasive study of ten Swedish book fragments	MA-XRF imaging applied from the MOLAB platform of ERIHS on several fragments from from books thought locally produced in Sweden for the study of their polychromy. Data collection for the pilot on pictorial artworks and testing of analytical tools developed in the project.	HSS forum 2024 - Heritage Science Sweden
OU7 - ILIESI-RM	OPERAS		4D, France	15/05/2024	In person & online	4D Blitz, Villasanta (MB)	Workshop		Dissemination	Developers	30	Modelli di digital scholarly edition	The contribution aims to present to developers how to create a digital scholarly edition, what the demands of the digital humanities community are and what needs the H2IOSC project responds to	
	CLARIN		Univr	25/05/2024	Online		Webinar		Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori, Pubblico generalista, Studenti	6	Digital Spritz - Formazione FAIR per le scienze umane e del patrimonio: le iniziative di H2IOSC e CLARIN-IT	Presentazione sullo stato dei lavori del WP8 e in particolare sulla formazione CLARIN in H2IOSC: materiali, eventi e piattaforme	https://www.dlts.univr.it/documenti/iniziativa/dallidai321679.pdf
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN	DARIAH, E-RIHS, OPERAS		29/05/2024	In person	Catania	Conference	Me.Te. Digitali. Mediterraneo in rete tra testi e contesti, Proceedings del XIII Convegno Annuale AIUCD2024	Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori	120	Materiali didattici come oggetti digitali FAIR: una metodologia condivisa per la formazione in H2IOSC		https://amsacta.unibo.it/id/eprint/7927/
OU9 - ISPC-CT	E-RIHS		National Gallery Washington	04/06/2024	In person	Washington, USA	Conference	XRF-RIS 2024 conference and workshop, Washington, USA, June 2024	Dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori, Musei	150	Deep Learning Applications for MA-XRF Imaging	AI/ML applications for the analysis of datacubes obtained from advanced X-rays diagnostics of paintings	maxrf-ris-meeting-2024.academic.wlu.edu
OU9 - ISPC-CT	E-RIHS		National Gallery Washington	04/06/2024	In person	Washington, USA	Conference	XRF-RIS 2024 conference and workshop, Washington, USA, June 2024	Dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori, Musei	150	The MOLAB transnational access for an in-situ investigation of the Hunt frieze of the tomb of Philip II at Aigai (Vergina, Greece)	MA-XRF imaging applied from the MOLAB platform of ERIHS on the hunt frieze of the monumental funerary tomb of Philip II at Aigai, Greece, for the study of its polychromy. Data collection for the pilot on pictorial artworks and testing of analytical tools developed in the project.	maxrf-ris-meeting-2024.academic.wlu.edu
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CLARIN ERIC	04/06/2024	Online		Seminar	CLARIN Café	Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori, tecnici, professionisti della traduzione	60	Translation Technologies & Workflows for SSH Researchers	translation technologies from a train-the-trainer perspective. It aims to provide an overview of available open educational resources that can be used in translation technology teaching and learning. After an introduction to translation and translation technology, the invited speakers will share	https://www.clarin.eu/event/2024/clarin-cafe-translation-technologies-workflows-ssh-researchers
OU11 ISPC-MI	E-RIHS		UO ISPC-MI	19/06/2024	In person	Torino	Conference	EVOA 2024 - Egitto e Vicino Oriente antichi	Dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori	2		Presentation of the ISCP-MI ongoing work for the H2IOSC project, focused on the realization of an epigraphic ontology, part of a wider Heritage Science ontology, and on one of the pilot case-studies which is DASI, the Digital Archive for the Study of pre-Islamic Arabian Inscriptions	
OU9 - ISPC-CT	E-RIHS		Gordon Research	07/07/2024	In person	Les Diablerets, Switzerland, July 2024	Conference	Gordon Research Conference	Dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori	150	Deep learning for MA-XRD/MA-XRF imaging for pigment-specific analysis of paintings	Development of AI/ML services for advanced processing of multimodal datasets from MA-XRF/MA-XRD analysis of painted artworks	2024 Scientific Methods in Cultural Heritage Research Conference GRC
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CLARIN ERIC	25/07/2024	Online		Seminar	CLARIN Café	Engagement	Accademia, Ricercatori	30	Of Users and Infrastructures		https://www.clarin.eu/content/clarin-cafe
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CLARIN ERIC	23/09/2024	Online		Seminar	CLARIN Café	Engagement	Accademia, Ricercatori	30	SSHOC Marketplace and Workflows		https://www.clarin.eu/content/clarin-cafe
OU12 - ISPC-RM	E-RIHS		CNR, Italy	27/09/2024	In person	CNR-ISPC, DHILab (sede di Roma)	Event	I4SCIENCE - La notte europea delle ricercatrici e dei ricercatori	Dissemination	General public	200	Innovation, Imagination, Integration, Impact of Science - Servizi 3D open-source per l'Heritage Science	All'interno di I4SCIENCE abbiamo organizzato due postazioni: esplorazione interattiva tramite visori di alcuni ambienti virtuali online e dimostrazione di strumenti open-source online dedicati alla visualizzazione 3D. In fine abbiamo mostrato le 3D analytics delle interazioni con gli ambienti virtuali visitati (pilot 7.7 di H2IOSC).	https://notteoiricercatori-i4science.cnr.it/
OU12 - ISPC-RM	E-RIHS	OU04 - ISPC FI	Khronos, ACM	27/09/2024	In person	Guimaraes, Portogallo	Workshop	Web3D Conference 2024	Dissemination	3D interattiva	25		stata presentata una applicazione orientata alla diagnostica basata su uno	https://web3d.siggraph.org/archive/web3d2024/
OU12 - ISPC-RM	E-RIHS		Associazione Plug	29/09/2024	In person	Pignola (PZ)	Workshop	Come to Code 2024	Dissemination	web, machine learning, cloud	200	ATON framework: creare Web3D e WebXR con facilità	conoscere e confrontarsi sui temi dell'innovazione tecnologica. Attraverso	https://www.cometocode.it/

OU1 - OVI-FI	E-RIHS		University of Malta	07/10/2024	In person	MetroArcheo, Malta	Conference		Dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori, musei	30	THz Time-Domain transmission and reflection imaging for art material analysis: preliminary results @E-RIHS.it	cultural heritage studies given the uniqueness and inestimable value of works of art. Techniques that are able to reveal details not visible to the naked eye are beneficial for the study of the original project followed by the artist. Among these, THz time-domain spectrometers are worth considering thanks to their capability of performing high-resolution imaging with good penetration depth in most paint materials. Accordingly, in the framework of	MetroArcheo 2024 (2024 International Conference on Metrology for Archaeology and Cultural Heritage), 7-9 Oct. 2024
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CLARIN ERIC	15/10/2024	In person	Barcelona	CLARIN Annual Conference 2024	CLARIN Annual Conference 2024	Dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori	120	Adapting UPSKILLS Modules to the University Curricula: CLARIN-IT Training Experience at the University of Ferrara		https://www.clarin.eu/event/2024/clarin-annual-conference-2024
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		AISO/AISV/UNISI/Tavolo permanente per le fonti orali	28/10/2024	In person	Arezzo, Università di Siena	Gionata di studi		Dissemination	Ricercatori ed esperti nell'ambito di archivi e fonti orali	50	H2IOSC per gli archivi orali - Monica Monachini FAIRness e archivi orali - Claudia Soria, Francesca Frontini	V Giornata di Studi sulle Fonti Orali Le molte voci delle voci Gli archivi orali negli atenei, negli istituti, nei territori	https://www.societadilinguisticaitaliana.net/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Locandina-V-Giornata-di-Studi-dulle-Fonti-Orali.pdf
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN	DARIAH	UniGe	06/11/2024	In person	Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Genova	Meeting	Terzo incontro in presenza della Comunità Italiana dei Data Steward	Engagement and dissemination	Data Steward	40	Progettare Materiali Didattici FAIR: L'esperienza di H2IOSC nella Gestione Condivisa di Oggetti Digitali Complessi		https://opencscience.unige.it/genQAweek2024
OU15 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		CNR-INO, Italy	28/11/2024	In person	Symposium CNR-INO, istituto degli Innocenti, Firenze	Conference		Dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori	300	A performance comparison of 3D survey instruments for their application in the cultural heritage field	In this work, we compared the performance of four 3D instruments based on different working principles by measuring four samples representative of artworks. We verified the accuracy and technical specifications in the suppliers' datasheets by computing the point density and evaluating both the lateral and axial resolution. The comparison between the nominal and calculated values from measuring the former samples was used to predict the performance of the instruments in real-case scenarios.	conference presentation: https://zenodo.org/records/14215766
OU15 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		CNR-INO, Italy	28/11/2024	In person	Symposium CNR-INO, istituto degli Innocenti, Firenze	Symposium		Dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori	300	New Frontiers in Wall Paintings Diagnostics with Non-invasive Techniques	This contribution presents new achievements and challenges in on-site wall painting diagnostic procedures. Using holographic interferometry, infrared thermography, THz imaging, and other methods, our approach goes far beyond the only defect detection, enabling in-depth subsurface analysis and uncovering future risks. We illustrate the contribution of these techniques to current conservation campaigns on renowned wall paintings in Florence, supporting our research by laboratory simulation studies	https://zenodo.org/records/14215766
OU15 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		CNR-INO, Italy	29/11/2024	In person	Symposium CNR-INO, istituto degli Innocenti, Firenze	Symposium		Dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori	300	Women studying women: non-invasive and non-contact optical analysis on the painting Allegory of Inclination by Artemisia Gentileschi	The analysis, carried out by a female team, allowed to identify the pigments, to document the state of conservation of the painting, to study the artist's technique and to reveal the Allegory's original nudity, which was later covered by a drape painted by Volterrano due to its perceived immorality.	conference presentation, https://zenodo.org/records/14215766
OU12 - ISPC-RM	E-RIHS		Università degli Studi Roma Tre	05/12/2024	In person	Università degli Studi Roma Tre - Dipartimento di Architettura	Giornata studi		Dissemination			D-TECH Digital Twin Environment for Cultural Heritage	Illustrato il servizio ATON di E-RIHS e l'integrazione con la federazione H2IOSC, evidenziando aspetti di interoperabilità e le moderne tecnologie web per il settore dei digital twin	
OU11 ISPC-MI	E-RIHS		UO ISPC-MI	17/12/2024	In person	Museo Egizio, Torino	Conference		Dissemination	Accademia, Ricercatori, Musei		Different epigraphies same challenges: crossing borders of disciplinary domains in digital epigraphy	Memory is our Future. International Symposium for the 200th Anniversary of the Museo Egizio, panel "Ancient texts and new technologies" (Torino, 16-18/12/2024)	https://www.museoegizio.it/esplora/appuntamenti/memory-is-our-future-simposio-internazionale/
OU12 - ISPC-RM	E-RIHS		CNR, Italy	17/12/2024	In person	CNR-ISPC, DHILab (sede di Roma)	Event		Dissemination	High school students	16	Esperienze immersive tra archeologia e intelligenza artificiale	L'attività ha previsto la fruizione da parte degli studenti di due esperienze in realtà immersiva: un ambiente archeologico, e un panorama generato con l'AI a partire dal romanzo Il barone rampante. L'esperienza VR è stata presentata attraverso ATON e sono state tracciate le sessioni con i servizi del Pilot 7.7 Interlumo. Al termine dell'attività gli studenti hanno compilato un questionario anonimo incentrato sul senso di presenza dell'esperienza	
OU11 ISPC-MI	E-RIHS		UO ISPC-MI	17/01/2025	In person	Venezia	Round table		Engagement	Accademia, ricercatori	15	Heritage Science and Web Semantic - Innovazione e prospettive per l'epigrafia digitale	The main topic was the application of Semantic Web (SW) technologies in the wider field of Heritage Science. A panel of domain experts - coming from archaeological, historical, and epigraphic disciplines - and knowledge engineers participated. The discussion was centered on the potential of applying SW technologies to large archaeological, historical, and epigraphic datasets.	https://hsort-ec1a1f2.gitlab.io/posts/round-table-venice/
OU12 - ISPC-RM	E-RIHS		Archeologia Viva	23/02/2025	In person	Palazzo dei Congressi, Firenze	Exhibition		dissemination	Professionisti museali, archeologi, studenti	30	TourismA	In due stand. Presso la Fondazione CHANGES è stato presentato un	https://www.tourisma.it/home/
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN			04/03/2025	In person	Tartu, Estonia	Seminar	DHNB 2025	Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori	150	Building a Sustainable CLARIN Trainers' Network: Challenges and Lessons Learnt from the CLARIN-IT Consortium		https://dhnbn.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/DHNB-2025_abstracts.pdf
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CLARIN ERIC	10/03/2025	Online		Seminar	CLARIN Café	Engagement	Accademia, Ricercatori	30	Project Management in DH		https://www.clarin.eu/content/clarin-cafe
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		Fondazione RUT	13/03/2025	In person	Firenze	Invited talk	Fiera Didacta 2025	Engagement	Docenti della scuola secondaria di secondo grado	10	Dalla Ricerca alla Didattica: la Fondazione Rut e l'Infrastruttura CLARIN per lo Studio e l'Interpretazione del Linguaggio		https://www.illc.cnr.it/events/dalla-ricerca-alla-didattica-la-fondazione-rut-e-linfrastruttura-clarin-per-lo-studio-e-linterpretazione-del-linguaggio/
OU11 ISPC-MI	E-RIHS		UO ISPC-MI	26/03/2025	In person	ISPC-CNR, Milano	Round table		Engagement	Accademia, ricercatori	15	Heritage Science and Semantic Web - Semantics for Heritage Conservation	The main topic was the application of Semantic Web technologies in the wider field of Heritage Science. A panel of domain experts - coming from chemistry, geology and natural sciences - and knowledge engineers were present. The discussion was focused on the identification of topics and case studies relevant for the description of tangible Heritage.	https://hsort-ec1a1f2.gitlab.io/posts/round-table-milan/
OU11 ISPC-MI	E-RIHS		UO ISPC-MI	16/04/2025	In person	ISPC-CNR, Milano	Round table		Engagement	Accademia, ricercatori	15	Heritage Science and Semantic Web - Semantics for Archaeology and Heritage Dissemination	The main topic was the application of Semantic Web technologies within the broader field of Heritage Science. The panel included domain experts from Archaeology and Cultural Heritage promoters, alongside knowledge engineers. The discussion centered on identifying key topics and case studies relevant to the description of tangible Heritage.	https://hsort-ec1a1f2.gitlab.io/posts/round-table-milan-bis/
OU12 - ISPC-RM	E-RIHS		Sapienza Università di Roma, Dipartimento di Storia, Disegno e Restauro dell'Architettura	18/04/2025	In person	Sapienza Università di Roma, Facoltà di Architettura, sede Valle Giulia	Conference	3D Modelling & BIM	Engagement and dissemination	Professionisti e accademici nell'ambito dell'architettura	50	(1) Camagni, Casale, Fanini, Ippoliti, Menconero, Tomasella, MUSE: Digital twin per la fruizione museale; (2) Canciani, D'Accolti, Gallo, La Pasta, Digitalizzazione e modellazione 3D per la rigenerazione urbana: il caso di Totfa.	Le due presentazioni orali del convegno sono frutto delle collaborazioni nate attraverso la seconda call TNA/NA: con l'occasione, è stata pubblicata la terza call TNA/NA.	https://www.3d-modeling.it/it/ws2025/

OU7 - ILIESI-RM	OPERAS		European Society for textual scholarship	28/04/2025	In person	Centre d'Études Supérieures de la Renaissance, University of Tours	Conference		Dissemination	Ricercatori	50	Manuscripts And Printed Sources in Leibniz's Geological Writings. A Case Study for the Humanities And Cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud	With around 100000 sheets on an impressive variety of topics, Leibniz's Nachlass constitutes a still partially unexplored witness of the multilayered relevance of manuscripts during the early modern period. The paper analyzes a thematic subset of this corpus, Leibniz's texts on earth history and science, that will be the object of a digital edition in the context of the Humanities and Cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud (H2IOSC) project. While a relatively small subset (around 60 objects, carrying 47 texts, according to current estimation, plus a yet to be defined numbers of letter) it nonetheless provides an interesting variety of text-bearing objects: manuscripts, both autograph and not, printed texts, marginalia. The variety of object crosses the variety of textual typologies (fully developed essays, short notes, drafts, book extract, book reviews, letters) as well as non-textual objects (drawings, sketches, etc.) and, especially in the case of Leibniz's main work on the issue, the Protogaea, provides the material for a genetic reconstruction of the text. I will analyze the set of relations that the corpus entails and the problem it raises in terms of its description via structured metadata.	https://cesr-ests2025.sciencesconf.org/
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CLARIN ERIC	14/05/2025	Online		Seminar	CLARIN Café	Engagement	Accademia, Ricercatori	30	How to Talk to Your Funder: A Funder's Perspective		https://www.clarin.eu/content/clarin-cafe
OU11 ISPC-MI	E-RIHS		UO ISPC-MI	19/05/2025	Online		Workshop		Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori	15	Esperienze di epigrafia digitale a confronto - Presentazione dei corpora	Presentation of the epigraphic corpora to be discussed in the May 2025 workshop	https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/experiences-in-digital-epigraphy-compared/
OU12 - ISPC-RM	E-RIHS		Scuola di Ateneo di Architettura e Design, Università di Camerino	21/05/2025	In person	Scuola di Ateneo di Architettura e Design, Ascoli Piceno	Conference	Career Day 2025	Engagement and dissemination	Studenti/studentesse di architettura e design di Ascoli, imprese marchigiane che operano nel settore dell'architettura e del design	80	L'intervento aveva il titolo: "Nuove tecnologie applicate ai beni culturali. Alcune linee di ricerca del CNR ISPC" e sono stati presentati i servizi ATON e Interlumo.	Invito a partecipare al Career Day 2025 della Scuola di Architettura e Design di Unicam come espressione del mondo del lavoro nella ricerca pubblica.	https://careerday.unicam.it/ascoli/programma.php
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		Comunità Italiana dei Data Stewards	22/05/2025	In person	Firenze	Invited talk	Incontro in presenza della Comunità Italiana Data Stewards	Engagement and dissemination	Data Stewards	60	Piattaforme FAIR-by-Design. Il Training di H2IOSC per il Supporto alla Ricerca		
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		AIUCD	28/05/2025	Online		Invited talk		Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori	10	Introduzione alla Progettazione Didattica FAIR. Metodologie e Strumenti per la Formazione nella Scienza Aperta	La presentazione illustra la metodologia di progettazione didattica e le piattaforme sviluppate nell'ambito della formazione del WP8 "Training, Capacity Building, Engagement" del progetto H2IOSC. Dopo una breve introduzione sulla metodologia FAIR-by-Design, riadattata dal progetto Skills4EOSC, la presentazione anticipa le principali funzionalità delle due piattaforme sviluppate in H2IOSC: il Learning Management System chiamato Training Environment e il repository per materiali didattici riutilizzabili chiamato Training Library a supporto di studenti e docenti nelle Scienze Umane e Sociali e oltre.	https://www.aiucd.it/espertando-aiucd2025/
OU11 - ISPC-MI	E-RIHS		CNR-ISMED, CNR-ISPC	28/05/2025	In person	Caracciolo, Brienza (Pz)	Workshop		dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori	16	Esperienze di epigrafia digitale a confronto	Cnr-ISMed e Cnr-Ispc nel quadro dei progetti PRIN2022 UrBE e PNRR-IR	https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/experiences-in-digital-epigraphy-compared/
OU12 - ISPC-RM	E-RIHS		UNGUESS s.r.l.	29/05/2025	In person	Milano	Workshop		Engagement and dissemination	User researcher (UX/UI)	40	L'uso della nuove tecnologie per l'analisi del comportamento utente in ambiente virtuale: dalla raccolta alla visualizzazione dei dati	Nel contesto dell'evento annuale URCAI, è stato presentato il pilot E-RIHS "Interlumo" con un workshop suddiviso in una parte teorica introduttiva e una parte di esperienza hands-on	https://www.urca.live/agenda
OU11 ISPC-MI	E-RIHS		UO ISPC-MI	11/06/2025	In person	Verona	Conference	AIUCD 2025 - Diversità, Equità e Inclusione: Sfide e Opportunità per l'Informatica Umanistica nell'Era dell'Intelligenza Artificiale	Dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori	234	Presentation of the paper "Modelling an Ontology for Heritage Science: Challenges and Key Strategies" (see Publications)		https://aiucd2025.dlts.univr.it/
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH		DARIAH EU	17/06/2025	In person	Göttinga, Germania	Conference	DARIAH Annual Event 2025 The Past (DAE 2025)	Dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori, professionisti	ca. 300	Building a FAIR Training Ecosystem for the Social Science and Humanities within the H2IOSC project		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15755151
OU15 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		SPIE (The International Society for Optics and Photonics)	23/06/2025	online	Munich, Germany	Conference		Dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori, professionisti	ca.100	Optics for Art, Architecture and Archaeology X	Optimising DHSPi-SIRT detection diagnostics through combined thermal and humidity excitation procedures on fresco mock-ups	https://spie.org/eom/conferencedetails/optics-for-art-architecture-archaeology
OU12 - ISPC-RM	E-RIHS	OU10 - ISPC-LE	H2IOSC	08/07/2025	In person	ISPC-CNR, Napoli	Event		Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori, PMI, PA, No-profit		H2IOSC meets the public and private sectors: presentation of advanced digital services and tools for the cultural field	Presentation of the H2IOSC clusters' services and the initial results from the TNA calls	https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/h2iosc-meets-public-and-private-sectors-in-naples/
OU12 - ISPC-RM	E-RIHS		Università di Siena, CNR, Indiana University, Fraunhofer, Fondazione B. Kessler	08/09/2025	In person	Siena	Workshop	Digital Heritage 2025	Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori	30	Workshop on "Developing interactive web-based virtual environments using ATON and Godot" (see Publications)		https://digitalheritage2025.unisi.it/
OU12 - ISPC-RM	E-RIHS		Università di Siena, CNR, Indiana University, Fraunhofer, Fondazione B. Kessler	09/09/2025	In person	Siena	Conference	Digital Heritage 2025	Dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori	+500	Presentation of the paper "Shaping a Web3D framework for different scientific communities: ATON as a service in H2IOSC" (see Publications)		https://digitalheritage2025.unisi.it/
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR-ILC	09/09/2025	In person	Firenze	Conference	IEEE Cyber Humanities Conference	Engagement	Accademia, ricercatori	20	From Collection to Transcription: a Workflow for Managing Speech Data by the CLARIN Trainers' Network		https://www.ieee-ch.org/
OU12 - ISPC-RM	E-RIHS		Università di Siena, CNR, Indiana University, Fraunhofer, Fondazione B. Kessler	10/09/2025	In person	Siena	Conference	Digital Heritage 2025	Dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori	+500	Presentation of the paper "Exploring Anamorphoses in Immersive Virtual Reality on the Web: Design and Challenges of the Anamorphic Gallery of Anamorphoses (AnGA)" (see Publications)		https://digitalheritage2025.unisi.it/

OU12 - ISPC-RM	E-RIHS		Università di Siena, CNR, Indiana University, Fraunhofer, Fondazione B. Kessler	10/09/2025	In person	Siena	Conference	Digital Heritage 2025	Dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori	+500	Presentation of the paper "Procezo: Data Processing Services for 3D Analytics" (see Publications)	https://digitalheritage2025.unisi.it/
OU15 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		Società Chimica Italiana	10/09/2025	In person	Cremona	Conference		Dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori		Scientific Investigation and Cleaning Strategies for the Conservation of the Gilded Steel Shield of Captain Francesco Bernardo	https://www.congressodabc.it/
E-RIHS	E-RIHS		University of Siena	10/09/2025	in person	Siena; Italy	Conference	Digital Heritage 2025	Dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori, professionisti	>300	Bridging Disciplines for Heritage Professionals: The H2IOSC Digital Training Platform (by CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RIHS and OPERAS)	https://digitalheritage2025.unisi.it/
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH		Roma Tre and DARIAH-IT	10/09/2025	In person & online	Firenze	Conference	IEEE CH	Engagement and dissemination	Ricercatori/PA/PMI	150	annual event co-sponsored by the IEEE Systems, Man, and Cybernetics (SMC) Society. It focuses on theoretical and practical aspects of technologies applied to Social Science and Humanities (SSH) that includes Arts, Heritage, History, Archeology, Linguistics, Libraries, and so forth. SSH	https://www.ieee-ch.org/
OU11 ISPC-MI	E-RIHS		UO ISPC-MI	11/09/2025	In person	Siena	Conference	Digital Heritage 2025	Dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori	+500	Presentation of the paper "H/RADIOSA: Recommended Approaches for the Development of Interoperable Open Semantic Artefacts in the Heritage Domain" (see Publications)	https://digitalheritage2025.unisi.it/
OU12 - ISPC-RM	E-RIHS	OU4 ISPC-FI	Università di Siena, CNR, Indiana University, Fraunhofer, Fondazione B. Kessler	11/09/2025	In person	Siena	Conference	Digital Heritage 2025	Dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori	+500	Presentation of the paper "Early Stage of Community-Driven UI/UX Refactoring of the Open-Source ATON Framework" (see Publications)	https://digitalheritage2025.unisi.it/
OU12 - ISPC-RM	E-RIHS		Università di Siena, CNR, Indiana University, Fraunhofer, Fondazione B. Kessler	11/09/2025	In person	Siena	Conference	Digital Heritage 2025	Dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori	+500	Presentation of the paper "The IlluminAI project: a deep neural network and immersive visualization system to enhance illuminated manuscripts" (see Publications)	https://digitalheritage2025.unisi.it/
OU12 - ISPC-RM	E-RIHS		Roma, Università degli	12/09/2025	In person	Roma	Conference	Representation Disciplines	Dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori	+300	Immersive VR Experience in Il barone rampante by	https://www.unioneitalianadise.gno.it/convegno/2025/
OU12 - ISPC-RM	E-RIHS		CNR, Indiana University, Fraunhofer, Fondazione B. Kessler	12/09/2025	In person	Siena	Expo	Digital Heritage 2025	Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori, professionisti	+500	Booth focused on "Interlumo: Analytics Services of Remote Interactions"	https://digitalheritage2025.unisi.it/
OU12 - ISPC-RM	E-RIHS		CNR ISPC, RUFA, IED, Sapienza Università di Roma	16/09/2025	In person	Roma	Expo	The AFAM Roadshow – Ricerca. Creatività. Innovazione	Engagement and dissemination	Accademia, ricercatori, studenti, PMI	70	Booth focused on "Interlumo: Analytics Services of Remote Interactions" and the WebXR application /imagine	https://grandtourafam.it/evento/emotivita-e-intelligenze-artificiali/
OU12 - ISPC-RM	E-RIHS		CNR, Area Territoriale della Ricerca Roma 1	26/09/2025	In person	Roma	Expo	delle Ricercatrici e dei Ricercatori	Engagement	Pubblico non specialista	1000	Booth focused on ATON, Interlumo and Illuminated Manuscripts Hub	https://notteideiricercatori-4science.cnr.it/
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CLARIN ERIC	30/09/2025	In person	Vienna	Conference	CLARIN Annual Conference 2025	Engagement	Accademia, ricercatori	100		
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR-ILC	06/10/2025	In person & online	Marrakech	Conference	8th IEEE CIST'25 Congress	Engagement	Accademia, ricercatori	50	Transforming Text into Discovery: OCR Enrichment of Digital Collections in the University of Galway Library	Preserving the Cultural Tradition and Written Heritage: Science and Technology in Service of Geritage, Patrimony and Social Values https://www.ieee-congress.org/cist25/

Annex 2 – List of H2IOSC publications

	Authors	Title	Membership Organization (insert UO N. & Acronym if H2IOSC partner institution)	Type of publications (publication, paper, article, report, deliverable, etc.)	Category	Reference	Description	Type (insert one of the two options indicated)	Ambiti disciplinari nel rispetto della Delibera CNR n. 126/2024	Authors TD	Authors ADR	Authors PhD students		
Riga con indicazioni da seguire per compilare le colonne I - J - K - L - M										INSERIRE UNA DELLE DUE OPZIONI DAL MENU A TENDINA	INSERIRE AMBITO DISCIPLINARE, SELEZIONANDO DALLA LISTA DISPONIBILE NEL FOGLIO. Ambiti disciplinari ad esempio: SH8. 1 Archaeological methods and theory, history of archaeology NB: se la pubblicazione ricade in più di un ambito, evidenziare in grassetto quello principale	Inserire chi tra gli autori della pubblicazione è TD (Tempo determinato)	Inserire chi tra gli autori della pubblicazione ha un ADR (Assegno di Ricerca)	Inserire chi tra gli autori della pubblicazione è un Dottorando/a
1	Michela Botticelli; Costanza Milani; Eva Luna Ravan; Claudia Caliri; Francesco Paolo Romano	Naples Yellow Revisited: Insights into Trades and Use in 17th-Century Sicily from the Macro X-ray Fluorescence Scanning of Matthias Stomer's 'The Mocking of Christ'	UO9 ISPC-CT	paper in rivista ISI	Scientific	Heritage 2024, 7(3), 1188-1201; https://doi.org/10.3390/heritage7030057	MA-XRF imaging applied from the MOLAB platform of ERIHS on paintings by Matthias Stomer. Data collection for the pilot on pictorial artworks and testing of analytical tools developed in the project.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Michela Botticelli		Eva Luna Ravan		
2	Zdenek Preisler, Rosario Andolina, Andrea Busacca, Claudia Caliri, Costanza Milani, and Francesco Paolo Romano	Deep learning for enhanced spectral analysis of MA-XRF datasets of paintings	UO9 ISPC-CT	paper in rivista ISI	Scientific	Science Advances 10, eadp6234(2024). DOI: 10.1126/sciadv.adp6234	Recent advancements of noninvasive imaging techniques applied for the study and conservation of paintings have driven a rapid development of cutting-edge computational methods. Macro X-ray fluorescence (MA-XRF), a well-established tool in this domain, generates complex and voluminous datasets that pose analytical challenges. To address this, we have incorporated machine learning strategies specifically designed for the analysis as they allow for identification of nontrivial dependencies and classification within these high-dimensional data, thereby promising comprehensive interrogation. We introduce a deep learning algorithm trained on a synthetic dataset that allows for fast and accurate analysis of the XRF spectra in MA-XRF datasets. This approach successfully overcomes the limitations commonly associated with traditional decomposition methods.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	PE6_11 Machine learning, statistical data processing and applications using signal processing (e.g. speech, image, video); SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Zdenek Preisler, Rosario Andolina				
3	Anna Piccirillo, Paola Buscaglia, Claudia Caliri, Francesco Paolo Romano, Danilo Paolo Pavone, Eva Luna Ravan, Michela Botticelli, Claudia Conti, Maria Catrambone, Costanza Milani, Ilaria Degano, Alessia Andreotti, Federica Nardella, Marco Samadelli, Alice Paladin, Roberta Genta, Michela Cardinali, Federica Pozzi, Daniela Picchi	Unravelling the mummy's shroud: A multi-analytical study of a rare painted textile from Roman Egypt	UO9 ISPC-CT	paper in rivista ISI	Scientific	Journal of Cultural Heritage 2024, 68, 107-121. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2024.05.006	MA-XRF imaging applied from the MOLAB platform of ERIHS on a Roman-Egypt mummy shroud for the study of its polychromy. Data collection for the pilot on pictorial artworks and testing of analytical tools developed in the project.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Michela Botticelli		Eva Luna Ravan		
4	Tiziana Cavaleri, Paola Buscaglia, Enrico Ferraris, Marco Gargano, Michela Botticelli, Francesco Paolo Romano, Claudia Caliri	Discovering manganese-based blacks in the grave goods of Kha and Merit (Egypt, 1450-1400 BCE): Multidisciplinary investigation on use and nature	UO9 ISPC-CT	paper in rivista ISI	Scientific	Dyes and Pigments, 231, 112400. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dysoig.2024.112400	MA-XRF and MA-XRD imaging applied from the MOLAB platform of ERIHS on several New Kingdom-Egypt wood caskets for the study of their polychromy. Data collection for the pilot on pictorial artworks and testing of analytical tools developed in the project.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Michela Botticelli				
5	Winther, T., Tahkokallio, J., Doherty, B., Norrehed, S., Aldo, R., Caliri, C., Albertin, F., Botticelli, M., Nilsson, S. E., Barchi, L., Ravan, E. L., & Heikkilä, T.	The Palette of the Medieval North – a non-invasive investigation of the colourants of ten fragments from Medieval Swedish Manuscripts	UO9 ISPC-CT	paper in rivista ISI	Scientific	Heritage Science, accepted, in press	MA-XRF imaging applied from the MOLAB platform of ERIHS on several fragments from from books thought locally produced in Sweden for the study of their polychromy. Data collection for the pilot on pictorial artworks and testing of analytical tools developed in the project.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Michela Botticelli		Eva Luna Ravan		
6	G. Festa, C. Caliri, M. Botticelli, C.G. Fatuzzo, E. Ferraris, J. Auenmüller, D.P. Pavone, G. Privitera, C. Scalfigno, C. Milani, F.P. Romano	Studying ancient Egyptian copper-alloy objects via X-ray diffraction and Machine Learning	UO9 ISPC-CT	paper in rivista ISI	Scientific	Journal of Cultural Heritage, accepted, in press	The paper reports a novel approach to studying the manufacturing techniques of ancient Egyptian metal objects. The study approach was performed on 12 copper-alloy objects, the majority of which are metal vessels. They were part of the burial assemblage of the Theban Tomb (TT) 8, belonging to the 'overseer of works at the Great Place' Kha and his wife Merit, that was found undisturbed in 1906 in Western Thebes (Egypt). The funerary assemblage, dating to the mid-18th Dynasty (ca. 1425-1352 BCE) is currently kept at Museo Egizio, Turin (Italy). The investigation aimed to gather further	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques; PE6_11 Machine learning, statistical data processing and applications using signal processing (e.g. speech, image, video)	Michela Botticelli				
7	Gianluca Santagati, Claudia Giuseppina Fatuzzo, Andreas Germanos Karydas; Claudia Caliri; Giuliana Aquilanti; Michela Botticelli; Eva Luna Ravan; Francesco Paolo Romano	Development and characterization of a high-sensitivity and high-throughput in-house multimodal TXRF/GIXRF mobile spectrometer	UO9 ISPC-CT	paper in rivista ISI	Scientific	Spectrochimica Acta Part B: Atomic Spectroscopy, Submitted	Total-reflection X-ray Fluorescence (TXRF) and Grazing incidence X-ray Fluorescence (GIXRF) techniques are non-destructive methods widely applied across diverse research domains. These methodologies capitalize on constructive and destructive interferences between grazing incident and reflected X-rays to generate an X-ray standing wave (XSW) field, optimizing excitation conditions at interfaces and reflective surfaces and minimizing background noise thus enabling highly sensitive depth-resolved specific analysis at the nanometer regime. High precision tuning of the angle of incidence allows detection of thin layers down to the nanometer scale. While TXRF is established in global laboratories, advanced methods like GIXRF have predominantly remained confined to synchrotron radiation facilities due to the need of high flux monochromatic X-ray sources as well as	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Michela Botticelli, Gianluca Santagati		Eva Luna Ravan		
8	Eva Luna Ravan, Ariadne Kostomitsopoulou Marketou, Fani Pinakidou, Claudia Caliri, Costanza Milani, Francesco Paolo Romano, Hariclia Brecolouki, Alexandra Rodler-Rorbo and Andreas Germanos Karydas	EGYPTIAN BLUE: VARIABILITY IN PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGY, MATERIAL PROVENANCE AND DETERIORATION	UO9 ISPC-CT	poster	Scientific	EXRS-2024, Athens, June 24-28 2024 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14654590	Il poster illustra uno studio multianalitico e non distruttivo del blu egizio, caratterizzando campioni archeologici con tecniche avanzate come XRF, XANES e XRPD per comprendere provenienza, tecnologia di produzione e degrado dei materiali	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques			Eva Luna Ravan		
9	C. Caliri, C.G. Fatuzzo, D.P. Pavone, G.M. Privitera, E.L. Ravan, Z. Preisler, C. Milani, F.P. Romano	A novel mobile MA-XRF scanner based on a hodoscopic multi-detector system for application in the cultural heritage field	UO9 ISPC-CT	conference presentation	Scientific	EXRS-2024, Athens, June 24-28 2024 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14654221	La presentazione orale ha come oggetto lo sviluppo di un innovativo scanner MA-XRF basato su un sistema multidetector per la caratterizzazione non invasiva di opere d'arte	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Zdenek Preisler		Eva Luna Ravan		
10	E.L. Ravan, F.P. Romano, C. Caliri, C. Milani, D. Bili, D. Magrini, C. Conti, A. Bottone, M. Realini, E. Davanzo, E. Ferraris, V. Turina, F. Rosi	Multimodal noninvasive approach revealing the ancient Egyptian palette	UO9 ISPC-CT	poster	Scientific	Technart 2023, Lisbon, May 7-12 2023 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14654111	Il poster illustra un protocollo analitico multimodale usato per la caratterizzazione della palette pittorica di sei cassette funerarie egizie appartenenti alla tomba di Kha e Merit	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques			Eva Luna Ravan		
11	Francesco Paolo Romano, Costanza Milani, Claudia Caliri, Claudia Fatuzzo, Giulia Privitera, Eva Luna Ravan, Dario Zappalà, Zdenek Preisler	A novel MA-XRD/MA-XRF scanner for pigment-specific mapping of paintings	UO9 ISPC-CT	conference presentation	Scientific	Technart 2023, Lisbon, May 7-12, 2023 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14653997	La presentazione orale ha come oggetto lo sviluppo di uno scanner innovativo sviluppato presso l'XRAYLab dell'ISPC-CNR di Catania, per la caratterizzazione simultanea della distribuzione spaziale degli elementi chimici e delle fasi cristalline dei pigmenti	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques; PE6_11 Machine learning, statistical data processing and applications using signal processing (e.g. speech, image, video)	Zdenek Preisler		Eva Luna Ravan		
12	Anna Piccirillo, Paola Buscaglia, Federica Pozzi, Claudia Caliri, Francesco Paolo Romano, Danilo Paolo Pavone, Eva Luna Ravan, Claudia Conti, Maria Catrambone, Costanza Milani, Ilaria Degano, Alessia Andreotti, Federica Nardella, Marco Samadelli, Alice Paladin, Roberta Genta, Michela Cardinali, Daniela Picchi	An Egyptian mummy of the Roman period with a painted shroud: a multi-analytical study of its technical features	UO9 ISPC-CT	poster	Scientific	Technart 2023, Lisbon, May 7-12 2023 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14653943	Il poster illustra lo studio multianalitico di una rara mummia egizia di periodo romano, con sudario dipinto conservata presso il Museo Civico Archeologico di Bologna.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques			Eva Luna Ravan		
13	Eva Luna Ravan, Francesco Paolo Romano, Ariadne Kostomitsopoulou Marketou, Fani Pinakidou, Kalliope Tsampa, Andreas Germanos Karydas, Hariclia Brecolouki and Claudia Caliri	Egyptian Blue: variability in production technology, material provenance and deterioration	UO9 ISPC-CT	conference presentation	Scientific	EXRS-2024, Athens, June 24-28 2024 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14653855	La presentazione orale ha come oggetto lo studio multianalitico noninvasivo di frammenti di pitture murali provenienti da tombe macedoni del tardo periodo classico e dell'inizio del periodo ellenistico.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques			Eva Luna Ravan		
14	Ariadne Kostomitsopoulou Marketou, Fani Pinakidou, Eva Luna Ravan, Francesco Paolo Romano, Hariclia Brecolouki, Alexandra Rodler-Rorbo and Andreas Germanos Karydas	On the production of Egyptian blue: sXRF and XANES analysis of pigment pellets	UO9 ISPC-CT	conference presentation	Scientific	EXRS-2024, Athens, June 24-28 2024 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14653807	La presentazione orale si propone di far luce sul processo di produzione del blu egizio attraverso l'analisi di pellet di pigmento inutilizzati provenienti da siti archeologici.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques			Eva Luna Ravan		

15	Ariadne Kostomitsopoulou Marketou, Fani Pinakidou, Eva Luna Ravan, Francesco Paolo Romano, Hariclia Brecolouaki, Alexandra Rodier-Rarbo, Andreas Germanos Karydas	TRACING THE TRAJECTORIES OF EGYPTIAN BLUE PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGY: XRD, SXRF AND SXANES ANALYSIS OF HELLENISTIC AND ROMAN SAMPLES	U09 ISPC-CT	conference presentation	Scientific	30th Annual Meeting of the European Association of Archaeologists (EAA) in Rome, Italy, August 27-31 2024 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14653624	La presentazione orale tratta l'analisi XRF e XANES di campioni di blu egizio provenienti da diversi siti archeologici, svolta presso ELETTRA (sincrotrone, Trieste) combinate con misure XRD effettuate presso l'XRAYLab dell'ISPC-CNR di Catania	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8_Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques			Eva Luna Ravan
16	Liggins, Florence, Detalle, Vincent, Romano, Francesco Paolo, Cassetti, Patrick, Liang, Haida, S. Kogou, C.S. Cheung, A. Vichi, A. Suzuki, V. Detalle, X Bai, M. Botticelli, C. Caliri, E. Ravan, C. Tennenini, P. Cassiti	UNDERSTANDING THE CAROLINGIAN ARTIST THROUGH A NOVEL WORKFLOW INVOLVING MULTIMODAL REMOTE AND IN-SITU SPECTRAL IMAGING AND SPECTROSCOPIC TECHNIQUES	U09 ISPC-CT	conference presentation	Scientific	30th EAA (European Association of Archaeologists) Annual Meeting, Sapienza University of Rome, Rome, Italy https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14658235	La presentazione orale ha come oggetto lo studio multianalitico per la caratterizzazione dei materiali originali e i prodotti di degrado di pitture murali storiche del convento benedettino di Saint John (Mustair, Svizzera).	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH8_Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Michela Botticelli		Eva Luna Ravan
17	C. Caliri, R. Andolina, M. Botticelli, Z. Preister, E.L. Ravan, G. Santagati, C. Miliani, F.P. Romano	Novel X-ray imaging techniques for the noninvasive investigation of European Heritage within MOLAB platform of E-RIHS	U09 ISPC-CT	conference presentation	Scientific	EXRS 2024 (European Conference on X-ray Spectrometry), 6-13 June 2024, Athens, Greece https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14671972	The MOLAB platform of E-RIHS, the European Infrastructure for Heritage Science, provides access to advanced analytical spectroscopies for the non-invasive characterization of tangible cultural heritage on site. XRAYLab of the Institute of Heritage Science (ISPC-CNR) in Catania specializes in developing novel mobile X-ray instruments for use in MOLAB's collaborative projects. In the measurement activities performed, we have combined on the same object different analytical techniques to investigate both the chemical nature of the painted materials and their layered structure. A highly sensitive MA-XRF scanner with on-the-fly imaging capabilities, a strongly focused beam and 6-SDDs. A novel MA-XRPD based on linear Si-strip detectors covering the Bragg region is then applied for obtaining pigment specific identification and to highlight their related degradation products. Finally, we recently introduced a mobile high-resolution digital radiography equipped with a motorized frame	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8_Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques; PE6_11 Machine learning, statistical data processing and applications using signal processing (e.g. speech, image, video)	Michela Botticelli, Rosario Andolina, Zdenek Preister, Gianluca Santagati		Eva Luna Ravan
18	M. Botticelli, E.L. Ravan, D.P. Pavone, C. Caliri, F.P. Romano, B. Doherty, F. Sabatini, F. Albertin, F. Rosi, A. Romani, S. Kogou, F. Liggins, C.S. Cheung, H. Liang, N. Kladiouri, K. Tsampa, A.G. Karydas, A. Georgiadou, H. Brecolouaki	The MOLAB transnational access for an in-situ investigation of the Hunt frieze of the tomb of Philip II at Aigai (Vergina, Greece)	U09 ISPC-CT	conference presentation	Scientific	X-ray fluorescence imaging (MA-XRF) and reflectance imaging spectroscopy (RIS), The George Washington University, Washington DC, USA. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14653080	Funerary paintings from ancient Macedonia produced under the reign of Philip II and Alexander the Great offer the most significant insights into monumental painting during the late Classical and early Hellenistic period. On the large-scale compositions decorating the façades and the interiors of Macedonian tombs it is possible to investigate the ancient painters' techniques and to explore the themes of a local funerary iconography. A recent analytical campaign by the MOLAB facilities within the IPERION HS Consortium as part of the research project REVIS, funded by the Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation, assisted in the characterization of the largest and most famous Classical painting, the Hunt frieze of the façade of the Tomb of Philip II at ancient Aigai (Vergina), NE Greece, providing non-invasive mobile in-situ analyses: MA-XRF and XRD, single-point reflection spectroscopy in the Vis-NIR-SWIR and mid-IR ranges, Vis-NIR (400-1000nm) reflectance spectral imaging (RSI) at close range on scaffolding platform and remote sensing techniques at ~10m from the ground such as VIS-SWIR (400-2500nm) BSI, laser induced fluorescence (LIF) spectral imaging and Raman	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8_Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Michela Botticelli		Eva Luna Ravan
19	Monica Monacini	H2IOSC per la transizione digitale e l'innovazione sociale	U0 08 ILC	Article (newspaper)	Outreach	https://corisc.sherpoint.com/~/~/sites/PNRR-InfrastrutturaGenerale2-EDITORIALBOARD/Documents/20-condviva/EDITORIAL%20BOARD/ARTICOLI_outreach/scenari_29_gennaio_2024_7%20%11.pdf?c=1&web=1&e=wGEF0Y						
20	A. Dal Fovo, M. Morello, A. Mazzinghi, C. Toso, M. Galeotti, E. Pampaloni, R. Fontana	Spectral mapping techniques for the stratigraphic and compositional characterization of a 16th century painting	U015 INO-FI	paper in rivista ISI	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.1140/eop/s13360-023-04738-z	This paper investigates the stratigraphy and pigments distribution of a 16th-century painting from the Uffizi Galleries collection. Cross-sectional SEM-EDS analysis and elemental mapping to obtain preliminary compositional information and to make an initial hypothesis about the pigments used for specific areas of the painting. RIS was then performed on the entire painting and the SCM classification algorithm was applied to the image cube.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8_Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE6_11 Machine learning statistical data processing and applications using signal processing; SH8_4 Museums, exhibitions, conservation and restoration	Alice Dal Fovo		
21	M. Galeotti, S. Porcinai, A. Cagnini, M. Baruffetti, C. Blondi, A. Dal Fovo, R. Fontana	Organic Patinas on Small Historical Bronzes: From Mock-Ups to Actual Artworks	U015 INO-FI	paper in rivista ISI	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.3390/coatings14020712	This paper reports the preliminary results of a broad project aimed at investigating organic coatings on indoor historical bronzes. A multi-analytical approach, based on a set of noninvasive techniques, was applied to study the composition, thickness, and morphology of both a series of mock-ups and a real artwork, a Renaissance bronze relief.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8_Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE6_11 Machine learning statistical data processing and applications using signal processing; SH8_4 Museums, exhibitions, conservation and restoration	Alice Dal Fovo		
22	A. Dal Fovo, R. Fontana, R. Cicchi	Stratigraphic mapping of paintings by multispectral reflectography	U015 INO-FI	paper in rivista ISI	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.1140/eop/s13360-023-04738-z	This paper reports on the use of diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS) to obtain stratigraphic information about painting materials. The thickness of pictorial layers can be quantified by the intensity of the spectral reflectance factor measured at a given wavelength in the infrared. Multispectral reflectography can be used to obtain thickness maps of paint layers, exploiting the transparency of pigments in narrow spectral regions where it is possible to identify significant spectral features.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8_Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE6_11 Machine learning statistical data processing and applications using signal processing; SH8_4 Museums, exhibitions, conservation and restoration	Alice Dal Fovo		
23	A. Dal Fovo, L. Sepiacchi, S. Innocenti, J. Striova, R. Fontana	Botticelli-style tempera portrait on tile: Imaging and specific on-site spectroscopic analysis and cleaning examination	U015 INO-FI	paper in rivista ISI	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2023.11.023	In this work, three non-invasive spectroscopic techniques, i.e., RIS, SSE TM -RS, and FORS were applied to shed light on the authorship of a painting belonging to the collection of the Uffizi Galleries. To this aim, the composing materials and the execution technique were investigated to assess their compatibility with Botticelli's production. To provide support for an informed restoration process the colour variations induced by the cleaning intervention were quantified.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8_Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE6_11 Machine learning statistical data processing and applications using signal processing; SH8_4 Museums, exhibitions, conservation and restoration	Alice Dal Fovo		Silvia Innocenti
24	R. Fontana, A. Dal Fovo, M. Giugni, I. Lughni, S. Innocenti, M. Raffaelli, J. Striova, E. Vannini	Analisi ottiche non invasive e non a contatto sull'allegoria dell'Inclinazione	U015 INO-FI	capitolo di un libro	Scientific	Ed. Officina Libraria, 2024, p. 304, ISBN: 9788833672502	p. 167-172, in "Artemisia Gentileschi: l'Inclinazione per Michelangelo Buonarroti il Giovane", Curated by: Cristina Acidini and Alessandro Cecchi; Collection: "Buonarrotiana. Studi su Michelangelo e la famiglia Buonarroti"	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8_Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; SH8_3 Cultural studies and theory, cultural identities and memories, cultural heritage; SH8_4 Museums, exhibitions, conservation and restoration	Alice Dal Fovo		Silvia Innocenti
25	L. Benassi, J. Striova, D. I. Quintero Balbas, S. Manconi, Szikszai, Z.	E-RIHS IP D5.3 E-RIHS ERIC Catalogue of Service: Approach and Advancement	U015 INO-FI	deliverable	-	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4002040	Based on the experience of IPERION HS and other research infrastructures, the E-RIHS service catalogue will be built as a standalone platform and it will have two components: the frontend, that will have a user-friendly interface and the backend that will be composed of a system of dashboards and BI tools for monitoring the performance of the access provision over time. The E-RIHS service catalogue will be implemented with a FAIR data management and in a way to be easily integrated and connected with the EOSC environment	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH8_9 - Digital approaches to anthropology, cultural studies and art; PE6_10 - Web and information systems, data management systems, information retrieval and digital libraries, data fusion; SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere	Diego Iván Quintero Balbás		
26	A. Caravale, N. Duran-Silva, B. Grimau, P. Moscati, B. Rondelli	Developing a digital archaeology classification system using Natural Language Processing and Machine Learning techniques.	U012-ISPC RM	paper in rivista	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.19282/ac.34.2.2023.01	The Authors propose a knowledge map to analyse and access scientific contents related to Digital Archeology by leveraging various Machine Learning (ML) techniques. The case study concerns the articles published in our international journal "Archeologia e Calcolatori" in the decade from 2011 to 2020 and, as a benchmark, the publications in the "Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology" (CAA) conference proceedings and journal. The titles and abstracts of the publications featured in these two data sets were analysed using a supervised classification approach into the subfields of computer science, based on the ACM's taxonomy, and by applying topic modelling techniques to discover emergent topics, Named Entity Recognition to identify specific archaeologically relevant entities, and geotagging techniques to link articles with the geographical locations they discuss. The results achieved, although preliminary, provide some methodological suggestions: i) the opportunity to build custom analyses by taking advantage of the increasing availability of open data and metadata; ii) the scope of the contribution of archaeology, and in particular of computational archaeology, to the Heritage Science interdisciplinary domain; the heuristic and predictive role of different ML techniques to gain a multi-faceted access to data analysis and interpretation.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8_6 Digital, computational, virtual and geospatial archaeologies			
27	D. Avola, L. Cinque, A. Di Mambro, A. Fagioli, M.R. Marini, D. Panone, B. Faini, and G. Foresti	Spatio-Temporal Image-Based Encoded Atlases for EEG Emotion Recognition	U012-ISPC RM	paper in rivista	Scientific	https://www.worldscientific.com/doi/10.1142/S0129065724500242	Emotion recognition plays an essential role in human-human interaction since it is a key to understanding the emotional states and reactions of human beings when they are subject to events and engagements in everyday life. Moving towards human-computer interaction, the study of emotions becomes fundamental because it is at the basis of the design of advanced systems to support a broad spectrum of application areas, including forensic, rehabilitative, educational, and many others. In particular, the proposed system extracts spatio-temporal image encodings, or atlases, from EEG data through the Processing and transfer of Interaction States and Mappings through Image-based eNcoding (PRISMIN) framework, thus obtaining a compact representation of the input signals. PRISMIN is one of the services exposed in WPE	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	PE6_11 Machine learning, statistical data processing and applications using signal processing (e.g. speech, image, video); PE6_7 Artificial intelligence, intelligent systems, natural language processing; PE6_3 Software engineering, programming languages and systems			

28	Bruno Fanini & Giorgio Gosti	A new generation of collaborative immersive analytics on the web: open-source services to capture, process and inspect users' sessions in 3D environments	UO12-IPSC RM	paper in rivista	Scientific	https://www.mdpi.com/1999-5903/16/5/147	Recording large amounts of users' sessions performed through 3D applications may provide crucial insights into interaction patterns. Such data can be captured from interactive experiences in public exhibits, remote motion tracking equipment, immersive XR devices, lab installations or online web-applications. Immersive Analytics (IA) deals with benefits and challenges of using immersive environments for data analysis and related design solutions to improve the quality and efficiency of the analysis process. Today web technologies allow us to craft complex applications accessible through common browsers, and APIs like WebXR allow us to interact and explore virtual 3D environments using immersive devices. WebXR IA tools are still quite new in literature: they present several challenges, and leave quite unexplored the possibility of synchronous collaborative inspection. The opportunity to share the virtual space with remote analysts in fact, improves sense-making tasks and offers new ways to discuss interaction patterns together, while inspecting captured records or data aggregates. Furthermore, with proper collaborative approaches, analysts are able to share Machine Learning (ML) pipelines and constructively discuss the outcomes and insights through tailored data visualization, directly inside immersive 3D spaces, using a web browser. Under the H2IOSC project (pilot 7.7), we present the first results of an open-source pipeline involving tools and services for capturing, processing, and inspecting interactive sessions collaboratively in WebXR with other analysts. The modular pipeline can be easily deployed in research infrastructures (RIs), remote dedicated hubs or local scenarios. We deployed the pipeline to assess the different services and to better understand how people interact with generative AI environments. Obtained results can be easily adopted for a multitude of case studies, interactive applications, remote equipment or online applications, to support or accelerate the detection of interaction patterns among remote analysts, collaborating in the same 3D space.	PE6_9 Human computer interaction and interface, visualisation; PE6_7 Artificial intelligence, intelligent systems, natural language processing; PE6_11 Machine learning, statistical data processing and applications using signal processing (e.g. speech, image, video)	Giorgio Gosti	
29	M. Mallia, M. Bandini, A. Bellandi, F. Murano, S. Piccini, L. Rigobianco, A. Tommasi, C. Zavattari, M. Zini, V. Quochi	DigitAnt: a platform for creating, linking and exploiting LOD lexica with heterogeneous resources	UO 08 ILC	paper	Scientific	Proceedings of the 9th Workshop on Linked Data in Linguistics (LDI-2024)	Over the past few years, the deployment of Linked Open Data (LOD) technologies has witnessed significant advancements across a myriad of sectors, linguistics included. This progression is characterized by an exponential increase in the conversion of resources to adhere to contemporary encoding standards. Such transformations are driven by the objectives outlined in "ecological" methodologies, notably the FAIR data principles, which advocate for the reuse and interoperability of resources. This paper introduces the solutions devised within a nationwide collaborative research project aimed at integrating techniques and methodologies from the conventional study of epigraphic materials, computational lexicography, semantic web, and other digital humanities subfields. It details its services, utilities, and data types and shows how it manages to produce, exploit, and interlink LLOD and non-LLOD datasets in ways that are meaningful to its intended target disciplinary context, i.e. historical linguistics over epigraphic data. The paper also introduces how DigitAnt services and functionalities will contribute to the empowerment of a recently started Italian infrastructure cluster project devoted to the construction of a nationwide federation of research infrastructures for the humanities and cultural heritage, and in particular to its pilot project towards establishing an authoritative LLOD platform.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere	M. Mallia
30	M. Mallia, R. Del Gratta, V. Quochi	Funzioni e sostenibilità di una piattaforma digitale per le lingue arcaiche	UO 08 ILC	paper	Scientific	Proceedings of the AIUCD 2024	Questo studio introduce il tema della sostenibilità a lungo termine delle applicazioni o piattaforme digitali di fruizione di materiali linguistici ed epigrafici nel contesto delle infrastrutture di ricerca per le scienze umane e sociali e ne propone una prima valutazione tecnica partendo da un'esperienza attuale e concreta: la piattaforma web del progetto DigitAnt	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere	M. Mallia
31	Roberta Bianca Luzzi, Maria Caradonna, Alessandra Caravale, Antonio D'Eredità, Niccolò Giampietro, Giacomo Mancuso, Paola Moscati, Valeria Quochi, Alessia Spadi, Monica Monachini and Emiliano Degl'Innocenti	Digital Humanities and Heritage Science: moving from landscaping to a dynamic research observatory in an Open Science Cloud	UO 08 ILC, UO 01 OVI-FI	paper	Scientific	Proceedings of the AIUCD 2024	The contribution presents the work carried out in the second work package of the Humanities and Heritage Italian Science Cloud (H2IOSC) infrastructural project dedicated to "Landscaping and Building Communities". The activity involved a comprehensive survey/investigation encompassing language technologies, digital humanities, and heritage science disciplines in Italy. The aim of the landscaping was to collect information on the latest and most prevalent resources, tools, communities, best practices, standards, and projects developed within the Heritage, Social Sciences, and Digital Humanities communities. In this work package, the four partnering infrastructures - CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RHS, and OPERAS - collaborated closely to develop the best strategies for engaging and meeting the needs of their target research communities as well as to identify the set of priority items (resources, tools, and services) to FAIRify and onboard into the national Marketplace.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere SH4_6 Learning, memory; cognition in ageing SH4_9 Theoretical linguistics; computational linguistics	Roberta Bianca Luzzi, Antonio D'Eredità, Nicola Giampietro, Giacomo Mancuso, Alessia Spadi
32	Giulia Pedonese, Francesca Frontini, Roberta Ottaviani, Federico Boschetti, Alessia Spadi, Lucia Francalanci, Alessia Scognamiglio, Pietro Restaneo, Antonina Chaban, Jana Striova, Laura Benassi	Materiali didattici come oggetti digitali FAIR: una metodologia condivisa per la formazione in H2IOSC	UO 08 ILC, UO 01 OVI-FI	poster	Scientific	Proceedings of the AIUCD 2024	Il presente lavoro dettaglia la strategia per lo sviluppo di iniziative di formazione nell'ambito del progetto H2IOSC e mira a coinvolgere la comunità italiana di riferimento sulle modalità di design e di fruizione di moduli didattici che integrino l'uso delle infrastrutture di Ricerca. In particolare, il contributo si sofferma sulla descrizione dei requisiti per l'implementazione dell'infrastruttura di training e sugli standard condivisi per la descrizione dei materiali didattici come oggetti digitali FAIR al fine di massimizzare il riutilizzo in un'ottica train the trainers.	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere	Giulia Pedonese, Roberta Ottaviani, Alessia Spadi, Lucia Francalanci, Antonina Chaban	
33	M. Mallia	A Digital Platform for Pan-Latin Lexicons: Utilizing SKOSMOS for Vocabulary Visualization and Management	UO 08 ILC	poster	Scientific	CLARIN CONFERENCE 2024	The ILCACLARIN platform provides a robust environment for managing and publishing controlled vocabularies, thesauri, and taxonomies. This service, designed for partners in the national CLARIN-IT consortium and the H2IOSC project, plays a key role in ensuring semantic interoperability across diverse datasets and research projects. The platform leverages the open-source software SKOSMOS, which supports the SKOS (Simple Knowledge Organization System) data model. Researchers can explore structured concepts, visualize hierarchies, and access vocabulary data via intuitive search interfaces and thematic indexes.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere	M. Mallia
34	A. Tommasi, C. Zavattari, M. Mallia, V. Quochi	REST Services for Corpus management Annotation and Search	UO 08 ILC	paper	Scientific	CLARIN CONFERENCE 2024	This paper presents a back-end software that offers a set of micro web services for the general purpose management and search of text documents and annotations. Initially developed for a digital epigraphy project, the system focuses on integrating texts and lexicons represented in different paradigms. Nonetheless, the solution is designed to be general and adaptable across various domains.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	PE6_10 Web and information systems, data management systems, information retrieval and digital libraries, data fusion; SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere	M. Mallia
35	Sofia Pescarin, Marcello Massida, Manuele Veggì, Samuele Spotti, Laura Travaglini	Co-Design Tool for Cultural Heritage Experiences (v. 0.9.0)	UO 04 ISPC - FI	tool	Scientific	Zenodo Open Access Publication, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10986215	Il presente lavoro consiste in uno strumento di codesign per la creazione collaborativa di esperienze nell'ambito del patrimonio culturale, in linea con gli obiettivi dell'attività 7.9. Si rivolge a diversi stakeholder del progetto H2IOSC, quali ricercatori, professionisti del settore culturale e designer. In questa prima versione cartacea, basata sul toolkit VisitorBox, è possibile definire i design requirements e dettagliare la struttura dell'esperienza finale. L'architettura modulare di questo progetto consentirà di includere in futuro anche ulteriori fasi di design e parte degli strumenti e della metodologia adottati verranno reimpiantati nella progettazione e nella realizzazione del prototipo finale.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH8_9: Digital approaches to anthropology, cultural studies and art	M. Massida
36	Sofia Pescarin, Marcello Massida, Laura Travaglini	Interactive Digital Narrative Authoring Tools and Hybrid Experiences in Cultural Heritage: An Integrated Review	UO 04 ISPC - FI	conference proceedings	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.2312/gch.20231155	Interactive Digital Narrative Authoring Tools (IDN-AT) are software applications that allow users, without the need for programming skills, to create, design, and publish interactive digital narrative applications. In the field of Digital Heritage and specifically in that of Virtual Museums there is an increasing need of such tools, to enable non-programmers (designers, creatives and curators) to design and develop hybrid experiences in cultural contexts. This paper aims at reviewing available solutions, defining the gaps and still missing features, tools or services, with the goal of paving the way for a webXR integrated solution.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8_9: Digital approaches to anthropology, cultural studies and art	M. Massida
37	Sofia Pescarin, Marcello Massida, Laura Travaglini	Interactive Digital Narrative Authoring Tools and Hybrid Experiences in Cultural Heritage: An Integrated Review	UO 04 ISPC - FI	conference proceedings	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.2312/gch.20231155	Interactive Digital Narrative Authoring Tools (IDN-AT) are software applications that allow users, without the need for programming skills, to create, design, and publish interactive digital narrative applications. In the field of Digital Heritage and specifically in that of Virtual Museums there is an increasing need of such tools, to enable non-programmers (designers, creatives and curators) to design and develop hybrid experiences in cultural contexts. This paper aims at reviewing available solutions, defining the gaps and still missing features, tools or services, with the goal of paving the way for a webXR integrated solution.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8_9: Digital approaches to anthropology, cultural studies and art	M. Massida

38	Alberto Bucciero, Mohamed Emar, Alessandra Chirivì, Matteo Greco, Riccardo Colella, Andrea Pandurino, Francesco Taurino, Davide Zecca,	H2IOSC Project: The Italian Federated Cluster for IoT-based Monitoring and Digital Twinning of Cultural Heritage	OU10 - ISPC-LE	conference proceedings	Scientific	Accepted to SpliTech 2024 - 9th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies (SpliTech 2024) - co-sponsored by IEEE ComSoc, IEEE CRFID	The H2IOSC project aims to create a federated cluster of research infrastructures (RIs) in the domain of Cultural Heritage at the national level in Italy. Through four key RIs — DARIJA-IT, CLARIN, OPERAS, and E-RIHS — the project enables collaboration among researchers with interdisciplinary expertise. Within this context, DIGILAB emerges as a digital access platform for the Italian node of ERIHS, providing data management, digital tools, and services to boost cultural heritage preservation, fruition, and study. A significant aspect of DIGILAB architecture is its capability to support geo-localization and real-time monitoring of cultural heritage sites in terms of environmental conditions, structural integrity, and diagnostics, leveraging on novel Internet of Things (IoT) systems and large-scale Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs). By integrating WSNs into DIGILAB framework, the project enhances remote monitoring and control of cultural sites. These networks facilitate the collection of real-time data on factors such as temperature, humidity, and air quality, providing crucial insights for the Cultural Heritage research community. Moreover, WSNs enable proactive measures to be taken in response to emerging threats, mitigating risks and minimizing damage to cultural assets at a national level.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH8_10 Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage PE6_6 Informatics and information systems PE7_5 Systems engineering, sensorics, actorics, automation PE10_15 Earth observations from space/remote sensing	Mohamed Emar, Matteo Greco, Riccardo Colella, Andrea Pandurino, Francesco Taurino, Davide Zecca
39	Alberto Bucciero, Dora Francesca Barbolla, Giovanni Leucci, Riccardo Colella, Giuseppe Cannazza, Lara De Giorgi, Chiara Torre	NEW PROJECT FOR A SURFACE PENETRATING RADAR	OU10 - ISPC-LE	conference proceedings	Scientific	Accepted to SpliTech 2024 - 9th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies (SpliTech 2024) - co-sponsored by IEEE ComSoc, IEEE CRFID	For surface scanning applications of frescoes, plasters, and other works of art, it is necessary to use a high working frequency, to obtain good spatial resolution and adequate penetration. In this case, we chose to use a working frequency between 4 GHz and 6 GHz, which corresponds to a wavelength of approximately 1 cm in a medium in which the propagation speed of the electromagnetic wave is 0.07m/ns. At this frequency, objects with dimensions of the order of a millimeter and depths of up to a few tens of centimeters can be detected. The instrumentation aims to provide images of the object under examination from which it is possible to determine, without ambiguity, its morphological and electromagnetic properties (dielectric permittivity and conductivity). Furthermore, an application will be possible that allows remote detection of vital signs (for example breathing and heartbeat).	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH8_10 Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage PE7_5 Systems engineering, sensorics, actorics, automation PE10_15 Earth observations from space/remote sensing	Dora Francesca Barbolla, Riccardo Colella, Giuseppe Cannazza
40	Eva Pietroni, Alessandra Chirivì, Bruno Fanini & Alberto Bucciero	An Innovative Approach to Shape Information Architecture Related to Ancient Manuscripts, Through Multi-layered Virtual Ecosystems. From Codex4D to DataSpace Project	OU10 - ISPC-LE; UO12-ISPC-RM	conference proceedings	Scientific	Extended Reality, XR Salento 2023. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 14219. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-43404-4_16	This contribution deals with the theme of ancient manuscripts and proposes an innovative approach to the construction of cultural ecosystems and virtual representations capable of integrating information levels of various kinds: not only textual and iconographic contents, as it usually happens, but also the form, structure, stratigraphy and elements hidden beneath the pictorial layers or beneath the texts visible on the surface, the constituent materials, the execution techniques, the state of conservation and the storytelling of the cultural context. This multidisciplinary approach results in a multidimensional virtual representation. Starting from the same data set, this cultural model is differently applied in a plurality of digital environments: 1) a 3D Web App, developed in the framework of the Code4D project, conceived for the scientific visualisation of the manuscript; the analytical exploration of the virtual model and its information levels; 2) a holographic showcase, again developed in the context of the Code4D project, conceived for the general public of museums and libraries, in which the research data are translated into a mixed-reality environment adopting a dramaturgical style; 3) an online digital platform, the DataSpace, mostly oriented to the scientific community, whose scope is to semantically organize, preserve in the long term, access, share and re-use information and data set produced by the Institute of Heritage Science, together with the documentation of processes and actions that led to their production. The contribution develops around these themes: conceptual maps, information architecture, user-experience design, and virtual environments to increase the knowledge of ancient manuscripts, in relation to various typologies of users.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH8_10 Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage PE6_9 Human computer interaction and interface, visualisation; SH6_6 Digital, computational, virtual and geospatial archaeologies	
41	A. BUCCIERO, A. CHIRIVÌ, B. FANINI, M. MASSIDA, S. PESCARIN, F. TAURINO	Soluzioni integrate web-based per il Patrimonio Culturale: una prospettiva	OU10 - ISPC-LE	conference proceedings	Scientific	Conferenza GARR 2022 - CondVisioni - La rete come strumento per costruire il futuro - selected Papers, Conferenza GARR, Palermo, 18-20 maggio 2022 - ISBN: 978-88-946629-1-7 DOI: 10.26314/GARR-Conf22-proceedings	Assistiamo ad una crescente richiesta di soluzioni integrate web-based a supporto della conoscenza e valorizzazione del patrimonio culturale. Il presente articolo fornisce una panoramica sulle più recenti attività e iniziative orientate al web nei campi dei beni culturali. Vengono quindi proposti alcuni esempi di strumenti, servizi e applicazioni realizzate dal CNR. Si conclude infine con le sfide lanciate dalle nuove priorità europee in merito alle infrastrutture delle Heritage Science, la Digital Library per il Patrimonio Culturale e il Cloud della Ricerca	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8_10 Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage PE6_10 Web and information systems, data management systems, information retrieval and digital libraries, data fusion SH5_11 Digital humanities computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere	M. MASSIDA, F. TAURINO
42	Caravale A., Moscati P., Rossi I.	Landscaping and Integrating Digital Archaeology and Digital Epigraphy resources: new challenges and future opportunities. Introduction to the Special section	UO11 ISPC-MI; UO12-ISPC RM	paper	Scientific	Caravale A., Moscati P., Rossi I. 2024, Landscaping and Integrating Digital Archaeology and Digital Epigraphy resources: new challenges and future opportunities. Introduction to the Special section, in Caravale C., Moscati P., Rossi I. (eds.), The H2IOSC project and its impact on digital antiquity within the E-RIHS infrastructure – I, «Archeologia e Calcolatori», 35.1, 515-520. https://doi.org/10.19282/ac.35.1.2024.30	Introduction to Special section The H2IOSC project and its impact on digital antiquity within the E-RIHS infrastructure	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH6_6 Digital, computational, virtual and geospatial archaeologies	
43	Mancuso G., D'Eredità A.	DHeLO and BiDIAR: new digital resources within the H2IOSC Project	UO12-ISPC RM	paper	Scientific	Mancuso G., D'Eredità A. 2024, DHeLO and BiDIAR: new digital resources within the H2IOSC Project, in Caravale C., Moscati P., Rossi I. (eds.), The H2IOSC project and its impact on digital antiquity within the E-RIHS infrastructure – I, «Archeologia e Calcolatori», 35.1, 521-542. https://doi.org/10.19282/ac.35.1.2024.31	This paper explores the initial outcomes of the H2IOSC Project, specifically within Work Package 2 (WP2 - Landscaping & Building Communities), which aims to survey the Italian digital landscape in Language Technologies, Humanities, and Heritage Science (HS). A significant outcome of the efforts of the Rome branch of CNR-ISPC is the development of two key resources: the DHeLO web app and the BiDIAR bibliographic collection. DHeLO (Digital Heritage Landscaping Platform) is designed to collect, store, and query metadata of research projects, products, and digital tools in Cultural Heritage (CH) and Heritage Science (HS). It aims to create a comprehensive disciplinary observatory by integrating data from multiple sources into a structured system that allows for complex queries and data indexing. This platform supports the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) and includes metadata standards based on the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI). BiDIAR (Bibliography of Digital Archaeology) functions as a relational database within Zotero, an open-source bibliographic tool. It compiles bibliographic entries relevant to digital archaeology, integrating themes and research outputs from the «Archeologia e Calcolatori» journal. This database aids in thematic trend analysis and network analysis by linking bibliographic citations, enhancing the understanding of research dynamics and impacts within the E-RIHS community. Analyzing these resources reveals an exponential increase in virtual reality and 3D modeling products, driven by epistemological developments and the disruptive use of photogrammetric modeling. These tools not only enhance data accessibility and usability but also support interdisciplinary collaboration and innovation in digital heritage and archaeology.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH6_6 Digital, computational, virtual and geospatial archaeologies	Mancuso G., D'Eredità A.
44	Scarpa E., Valente R.	A resource hub for interoperability and data integration in Heritage research: the H-SetIS database	UO11 ISPC-MI	paper	Scientific	Scarpa E., Valente R. 2024, A resource hub for interoperability and data integration in Heritage research: the H-SetIS database, in Caravale C., Moscati P., Rossi I. (eds.), The H2IOSC project and its impact on digital antiquity within the E-RIHS infrastructure – I, «Archeologia e Calcolatori», 35.1, 543-562. https://doi.org/10.19282/ac.35.1.2024.32	This article explores the contributions of the Milan branch of CNR-ISPC to the Humanities and Cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud (H2IOSC) Project, focusing on facilitating data integration within Heritage Science. Its primary objective is to ensure seamless interoperability between resources from multiple institutions by establishing a shared semantic framework. The multidisciplinary nature of Heritage Science underscores the necessity for shared data repositories and effective management tools. Recent literature highlights the importance of semantic technologies in improving data integration and interoperability. To this end, the H-SetIS database is currently under development. H-SetIS will function as a hub for the systematic surveying and description of various semantic tools relevant to the Heritage domain. Interestingly, a preliminary analysis of data within H-SetIS reveals that many semantic resources specifically designed to address the unique requirements of the Heritage domain do not meet the minimum quality requirements of accessibility and reusability. This finding underscores a potential area for future development: the creation of H-SetIS aims to support the ongoing development of a comprehensive ontology for Cultural Heritage, enhancing data FAIRness and the discipline's overall impact.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	PE6_10 Web and information systems, data management systems, information retrieval and digital libraries, data fusion SH5_11 Digital humanities; digital approaches to literary studies and philosophy	Scarpa E.; Valente, R.;
45	Caravale A., Moscati P., Rossi I.	Advancements of the H2IOSC Project: enhancement of digital resources in the Cultural Heritage field targeting archaeology and epigraphy. Introduction to the Special section	UO11 ISPC-MI; UO12-ISPC RM	paper	Scientific	Caravale A., Moscati P., Rossi I. 2024, Advancements of the H2IOSC Project: enhancement of digital resources in the Cultural Heritage field targeting archaeology and epigraphy. Introduction to the Special section, in Caravale C., Moscati P., Rossi I. (eds.), The H2IOSC project and its impact on digital antiquity within the E-RIHS infrastructure – II, «Archeologia e Calcolatori», 35.2, 463-470. https://doi.org/10.19282/ac.35.2.2024.48	Introduction to the second Special section The H2IOSC project and its impact on digital antiquity within the E-RIHS infrastructure	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH6_6 Digital, computational, virtual and geospatial archaeologies	
46	Rossi I., Salvador C.	An observatory of epigraphic resources on the web: the Open Digital Epigraphy Hub	UO11 ISPC-MI	paper	Scientific	Rossi I., Salvador C. 2024, An observatory of epigraphic resources on the web: the Open Digital Epigraphy Hub, in Caravale C., Moscati P., Rossi I. (eds.), The H2IOSC project and its impact on digital antiquity within the E-RIHS infrastructure – II, «Archeologia e Calcolatori», 35.2, 503-523. https://doi.org/10.19282/ac.35.2.2024.51	The Open Digital Epigraphy Hub (EpiHub) is an open access digital platform developed to streamline accessibility and organization of resources in digital epigraphy. Created within the Humanities and Cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud (H2IOSC), EpiHub addresses the fragmented landscape of digital epigraphic resources, which span disciplines like linguistics, philology, and archaeology. Offering a comprehensive catalogue of national and international resources – such as datasets, digital tools, geographical and chronological gazetteers, dictionaries, and text-processing software – EpiHub structures these assets through descriptive metadata to facilitate discoverability and usability for researchers and practitioners across diverse cultural and temporal scopes. The platform's flexible back-end architecture supports efficient data management and real-time updates to enhance front-end accessibility, organizing resources by thematic collections and allowing advanced searches based on specific epigraphic needs, such as language, geographic region, or historical period. Emphasizing FAIR principles, EpiHub standardizes metadata and controlled vocabularies to foster broader interoperability and data reuse across research projects. Integrated with related H2IOSC resources, including H-SetIS and DHeLO, EpiHub aims to become a central resource, continuously enriched to support collaboration and innovation within the digital epigraphy community.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; digital approaches to literary studies and philosophy	Chiara Salvador
47	Boschetti, F., Rigobianco L., Quochi, V.	Domain-Specific Languages for Epigraphy: the Case of ItAnt	UO 08 ILC	paper in volume	Scientific	Boschetti, F., Rigobianco L., Quochi, V. 2023. "Domain-Specific Languages for Epigraphy: the Case of ItAnt". Krister Linden, Thalassia Kontino and Jyrki Niemi (eds.), Selected papers of the CLARIN Annual Conference 2023. Linköping Electronic Conference Proceedings 210, pp. 191-202.	This contribution illustrates how the definition of a Domain-Specific Language can support the activities of epigraphists and historical linguists. It presents and discusses a method and technological solution, based on Domain-Specific Languages, for facilitating scholars in digitally representing the available knowledge of archaic languages and cultures. This is achieved by increasing the human readability of the encoded data without sacrificing compliance with standard models and formats. The work is framed within the context of an Italian National collaborative research project devoted to the study of the languages and cultures of ancient Italy. The platform developed within this project offers an interesting use case and motivation for experimenting with Domain-Specific Languages for the creation of necessary digital critical editions of the inscriptions relevant for these languages. After explaining the definition process of the DSL grammar, we finally test the applicability of the DSL grammar to five example inscriptions in the Faliscan language.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH5_11 Digital humanities; digital approaches to literary studies and philosophy	

48	Diego Quintero Balbas, Luca Pezzati, Barbara Cattaneo, Valentina Righetti and Jana Striava	3D scanning of daguerreotypes	UO15 INO-FI	paper in rivista	Scientific	Diego Quintero Balbas et al 2024 J. Phys. Photonics 6 035001. DOI 10.1088/2515-7647/ad41ab	Daguerreotypes are historical photographic images made on mirror-like metallic plates. These are heritage objects whose shape cannot be measured with invasive techniques, like contact probes, but the high reflectivity of their surfaces makes the use of non-invasive, 3D-measuring optical techniques challenging. Moreover, the dark areas resulting from their degradation produce a very high contrast, which adds extra difficulties to their measurement. In the last few years, several strategies have been developed to overcome the limitations of optical techniques when measuring reflective metallic surfaces. Many of these solutions are not applicable to the study of cultural heritage artifacts, as they are invasive. We attempted the use of conoscopic holography in a 3D-scanning system using a double exposure strategy. This is a promising option for 3D measuring of daguerreotypes, as we experimentally demonstrated in this work. We present the results obtained from the analyses of two 19th-century daguerreotypes with different superficial conditions. The double-exposure allowed us to obtain high-quality data from the entire object surface. This enabled the measurement of micro-scale details related to the manufacturing process and/or to the corrosion deposits. The proposed methodology can be exploited to monitor the overall health of highly reflective metallic objects but also the outcomes of some conservation treatments, such as cleaning.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE6, 11 Machine learning statistical data processing and applications using signal processing; PE4, 2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Diego Iván Quintero Balbás		
49	Diego Quintero Balbas, Laura Maestro-Guijarro, Paula María Carmona-Quiroga, Mohamed Oujja, Marta Castillejo, Francesca Bettini, Simone Porcinai and Jana Striava	Non-invasive stratigraphic analyzes of gelatine-based modern painting materials with linear and nonlinear optical methods	UO15 INO-FI	paper in rivista	Scientific	Diego Quintero Balbas et al 2024 J. Phys. Photonics 6 035018. DOI 10.1088/2515-7647/ad5772	Stratigraphic analyzes of polychrome surfaces, such as paintings, often need samples to offer consistent results regarding the sequence and composition of the layers. Non-invasive methodologies based on linear and nonlinear optical techniques limit material removal from the objects. Recently, optical coherence tomography (OCT) has become the preferred choice of heritage scientists because it is a safe and fast alternative for studying transparent or semi-transparent layers. Yet, nonlinear optical microscopy (NLOM) technique in its modality of multiphoton excitation fluorescence (MPEF) has emerged as a promising tool for the same purpose. Here, we explored linear (OCT and confocal Raman microspectroscopy (CRM)) and nonlinear (NLOM-MPEF) optical methods' capability to investigate gelatine-based layers in mock-up samples and a painting dated 1939 by an artist from the Surrealistic entourage. The optical behavior of mock-up samples that imitate the painting stratigraphy and of six painting fragments detached from the support was also investigated with fiber optics' reflectance spectroscopy and laser induced fluorescence (LIF). Thickness values from the mock-ups obtained with OCT, CRM, and MPEF have provided evidence of the complementarity, from a millimetric to a micrometric scale, and the limitations (e.g. strong fluorescence emission in CRM) of the methods. Moreover, the presence of gelatine was ascertained by LIF spectroscopy applied to the painting fragments and NLOM-MPEF confirmed its suitability as a non-invasive technique for investigating gelatine-based stratigraphic systems.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4, 2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques; SH8, 4 Museums, exhibitions, conservation and restoration	Diego Iván Quintero Balbás		
50	Silvia Innocenti, et al. Minerals 2024, 14(6), 557; https://doi.org/10.3390/min14060557	Historical Pigments and Paint Layers: Raman Spectral Library with 852 nm Excitation Laser	UO15 INO-FI	paper in rivista	Scientific	Silvia Innocenti, et al. Minerals 2024, 14(6), 557; https://doi.org/10.3390/min14060557	Raman spectroscopy (RS), for its robust analytical capabilities under constant development, is a powerful method for the identification of various materials, in particular pigments in cultural heritage. Characterization of the artist's palette is of fundamental importance for the correct formulation of restoration intervention as well as for preventive conservation of artworks. Here we examine the number and suitability of a research center, evaluating Raman Spectral Library for Raman spectroscopy.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4, 2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques; SH8, 4 Museums, exhibitions, conservation and restoration	Diego Iván Quintero Balbás		Silvia Innocenti
51	Benassi, L., Manconi, S., & Quintero Balbas, D. I. (2024). E-RHS CoS Guidelines for Service Managers. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14500623	E-RHS CoS Guidelines for Service Managers	UO15 INO-FI	deliverable	Outreach	Benassi, L., Manconi, S., & Quintero Balbas, D. I. (2024). E-RHS CoS Guidelines for Service Managers. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14500623	Guidelines for Service managers for compiling a Service (Organisation, Tool, Method, and Service) in the new E-RHS catalog of services.		SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE6, 10 Web and information systems, data management systems, information retrieval and digital libraries, data fusion	Diego Iván Quintero Balbás		
52	Benassi, L., Quintero Balbas, D. I., Buti, D., Doherty, B., Manconi, S., STRIOVA, J., Baroncini, L., & Giacomini, D. (2024). E-RHS IP DS.4 E-RHS ERIC Catalogue of Services. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14512437	E-RHS IP DS.4 E-RHS ERIC Catalogue of Services	UO15 INO-FI	deliverable	Scientific	Benassi, L., Quintero Balbas, D. I., Buti, D., Doherty, B., Manconi, S., STRIOVA, J., Baroncini, L., & Giacomini, D. (2024). E-RHS IP DS.4 E-RHS ERIC Catalogue of Services. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14512437	The E-RHS Catalogue of Services (CoS), available at https://catalogue.e-rhs.eu/, offers a simplified, interoperable, and FAIR-aligned platform for accessing and managing E-RHS services. Building on earlier E-RHS-related efforts within EU projects, the current version represents an advancement of the previous experiences, integrating innovative features aligned with the latest interoperability standards and enhanced user experience.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE6, 10 Web and information systems, data management systems, information retrieval and digital libraries, data fusion	Diego Iván Quintero Balbás		
53	Dal Fovo, Alice, Riccardo Cicchi, Claudia Gagliardi, Enrico Baria, Marco Fioravanti, and Raffaella Fontana.	Detecting Early Degradation of Wood Ultrastructure with Nonlinear Optical Imaging and Fluorescence Lifetime Analysis	UO15 INO-FI	paper in rivista	Scientific	Polymers 2024, 16(24), 3590; https://doi.org/10.3390/polym16243590	Understanding the deterioration processes in wooden artefacts is essential for accurately assessing their conservation status and developing effective preservation strategies. Advanced imaging techniques are currently being explored to study the impact of chemical changes on the structural and mechanical properties of wood. Nonlinear optical modalities, including second harmonic generation (SHG) and two-photon excited fluorescence (TPEF), combined with fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM), offer a promising non-destructive diagnostic method for evaluating lignocellulose-based materials. In this study, we employed a nonlinear multimodal approach to examine the effects of artificially induced delignification on samples of Norway spruce (Picea abies) and European beech (Fagus sylvatica) subjected to increasing treatment durations. The integration of SHG/TPEF imaging and multi-component fluorescence lifetime analysis enabled the detection of localized variations in nonlinear signals and τ-phase of key biopolymers within wood cell walls. This methodology provides a powerful tool for early detection of wood deterioration, facilitating proactive conservation efforts of wooden artefacts.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE6, 11 Machine learning statistical data processing and applications using signal processing; PE4, 2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques; PE3, 16 Physics of biological systems	Alice Dal Fovo		
54	A. Dal Fovo, C. Gagliardi, M. Fioravanti, R. Cicchi, R. Fontana	Characterization of degradation effects on wood ultrastructure by non-linear imaging	UO15 INO-FI	conference proceedings	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/202430814003	The characterization of deterioration processes in wooden artifacts is crucial for assessing their state of conservation and ensuring their preservation. Advanced imaging techniques are currently being explored to study the effect of chemical changes on the structural and mechanical properties of wood. Combined second harmonic generation and two-photon excited fluorescence (SHG/TPEF) imaging is a recently introduced non-destructive method for the analysis of cellulose-based samples. The study of aged wood degradation based on nonlinear signal variation is a promising avenue. This work involves nonlinear multimodal analysis of naturally aged and dendrochronologically dated spruce samples. SHG/TPEF imaging and fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM) were used to	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE6, 11 Machine learning statistical data processing and applications using signal processing; PE4, 2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques; PE3, 16 Physics of biological systems	Alice Dal Fovo		
55	A. Dal Fovo, M. Morello, A. Mazzinghi, C. Toso, E. Pampaloni, R. Fontana	Disclosure of a concealed Michelangelo-inspired depiction in a 16th-century painting	UO15 INO-FI	paper in rivista	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.3390/ijimaging10080175	Some paintings may have hidden depictions beneath the visible surface, which can provide valuable insights into the artist's creative process and the genesis of the artwork. Studies have shown that these covered paintings can be revealed through image-based techniques and integrated data processing. This study analyzes an oil painting by Becceri from the mid-16th century depicting the Holy Family, owned by the Uffizi Galleries. During the analysis of the materials, we discovered evidence of pictorial layers beneath the visible scene. To uncover the hidden figure, we applied a multimodal approach that included microprofilometry, reflectance imaging spectroscopy, macro X-ray fluorescence, and optical coherence tomography. We analyzed the brushstrokes of the hidden figures, identified the underdrawing, located the painted areas beneath the overpainted surface, and	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; SH8, 3 Cultural studies and theory, cultural identities and memories, cultural heritage; SH8, 4 Museums, exhibitions, conservation and restoration; PE6, 11 Machine learning statistical data processing and applications using signal processing; PE4, 2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Alice Dal Fovo		
56	I. Lunghi, E. Vannini, A. Dal Fovo, V. Di Sarno, A. Rocco, R. Fontana	A Performance Comparison of 3D Survey Instruments for Their Application in the Cultural Heritage Field	UO15 INO-FI	paper in rivista	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.3390/s24123876	3D modelling provides useful insights in several sectors (from industrial metrology to cultural heritage). Moreover, the 3D reconstruction of objects of artistic interest is becoming mandatory, not only because of the risks to which works of art are increasingly exposed (e.g., wars and climatic disasters) but also because of the leading role that the virtual fruition of art is taking. In this work, we compared the performance of four 3D instruments based on different working principles and techniques (laser micro-profilometry, structured-light topography and the phase-shifting method) by measuring four samples of different sizes, dimensions and surface characteristics. We aimed to assess the capabilities and limitations of these instruments to verify their accuracy and the technical	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; SH8, 3 Cultural studies and theory, cultural identities and memories, cultural heritage; SH8, 4 Museums, exhibitions, conservation and restoration; PE6, 11 Machine learning statistical data processing and applications using signal processing; PE4, 2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Alice Dal Fovo		
57	A. Dal Fovo, M. Morello, A. Mazzinghi, C. Toso, M. Galeotti and R. Fontana	Spectral mapping techniques for the stratigraphic and compositional characterization of a 16th century painting	UO15 INO-FI	paper in rivista	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.3390/heritage7030063	Identifying a painting's pigment palette is crucial for comprehending the author's technique, as well as for evaluating the degradation of the materials. This paper investigates the stratigraphy and pigments distribution of a 16th-century painting from the Uffizi Galleries collection. Firstly, we obtained compositional information through the cross-sectional analysis of samples using scanning electron microscopy. Secondly, we performed elemental mapping using macro-X-ray fluorescence followed by reflectance imaging spectroscopy. The painting image cube was analysed using the spectral correlation mapping (SCM) classification algorithm to accurately identify the distribution and composition of the pigment mixtures.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; SH8, 3 Cultural studies and theory, cultural identities and memories, cultural heritage; SH8, 4 Museums, exhibitions, conservation and restoration; PE6, 11 Machine learning statistical data processing and applications using signal processing; PE4, 2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Alice Dal Fovo		
58	A. Dal Fovo, L. Seplacchi, S. Innocenti, J. Striava, R. Fontana	Botticelli-style tempera portrait on tile: imaging and specific on-site spectroscopic analysis and cleaning examination	UO15 INO-FI	paper in rivista	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2023.11.023	In this work, a tempera painting of uncertain attribution from the Uffizi Galleries was studied. The painting, which portrays a man with apparently Botticellian features, was probably created by one of the most skilled forgers of the early 20th century, Umberto Giunti. He used a flat tile as a support, covered with preparatory layers emulating a wall painting. To shed light on the authorship of the painting, it was crucial to investigate its composing materials, as well as the execution technique and the state of conservation. To this end, non-invasive spectroscopic and imaging optical techniques were applied. Specifically, VIS-NIR multispectral reflectography was used to reveal the presence of possible preparatory drawings, pentimenti and overpaintings. Raman and Fibre Optics Reflectance	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; SH8, 3 Cultural studies and theory, cultural identities and memories, cultural heritage; SH8, 4 Museums, exhibitions, conservation and restoration; PE6, 11 Machine learning statistical data processing and applications using signal processing; PE4, 2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Alice Dal Fovo		Silvia Innocenti
59	V. Di Sarno, S. Zappia, E. Vannini, A. Dal Fovo, A. Rocco, P. Maddaloni, R. Fontana and I. Catapano	The Time-Domain transmission and reflection imaging for art material analysis: preliminary results @E-RHS.it	UO15 INO-FI	conference presentation	Scientific	MetroArcheo 2024 (2024 International Conference on Metrology for Archaeology and Cultural Heritage), 7-9 Oct. 2024	Non-destructive and non-contact methodologies have a significant role in cultural heritage studies given the uniqueness and inestimable value of works of art. Techniques that are able to reveal details not visible to the naked eye are beneficial for the study of the original project followed by the artist. Among these, THz time-domain spectrometers are worth considering thanks to their capability of performing high-resolution imaging with good penetration depth in most paint materials. Accordingly, in the framework of the SHINE project, both the NCLAB and FTLAB platforms of the Italian Node of the European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RHS-It) have been equipped with this cutting-edge equipment. This contribution provides a brief overview of the available systems and presents preliminary results obtained on ad-hoc prepared specimens and achieved using specifically designed data processing approaches. Specifically, transmission imaging results on painted canvas samples with hidden drawings and time of flight reflection imaging results on wood samples covered by different material layers are presented. These latter results provide insight into the samples allowing the detection of the material layers up to the wooden support.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; SH8, 3 Cultural studies and theory, cultural identities and memories, cultural heritage; SH8, 4 Museums, exhibitions, conservation and restoration; PE6, 11 Machine learning statistical data processing and applications using signal processing; PE4, 2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Alice Dal Fovo		
60	E. Vannini, I. Lunghi, A. Dal Fovo, V. Di Sarno, A. Rocco, R. Fontana	A performance comparison of 3D survey instruments for their application in the cultural heritage field	UO15 INO-FI	book of abstracts	Scientific	https://zenodo.org/records/14215786	In this work, we compared the performance of four 3D instruments based on different working principles by measuring four samples representative of artworks. We verified the accuracy and technical specifications in the suppliers' datasheets by computing the point density and evaluating both the lateral and axial resolution. The comparison between the nominal and calculated values from measuring the former samples was used to predict the performance of the instruments in real-case scenarios.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; SH8, 3 Cultural studies and theory, cultural identities and memories, cultural heritage; SH8, 4 Museums, exhibitions, conservation and restoration; PE6, 11 Machine learning statistical data processing and applications using signal processing; PE4, 2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Alice Dal Fovo		

61	I. Lunghi, A. Dal Fovo, E. Vannini, S. Innocenti, I. Striava, R. Fontana	Women studying women: non-invasive and non-contact optical analysis on the painting Allegory of Inclination by Artemisia Gentileschi	UO15 INO-FI	book of abstracts	Scientific	https://zenodo.org/records/14215766	In this work, we present the results of the non-invasive and non-contact optical analysis on the painting Allegory of Inclination by Artemisia Gentileschi, one of the most famous female painters of all time. The analysis, carried out by a female team, allowed to identify the pigments, to document the state of conservation of the painting, to study the artist's technique and to reveal the Allegory's original nudity, which was later covered by a drape painted by Volterrano due to its perceived immorality.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; SH8_3 Cultural studies and theory, cultural identities and memories, cultural heritage; SH8_4 Museums, exhibitions, conservation and restoration; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Alice Dal Fovo	Silvia Innocenti
62	A.Chaban, A. Rocco, V. Di Sarno, R. Fontana, J.Striava	New Frontiers in Wall Paintings Diagnostics with Non-Invasive Techniques	UO15 INO-FI	book of abstracts	Scientific	https://zenodo.org/records/14215766	This contribution presents new achievements and challenges in on-site wall painting diagnostic procedures. Using holographic interferometry, infrared thermography, THz imaging, and other methods, our approach goes far beyond the only defect detection, enabling in-depth subsurface analysis and uncovering future risks. We illustrate the contribution of these techniques to current conservation campaigns on renowned wall paintings in Florence, supporting our research by laboratory simulation studies	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8 - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; SH8_3 Cultural studies and theory, cultural identities and memories, cultural heritage; SH8_4 Museums, exhibitions, conservation and restoration; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Antonina Chaban	
63	M. Massidda, A. Bordignon, F. Fabbri, R. Nori, L. Piccardi, L. Travaglini, M. Veggi, S. Pescarini	Towards an Experiment Planner for Cognitive Studies in Virtual Heritage Environments. A Pilot Study.	UO 04 ISPC - FI	conference proceedings	Scientific	https://diglib.eg.org/items/6058f5fd-f02c-4bf9-8891-0ea40700a99f	The increasing role of Virtual Reality in psychology introduces new methods for replicable experiments and enhances techniques for analysing human behaviours. Despite the technological advancements, a flexible and user-friendly approach for researchers and psychologists is still lacking, making it challenging to meet their specific needs and requirements. This paper describes the design, development and testing of a prototype for configuring and managing experiments in virtual sessions in cultural 3D spaces. The prototype represents the first version of a future tool dedicated to the planning of assessment sessions in Virtual Heritage environments. To test this prototype we have used the Digital Twin of a physical Exhibition dedicated to Aldrovandi.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8_9: Digital approaches to anthropology, cultural studies and art	M. Massida	M. Veggi
64	M. Veggi, I. Cerato	Stratigraphic Units beyond Archaeological Contexts. A Proposal to Enhance Knowledge Management of Heterogeneous Data of Cultural Heritage Sites	UO 04 ISPC - FI	conference proceedings	Scientific	https://diglib.eg.org/items/a7265440-9482-4174-b97e-1d49ced06814	This paper introduces BranCO, an ontology tailored for the integration and reconstruction of heterogeneous cultural data, illustrated through the Brancacci Chapel in Florence. Central to this model is the concept of the "interpretative unit," which broadens the application of stratigraphic units (SU) beyond traditional archaeological use. The initial sections provide an overview of existing research, among which the Extended Matrix, and analyses the implementation of SU within semantic models for cultural heritage, as in the CIDOC-CRM standard and its extensions such as CRM-archaeo. On this basis, the paper outlines the main components of the ontology, developed following the SAMOD methodology. The satisfaction of both formal and rhetorical requirements highlights the potential for advancing this research, particularly to later integrate linked data with semantic nodes in 3D models.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8_9: Digital approaches to anthropology, cultural studies and art		M. Veggi
65	M. Veggi, I. Cerato	The Brancacci Chapel from the Quattrocento to the Semantic Web: An Ontology-Assisted Case Study of Cultural Data Management and Site Reconstruction	UO 04 ISPC - FI	paper in rivista	Scientific	Under peer review - DAACH Elsevier	This study proposes an ontological model for cultural heterogeneous data and cultural site reconstructions. It is based on the concept of interpretative unit, which extends the semantics of stratigraphic units also to non-archaeological contexts. The ontology is named after the case study of this research, the Brancacci Chapel in Florence. Indeed, after a state of the art overview of the development methodology and the description of the most relevant entities, a first test case is proposed. An entry of the catalogue of a recent exhibition on Masolino, a 15th century painter who worked at the decoration of the chapel, has been serialised as Turtle file and the semantics of knowledge graph has been assessed via competency questions. The positive results encourage the deepening of this line of research in the direction of connecting linked data with nodes in 3D models, as well as their visualisation and communication to non-specialist audiences.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8_9: Digital approaches to anthropology, cultural studies and art		M. Veggi
66	M. Veggi	State of the Art on Artificial Intelligence Resources for Interaction Media Design in Digital Cultural Heritage	UO 04 ISPC - FI	paper in rivista	Scientific	Under peer review - JOCCM ACM	This paper explores the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the design of interactive experiences for Cultural Heritage (CH). Previous studies indeed either miss to represent the specificity of the CH or mention possible tools without making a clear reference to a structured Interaction Design (iD) workflow. The study also attempts to overcome one of the major limitations of traditional literature review, which may fail to capture proprietary tools whose release is rarely accompanied by	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8_9: Digital approaches to anthropology, cultural studies and art		M. Veggi
67	E. Degl'Innocenti, L. Canova, F. Coradeschi, C. Di Meo, M. Sanesi, A. Spadi e F. Spinelli.	"Linking Tangible to Intangible: a Sustainable Workflow for Cultural Heritage and Humanities Data Integration" in "DARIAH Annual Event 2023: Cultural Heritage Data as Humanities Research Data, Budapest, Hungary, June 6-9 2023"	UO01 OVI-FI	poster	Scientific	https://zenodo.org/records/7985353	The aim of this poster is to present the work carried out by the DARIAH-IT team at CNR-OVI (Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche - Opera del Vocabolario Italiano) within the context of several national and international projects such as the SSHOC thematic cluster, the IPERION-HS H2020 project and the Italian Roadmap for the development of the DARIAH national node. The paper will focus on issues related to the collection, analysis and digital processing of resources and collections provided by memory and cultural institutions (GLAMs) and Research Organisations. In particular, we will present and discuss the most relevant findings and experiences and present a sustainable workflow for ingesting, mapping, modelling and visualising data collections from the aforementioned research domains. Particular relevance is given to the RESTORE infrastructure and its scalability towards the Italian (i.e.: H2IOSC National Recovery and Resilience Plan) and European contexts (i.e.: EGI-ACE) within the DARIAH framework.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere - PE6_10 Web and information systems, data management systems, information retrieval and digital libraries, data fusion;	F. Coradeschi, A. Spadi e F. Spinelli.	
68	Emiliano Degl'Innocenti, Alessia Spadi, Federica Spinelli, Lucia Francalanci, Michela Perino, Irene Falini, Francesco Coradeschi, Francesco Pinna	"Strumenti digitali per la trascrizione e la lemmatizzazione di testi in italiano antico" in "Me.Te. Digitali. Mediterraneo in rete tra testi e contesti, Proceedings del XIII Convegno Annuale AIUCD2024. A cura di: Di Silvestro, Antonio ; Spampinato, Daria (2024) Catania: AIUCD, p. 595. ISBN 978-88-942535-8-0. DOI 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/7927. In: Quaderni di Umanistica Digitale	UO01 OVI-FI	conference proceedings	Scientific	https://amsacta.unibo.it/id/eprint/7927	The contribution focuses on the development and use of methodologies to support and enhance research in the context of the humanities and cultural heritage, with particular reference to the field of digital philology. Starting from the case study of the Datini Fund of the Prato State Archives, the aim is the development of new digital tools, as well as the integration and enhancement of existing tools, aimed at the study of the private and commercial correspondence of the Prato merchant Francesco di Marco Datini.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere - SH5_4 Philology; text and image studies - PE6_10 Web and information systems, data management systems, information retrieval and digital libraries, data fusion	Alessia Spadi, Federica Spinelli, Lucia Francalanci, Michela Perino, Irene Falini, Francesco Coradeschi, Francesco Pinna	
69	Emiliano Degl'Innocenti, Alessia Spadi, Federica Spinelli, Lucia Francalanci, Michela Perino, Irene Falini, Francesco Coradeschi, Francesco Pinna	"Supporting digitally enhanced scientific workflows in a clustered Infrastructure: H2IOSC." In "Workflows: Digital Methods for Reproducible Research Practices in the Arts and Humanities" DARIAH Annual Event 2024, Lisbon, Portugal, June 19 to June 21, 2024.	UO01 OVI-FI	poster	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12073491	H2IOSC (Humanities and Cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud) is a project funded by the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) in Italy, aiming to create a federated cluster comprising the Italian branches of four European research infrastructures (RIs) - CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RHS, OPERAS - operating in the "Social and Cultural Innovation" sector of ESFR1 (European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures). The role of DARIAH-IT in the project is to build the distributed infrastructure and federate its 8 nodes, elaborate the semantic framework to represent the knowledge gathered in H2IOSC in an interconnected way and develop the Scientific Pilots supporting the digital philology workflow.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 - Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere - PE6_10 Web and information systems, data management systems, information retrieval and digital libraries, data fusion	Alessia Spadi, Federica Spinelli, Lucia Francalanci, Michela Perino, Irene Falini, Francesco Coradeschi, Francesco Pinna	
70	Emiliano Degl'Innocenti, Leonardo Canova, Francesco Coradeschi, Federica Spinelli	"Preservare il Tesoro. Per un nuovo sistema di interrogazione del corpora dell'Opera del Vocabolario Italiano." In "La Memoria Digitale. Forme Del Testo e Organizzazione Della Conoscenza." Atti Del XII Convegno Annuale AIUCD, 358-365.	UO01 OVI-FI	conference proceedings	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.6092/unibo/amsacta/7721	This article intends to present the project for a new system for querying the textual corpora of the Opera del Vocabolario Italiano, born from the collaboration between the Institute and the Italian node of the European research infrastructure DARIAH and aimed at providing, with an Open Science approach, a user-friendly, accessible and sustainable access platform to the corpora, which represent to date the textual basis on which the concept of "ancient Italian" is defined. A necessary introduction concerning the GATTO software, which has been the basis of all lexicographic operations carried out within the Institute for 25 years, is followed by the definition of the purposes and requirements, the conceptualisation of the tool and its relationship with GATTO, and the presentation of the first development phases, relating to the search functions by forms and by lemmas, and the first results. Finally, an essential timeline and an overview of the inclusion of the project in the European Open Science framework through the PON and PNRR projects of which DARIAH is a promoter is offered.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH5_11 Digital humanities computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere - SH5_4 Philology; text and image studies - PE6_10 Web and information systems, data management systems, information retrieval and digital libraries, data fusion	Francesco Coradeschi, Federica Spinelli	
71	Lino Leonardi	Una infrastruttura per le edizioni critiche di testi italiani antichi, in "Ecdotica", 20 (2023), pp. 71-81	UO01 OVI-FI	articolo in rivista	Scientific	https://site.unibo.it/ecdotica/it/numeri-della-rivista/ecdotica-20-2023	Specialists in digital philology have developed theories and research practices that are not always effective in meeting the demands of traditional textual criticism. This article proposes a scenario in which this mainstream model is complemented by a perspective more attentive both to the dynamics of the manuscript tradition and to the goal of the critical edition. The proposal concerns in particular ancient Italian texts, for which a shared procedure of digital treatment could be provided.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH5_4 Philology; text and image studies - SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere		
72	Irene Falini	I rimatori minori del Due e del Trecento visti dall'OVI: il caso di Lorenzo Moschi, in -Di arbasti ed umili meriti- Nuove prospettive filologiche e critiche sulla poesia "minore" del medioevo (XIII-XV secc.). Atti del convegno (Napoli, 25-26 maggio 2023), a cura di Raffaele Cesaro e Selene Maria Vatteroni, Roma, Antenor, pp. 253-275	UO01 OVI-FI	contributo in volume	Scientific	Accepted, in press	A dieci anni dall'avvio delle ricerche su Lorenzo Moschi, il contributo intende riassumere le nuove acquisizioni sulla sua biografia e sulla sua produzione poetica, mostrandone le ripercussioni in vari progetti che producono contenuti digitali nell'ambito della filologia della letteratura italiana dei primi secoli e della lessicografia dell'italiano antico.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH5_4 Philology; text and image studies	Irene Falini	
73	Lucia Francalanci, Francesco Coradeschi	"La lemmatizzazione semiautomatica dell'italiano antico" in "Boletino dell'Opera del Vocabolario Italiano", 29 (2024), pp.353-390	UO01 OVI-FI	articolo in rivista	Scientific	Accepted, in press	This paper aims to identify techniques and tools that facilitate the lemmatization of texts in early Italian, with a particular focus on the OVI Corpus of early Italian (Corpus OVI dell'italiano antico). While stressing the challenges associated with the unique characteristics of these texts, as well as the issues that arise in adapting existing tools to linguistic varieties for which they were not originally designed, this article outlines the methodological approach employed and presents the preliminary results obtained from the experiments conducted, concluding by discussing potential avenues for future research and development.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH4_9 - Theoretical linguistics; computational linguistics - SH5_11 - Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere - SH5_4 - Philology; text and image studies	Lucia Francalanci, Francesco Coradeschi	

74	Cristina Marras	Multilinear design and modelling for digital scholarly editions in Philosophy/Wielospektowe projektowanie i modelowanie naukowych edycji cyfrowych w filozofii, in Sztuka Edycji/The art of editing. Textological and Editorial Studies, special issue, 2023 (pp.55-62)	IOU1- LIESI	articolo in rivista	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.12775/SE.2023.0006	La riflessione pragmatico-critica sulla digitalizzazione del sapere, le sue pratiche e rappresentazione ha tracciato nuovi percorsi per la ricerca filosofica di oggi. La filosofia si è reinventata e ha iniziato a definirsi come una disciplina capace di utilizzare un ampio inventario concettuale e metodologico per, se non comprendere, almeno descrivere e interpretare una realtà multiforme. L'articolo si concentra su due aspetti. In primo luogo, mostra come il rapporto tra analogico e digitale si traduca nelle attuali pratiche di editing digitale scientifico. In secondo luogo, attraverso alcuni esempi di progetti dedicati soprattutto alle infrastrutture di ricerca, cerca di rispondere alla domanda se le edizioni digitali accademiche per la filosofia, pur mirando in linea di principio agli stessi obiettivi delle edizioni create in altri campi delle scienze umane, ossia fornire (a) rappresentazioni affidabili, attendibili e utili del nostro patrimonio testuale come base per ulteriori ricerche accademiche, abbiano le loro specificità.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH5_11; SH5_10			
75	Salvatore Cristofaro, Pierpaolo Sichera, Vittoria Fabiani, Enrico Pasini, M. Yu	"Infrastrutture di ricerca come strumenti di "interculturalità digitale" co-autori in Me.Te. Digitali. Mediterraneo in rete tra testi e contesti, Proceedings XIII Convegno Annuale AIUCD, A cura di: Di Silvestro Antonio; Spampinato Daria (2024, Catania 28- 30 maggio 2024, Università di Catania)	ILIESI-	articolo in Atti di Convegno	Scientific	https://amsacta.unibo.it/id/eprint/7927/	Il contributo si focalizza su alcune caratteristiche delle infrastrutture di ricerca (IR) per le scienze umane e il patrimonio culturale (SSH) che facilitano la scienza aperta. In particolare, presenta alcune funzioni di un marketplace per le SSH come esempi di messa in relazione e integrazione di strumenti per aggregare, accedere, rappresentare, condividere, riusare e comunicare la conoscenza.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere	Salvatore Cristofaro, Pierpaolo Sichera, Vittoria Fabiani		M. Yu
76	Pietro Sichera, Cristina Marras, Enrico Pasini	Orchestrazione api per workflow applicativi nell'ambito delle digital humanities" progetto H2IOSC, WPS: Marketplace	ILIESI-	Report tecnico-scientifico	Scientific	https://zenodo.org/records/14187534	In this paper we focus specifically on API orchestration for application workflows. The need for a detailed presentation of this element stems from the presence in the H2IOSC Marketplace technical terms of contract ("capitolato") of the ability to create "Level 2" services as aggregations that are not purely descriptive. Within these aggregations, the Marketplace must then be able to orchestrate for the user, from a dedicated space, the remote execution of individual "Level 1" services, without either processing or passing data between services committing Marketplace resources.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	PE6_10 Web and information systems, data management systems, information retrieval and digital libraries, data fusion	Pietro Sichera		
77	Sichera, Pietro; Cristofaro, Salvatore; Spampinato, Daria; Mazzagufu, Laura; DEL GROSSO, ANGELO MARIO	CHROMA model for H2IOSC	ILIESI - OU08-ILC-PI - ISTD	poster	Scientific	https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13913607	The CHROMA model (http://serverchroma.cnr.it/) offers an integrated approach rooted in projects like "Bellini Digital Correspondence" and "Pirandello Nazionale". It treats text as a complex multidimensional object through an editorial process	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere	Sichera, Pietro; Cristofaro, Salvatore;	Mazzagufu, Laura	
78	Menconero, S., Fanini, B., Pietroni, E.	The e-Archeo 3D Project, an Innovative and Sustainable Cultural Proposal Based on XR Technologies	UO12-ISPC RM	contributo in volume	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-62963-1_12	This contribution focuses on e-Archeo 3D: an application that visualises virtual archaeological reconstructions. It is an interactive browser-based application implemented on the open-source ATON platform. This application enables the visualisation of archaeological sites through 360° panoramas that can be explored and populated with multimedia content (audio, pictures, videos, and 3D models). Users can switch between the current archaeological context and the reconstruction hypothesis at each viewpoint while a voice (or text) narrates the main archaeological and historical information. Some parts of the panoramas pulsate with a yellow colour and give access to in-depth multimedia	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8_3 Cultural studies and theory, cultural identities and memories, cultural heritage, architectural heritage; SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere; PE6_9 Human computer interaction and interface, visualisation	Sofia Menconero		
79	Federica Spinelli, Silvia Iachello	H2IOSC Visual Identity	UO01 OVI-FI - UO9 ISPC-CT	Guidelines	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14646251	The "Visual Identity GUIDELINE" provides guidelines for the use of the H2IOSC project's visual identity, including logos and branded materials.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 - Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere; SH3_10 - Communication and information, networks, media	Federica Spinelli, Silvia Iachello		
80	Federica Spinelli, Silvia Iachello, Irene Falini, Silvestro Caligiuri, Daniele Carpià	H2IOSC Project Handbook	UO01 OVI-FI - UO9 ISPC-CT - UO 08 ILC - ILIESI	Handbook / Report	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12918010	The "H2IOSC Handbook" aims to provide an overview of the H2IOSC Project's state of the art and to introduce people who make it possible, not only to the H2IOSC community but also to a wider audience.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 - Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere;	Federica Spinelli, Silvia Iachello, Irene Falini		
81	Alberto Bucciero, Francesco Valentino Taurino	Conservation and Monitoring Cultural Assets through a Wireless Sensor Network IoT Platform	OU10 - ISPC-LE	articolo in Atti di Convegno	Scientific	ISBN: 978-960-598-623-0	a multi-sensor IoT platform to support the remote monitoring and the protection of Cultural Heritage assets through the integration of multiple data feeds gathering information from a large-scale Wireless Sensor Network drawn within the scope of the National PNNR project H2IOSC (Humanities and Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud).	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8_10 Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage PE6_6 Informatics and information systems PE7_5 Systems engineering, sensorics, actorics, automation PE10_15 Earth observations from space/remote sensing	Francesco Valentino Taurino		
82	Mohamed Emara, Riccardo Colella, Alberto Bucciero, Luca Catarinucci, Giuseppe Grassi	NFC-powered flexible strain gauge data logger for monitoring cracks in built cultural heritage	OU10 - ISPC-LE	articolo in Atti di Convegno	Scientific	DOI: 10.1109/IFETC61155.2024.10771886	Surface and structural cracks are among the most common problems that face structures and buildings. The problem is multiplied in the case of buildings in built cultural heritage due to the delicacy of working in historically and culturally valued environments. In this work, we report on circuit modelling and the design of a novel crack detection and monitoring system using NFC technology for built cultural heritage preservation. The system revolves around a flexible strain gauge sensor that can be bonded to the surface of the structure under consideration. The applied tension and compression are transferred to the surface of the strain gauge through the bond line between the surface of the considered structure and the strain gauge. The captured data are conditioned, processed, and wirelessly transferred to the reader through an NFC tag. The system is wirelessly powered by a radio frequency energy harvesting circuit, which guarantees extended working operations and eliminates the need for attaching batteries with corrosive substances to the walls of culturally valued structures. The captured data by the sensing circuit can be accessed by NFC-enabled smartphones, tablets and notebooks, which makes the system suitable for IoT applications.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH8_10 Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage PE7_2 Ingegneria elettrica PE7_6 Tecnologie della comunicazione, tecnologie ad alta frequenza PE7_8 Reti (di comunicazione, di sensori, di robot, ecc.)	Mohamed Emara, Riccardo Colella		
83	Mohamed Emara; Riccardo Colella; Alberto Bucciero; Luca Catarinucci; Giuseppe Grassi	Circuit Model of NFC-Powered Systems for Monitoring Cracks in Built Cultural Heritage	OU10 - ISPC-LE	articolo in Atti di Convegno	Scientific	DOI: 10.23919/SpliTech61897.2024.10612545	Cracks occurrence and propagation are among the most common problems that affect building construction safety and longevity. In built cultural heritage, these cracks are especially critical due to the construction's historical, cultural, architectural, and aesthetic value. To preserve the structural integrity and impact for future generations, it is essential to monitor cracks. This work discusses the design and simulation of the circuit model for an affordable and wireless system for monitoring surface cracks in construction. The system uses a waterproof resistive strain gauge that is bonded to the test specimen to monitor cracks. Near-field communication (NFC) technology is used for transmitting data wirelessly and powering through energy harvesting. An NFC reader, such as an NFC-enabled smartphone application, monitors the crack's behaviour by tapping it over the strain gauge sensing circuit. The system benefits from the lightweight and flexibility of the strain gauge, satisfying the necessity of maintaining a high level of delicacy in dealing with culturally valued materials. The strain gauge does not apply strain on the material when bonded with the surface. Moreover, the battery-free feature makes the system more dynamic and durable for monitoring various localised spots. This system is aligned with the precaution of not bringing corrosive materials into the vicinity of culturally valued materials.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH8_10 Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage PE7_2 Ingegneria elettrica PE7_6 Tecnologie della comunicazione, tecnologie ad alta frequenza PE7_8 Reti (di comunicazione, di sensori, di robot, ecc.)	Mohamed Emara, Riccardo Colella		
84	Valeria Minisini, Irene Muci	LINEE GUIDA PER UNA CULTURA OPEN DEL PATRIMONIO DIGITALE ITALIANO	OU10 - ISPC-LE, UO12-ISPC RM	poster	Scientific		Nel medesimo anno della Dichiarazione di Messina, in Italia entra in vigore il Codice dei Beni culturali e del paesaggio (D. Lgs. 42/2004) improntato su una visione tradizionale dei beni definiti all'art. 2, co. 2, "testimonianze aventi valore di civiltà". Principale fonte normativa per il settore, nonostante i diversi aggiornamenti nella sua pagina non hanno ancora trovato spazio la digitalizzazione e la gestione dei dati relativi al patrimonio culturale. Per questo, questa considerevole quantità di materiale ha risentito della trascuratezza di policy non aggiornate e management inadeguati alla sua valorizzazione attraverso l'uso e la condivisione a dispetto della cross-disciplinary research oggi affermata. Affinché il processo di transizione digitale si compia con risultati duraturi, è stata avviata una capillare opera di sensibilizzazione agli imperativi del movimento Open Science verso tutti i professionisti coinvolti, chiamati a essere protagonisti e forza motrice del cambiamento, attraverso l'adozione di linee guida e strategie condivise a livello nazionale.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_5 Archaeological science, bioarchaeology, environmental archaeology, geoarchaeology SH8_8 Ancient history, medieval history	Valeria Minisini, Irene Muci		
85	I. Muci, A. Chirivi, A. Bucciero, M. Greco	RESEARCH DATA EXPLORATION AND DISCOVERY	OU10 - ISPC-LE	articolo in Atti di Convegno	Scientific	ISBN 978-98-95409-28-3	There is a strong need throughout the scientific community for effective tools for analyzing, transforming, and correlating information from different sources. Despite this, in the vast cultural heritage community, heterogeneous information (be it the result of diagnostic investigations or humanistic research) is often managed independently within individual research groups and, over the years, stratified in a series of extremely heterogeneous paper and digital repositories. ReXplora project suggest a new way to effectively support scientists to process, explore and visualize scientific data, proposing a methodological approach to represent the different information classes into which the research data can be classified mapped over the proper visual representation class, according to the specific Italian context and the user profile.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere; PE6_9 Human computer interaction and interface, visualisation	M. Greco		I. Muci
86	Emiliano Degl'Innocenti, Monica Monachini, Alberto Bucciero, Enrico Pasini, Bruno Fanini and Francesca Frontini	H2IOSC: Humanities and Heritage Open Science Cloud	OU10 - ISPC-LE, UO12-ISPC RM	Poster	Scientific	ISBN 978-98-942535-7-3	Questo poster descrive gli obiettivi del progetto H2IOSC, Humanities and Heritage Open Science Cloud, che mira a costruire un cluster federato e inclusivo di IR nel dominio ESFRI dell'innovazione sociale e culturale volto a supportare ai ricercatori nelle varie discipline nei settori delle scienze umane, delle tecnologie linguistiche e dei beni culturali fornendo dati, strumenti e servizi digitali avanzati.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere;			
87	Colautti Veronica, Degl'Innocenti, Palamà Daniela Maria, Massi Benedetti Cristina	D1.1 Quality assurance plan, guidelines, project handbook	OU10 ISPC-LE, UO01 OVI-FI, UO04 ISPC-FI	Project deliverable	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14679949	This deliverable reports the management processes for communication, monitoring, approval of deliverables, administration, ethics, data access policy, IP management, quality plan adopted within the H2IOSC project, including the setting up of guidelines, templates and standards. It also provides the necessary indications to define the overall managerial strategy of how each phase established by the H2IOSC documentation must be made operational, with a dedicated timeframe, during the project implementation. The current text constitutes an updated version of Deliverable D1.1 (previous versions published in Bimesters I and VI) in which the relevant activities launched in order to ensure the proper and timely implementation of H2IOSC activities were described. The document must be read together with other project deliverables referred to in the text in consideration of the overlapping treatment of some topics.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere; IR Gestione di infrastrutture di ricerca, laboratori e impianti, tecnologie digitali per la ricerca	Colautti, Massi Benedetti		

88	Monica Monachini, Valeria Quochi, Paola Moscati, Alessandra Caravale, Alessandra Chirivì, Emiliano Degl'Innocenti, Roberta Bianca Luzietti, Alessia Spadi, Marta Caradonna.	D2.1 First report on the H2IOSC Landscapes	OU10 ISPC-LE, UO01 OVI-FI, UO 08 ILC, UO12-ISPC RM, ILIESI	Project deliverable	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14680020	The Humanities and Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud (H2IOSC) project involves four Italian nodes of research infrastructures (RIs) - CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RHS, and OPERAS. Within this project, the second work package focuses on establishing, mapping, and monitoring strategies for assessing the national and international operation contexts for the four RIs, the characteristics of their user communities, and the specific data resources, services, and tools that are most needed, used and newly created. The main objective of this work package is to conduct a comprehensive survey of the landscape of language technologies, humanities, and heritage science in Italy. This survey takes into account existing projects, resources, tools, communities, best practices, and standards that need to be integrated into the national Marketplace as well as the repositories of the four RIs. Collaboration within the work package was directed at structuring shared procedures for developing, managing, and adapting the survey's main objectives. Priority was on identifying and engaging key stakeholders within various communities. The surveying activity was organized around a set of shared activities, in parallel with others conducted by each infrastructure. The initial coordination activity focused on defining dimensions and criteria to guide the survey. It resulted in the creation of a structured questionnaire, which was designed to gather information about user needs, engage with stakeholders, identify communities of reference, evaluate relevant projects, and assess the FAIRness of data. The questionnaire was employed to gather insights on a wide range of topics, including data resources, software, tools, projects, training needs, prior knowledge of RIs, publications, and feedback. Such a questionnaire has been distributed among the relevant disciplinary communities and sub-communities of the four RIs. Respondents included students, researchers, professors, and subject matter experts in social science, digital humanities, and cultural heritage research fields. Preliminary results from the control group gave insights into the challenges and opportunities of the survey. Respondents have shared valuable information about data resources, technologies, software, and their training needs. The results highlight the need for clearer communication, dissemination activities, and better engagement strategies to encourage participation from the wider community. Addressing the lack of awareness regarding FAIR principles and fostering collaboration with researchers will be crucial moving forward. Future activities will involve data analysis, conducting interviews based on survey responses, and exploring strategies for integrating technology and software resources into the H2IOSC marketplace.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere;	Roberta Bianca Luzietti, Alessia Spadi		
89	Degl'Innocenti Emiliano, Spadi Alessia, Coradeschi Francesco	D4.13 Common semantic framework (interim)	UO01 OVI-FI	Project deliverable	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14680083	WP4 is focused on developing interoperability between available resources both at a physical level, creating the H2IOSC National Cloud Infrastructure and at a semantic level, by translating the state of knowledge with respect to the resources offered by each RI into a common semantic interdisciplinary and interoperable representation (i.e.: the H2IOSC reference ontology). WP4 will focus on the alignment (i.e.: collection, cleaning, mapping, and modeling) of resources gathered by the 4 participating RIs. To facilitate the alignment, a common mapping schema will be deployed to support the data transformation process: from the original format(s) towards the H2IOSC reference ontology. The actual H2IOSC-RO (Reference Ontology) development is meant to create a level of interoperability between resources gathered by RIs, by providing a shared Conceptual Reference Model to represent information coming from heterogeneous sources using a common vision. The development workflow involves: i) analyzing the state of the art and focusing on common problems related to the management of information provided by the RIs; ii) providing a pipeline of validated actions and guidelines on the assessment and semantization of data; iii) offering practical methods for heterogeneous data integration, including transformation and validation, fostering resources exploitation and reuse.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere;	Spadi Alessia, Coradeschi Francesco		
90	Marta Caradonna, Nicola Giampietro, Lisa Reggiani	D7.1 Report on shared and unique challenges for the H2IOSC research communities	ILIESI	Project deliverable	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14680055	Description The present report (Deliverable 7.1 of the H2IOSC project) presents the results of the first phase of activity in WP7, centered on a landscaping survey of prospective users input. The results of the survey are put in context and a SWOT analysis thereof is provided, in order to identify an essential to-do list. The relation to other activities in the WP is briefly sketched in conclusion.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere;	Nicola Giampietro		
91	Laura Benassi, Federico Boschetti, Leonardo Canova, Antonina Chaban, Emiliano Degl'Innocenti, Carmen Di Meo, Francesca Frontini, Monica Monachini, Roberta Ottaviani, Leonardo Pica Ciamarra, Giulia Pedonese, Pietro Restaneo, Alessia Scognamiglio, Alessia Spadi, Jana Striova	D8.1 Training Strategy	UO01 OVI-FI, UO 08 ILC, ISPF, ILIESI, INO	Project deliverable	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14680109	In this document we describe the state of the art of the four participating infrastructures in terms of training and define the training strategy of the project H2IOSC in terms of overall vision, and along the following 3 lines: - Building the H2IOSC the training infrastructure with a training portal and a depositing service for training materials (technical and functional requirements are described for both) - Creating an offer of common H2IOSC training materials, aimed at facilitating the use of the H2IOSC marketplace and pilots - Strengthening the disciplinary offer for the four participating infrastructures This is a living document, evolving during the life of the project with the natural upgrade of the awareness of the needs expressed by the various groups interested (users already in the community and identified potential users).	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere;	Antonina Chaban, Roberta Ottaviani, Giulia Pedonese, Alessia Spadi		
93	Del Grosso, Angelo Mario; Riccucci, Marina; Mercatanti, Elvira	Voci Dall'Inferno: Dante per Dire Il Lager - Digitalizzare e Studiare Le	UO08 ILC-PI	Proceedings	Scientific	https://amsacta.unibo.it/id/eprint/7927/	Il contributo illustra il progetto di ricerca Voci dall'Inferno. L'iniziativa scientifica ha due obiettivi, integrati e correlati: a) la digitalizzazione e la codifica di un corpus, il più ampio possibile di testimonianze non letterarie di	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere;	Mercatanti Elvira		
94	Del Grosso, Angelo Mario; Romoli, Francesca; Ricci, Letizia; Aiola, Chiara	The MaximHum project: from inventories to the first interface hypothesis	UO08 ILC-PI	Poster	Scientific	https://zenodo.org/records/13927721	Maximus the Greek/Michael Trivolis (Arta 1470ca-Sergiev Posad 1556/1557) was a man of letters and Orthodox monk who was educated in Italy at the school of the humanists and who, after taking vows on Mount Athos, spent the longest part of his life in Moscow, where he became the first important conduit	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere;	Ricci Letizia		
95	Del Grosso, Angelo Mario; Riccucci, Marina; Mercatanti, Elvira	Voci dall'Inferno: The voices of the Lager survivors	UO08 ILC-PI	Poster	Scientific	https://zenodo.org/records/13925918	Voci dall'Inferno is a research project directed by Professor Marina Riccucci (University of Pisa) since 2016, with support from Professor Angelo Mario Del Grosso (CNR-ILC, Pisa) and contributions from numerous Digital Humanities in Nazi concentration camps, approximately 20 million people perished. This included young and old, men and women, Jews, dissidents, and homosexuals. Only 10% of those deported survived. This paper introduces "Voci dall'Inferno" project, which aims to achieve two key objectives: a) Create a comprehensive	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere;	Mercatanti Elvira		
92	Del Grosso, Angelo Mario; Riccucci, Marina; Mercatanti, Elvira	The Impact of Digital Editing on the Study of Holocaust Survivors' Testimonies in the Context of Memory Work	UO08 ILC-PI	Proceedings	Scientific	https://aclanthology.org/2024.htres-1.1/		Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere;	Mercatanti Elvira		
96	Salvatore Cristofaro, Cristina Marras, Pierpaolo Sichea, Vittoria Fabiani, Enrico Pasini, M. Yu	"Interculturalità digitale" co-autori in Me.Te. Digitali. Mediterraneo in rete tra testi e contesti. Proceedings XIII Convegno Annuale AIUCD, A cura di: Di Silvestro Antonio; Spampinato Daria (2024, Catania 28- 30	ILIESI-PI	POSTER	Scientific	10.5281/zenodo.14710222	Il poster presenta le INFRASTRUTTURE DIGITALI intese come Ecosistemi di ricerca per la scienza aperta, descritte OPERAS the European Research Infrastructure for the development of open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities e il caso del Marketplace del progetto H2IOSC come un esempio di strumenti che favoriscono "Interculturalità digitale".	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere	Salvatore Cristofaro, Pierpaolo Sichea, Vittoria Fabiani	M. Yu	
97	Giulia Pedonese, Francesca Frontini, Dario Del Fante, Eleonora Federici	Adapting UPSKILLS Learning Modules to the University Curricula: Best Practices and Lessons Learnt from the H2IOSC Training Experience at the University of Ferrara	UO08 ILC-PI	Proceedings	Scientific	https://www.clarin.eu/sites/default/files/CLARIN_2024_ConferenceProceedings_Final.pdf	This paper details the steps taken to adapt and integrate the training materials developed by CLARIN ERIC in two bachelor's degree courses and one master's degree course at the University of Ferrara. The workflow applies the shared methodology developed within the Humanities and Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud project. It modifies the training materials of the UPSKILLS course "Introduction to Language Data: Standards and Repositories" according to the needs of three target courses focusing on English to Italian	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere;	Giulia Pedonese		

98	Iulianna van der Lek, Darja Fišer, Francesca Frontini, Giulia Pedonese	Introduzione ai Dati Linguistici: Standard e Archivi Digitali	UO08 ILC-PI	Course	Educational	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13911935	Traduzione italiana e adattamento del corso UPSKILLS "Introduction to Language Data: Standards and Repositories". L'adattamento è stato sviluppato secondo quanto stabilito nel Deliverable 8.1 "Training Strategy" nell'ambito dell'Attività 8.2.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere;	Giulia Pedonese								
99	Anas Fahad Khan, Giulia Pedonese, Michele Mallia, Francesca Frontini, Valeria Quochi, Elisa Squadraro	Linguistic Linked Open Data for Humanists	UO08 ILC-PI	Course	Educational	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13897931	Il corso prevede l'illustrazione delle basi del Linguistic Linked Open Data ed è stato sviluppato secondo quanto stabilito nel Deliverable 8.1 "Training Strategy" nell'ambito dell'Attività 8.2.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere;	Giulia Pedonese, Michele Mallia								Elisa Squadraro
100	R. Guarasci, A. Minutolo, G. Buonaiuto, G. De Pietro, M. Esposito	Raising the Bar on Acceptability Judgments Classification: An Experiment on ItaCoLA Using ELECTRA	ICAR	articolo in rivista	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics13132500	The task of automatically evaluating acceptability judgments has relished increasing success in Natural Language Processing, starting from including the Corpus of Linguistic Acceptability (CoLa) in the GLUE benchmark dataset. CoLa spawned a thread that led to the development of several similar datasets in different languages, broadening the investigation possibilities to many languages other than English. In this study, leveraging the Italian Corpus of Linguistic Acceptability (ItaCoLA), comprising nearly 10,000 sentences with acceptability judgments, we propose a new methodology that utilizes the neural language model ELECTRA. This approach exceeds the scores obtained from current baselines and demonstrates that it can overcome language-specific limitations in dealing with specific phenomena.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	PE6_7 Artificial intelligence, intelligent systems, natural language processing, PE6_10 Web and information systems, data management systems, information retrieval and digital libraries, data fusion	R. Guarasci								
101	R. Guarasci, R. Catelli, M. Esposito	Classifying deceptive reviews for the cultural heritage domain: A lexicon-based approach for the Italian language	ICAR	articolo in rivista	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2024.124131	Nowadays, the spread of deceptive reviews is a problem that has reached critical dimensions, having a significant economic impact on business activities. This paper aims to estimate – at the quantitative and qualitative levels – the possibility of using particular words to disambiguate between truthful and deceptive text, focusing on reviews produced in the cultural heritage domain. For this purpose, a lexicon-based methodology has used two different lexicons: sentiment information, intensifiers, downtoners, and negation operators. As known in the literature, these elements are crucial in a classification process related to deceptiveness. The evaluation phase has considered quantitative metrics such as accuracy and F1 score and ad hoc developed metrics that consider specific linguistic parameters such as polarity and tone of voice intensifiers. A qualitative analysis of a subset of the corpus has also been carried out to understand better factors that impact the classification of deceptive review. Several linguistic features have been considered, ranging from the number of intensifiers to their type and position in phrases and sentences. A comparison between the performances of two different lexicons used has been added to the analysis.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	PE6_7 Artificial intelligence, intelligent systems, natural language processing, PE6_10 Web and information systems, data management systems, information retrieval and digital libraries, data fusion	R. Guarasci								
102	S. Palange	Generative Artificial Intelligence: Prompt Engineering Overview	ICAR	Report tecnico-scientifico	Scientific	https://intranet.icar.cnr.it/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/RT-ICAR-NA-2024-05-1.pdf	Questo rapporto tecnico esplora il tema del "Prompt Engineering" nell'ambito dell'intelligenza artificiale generativa (GenAI). Il Prompt Engineering è una tecnica fondamentale che consente di ottimizzare le interazioni con modelli linguistici avanzati, come quelli offerti da ChatGPT[1], Claude[2] di Anthropic[3] o altri. Il documento copre una panoramica delle diverse tecniche di scrittura del prompt[4], principalmente focalizzata sull'utilizzo di ChatGPT, il ruolo del token e l'importanza del contesto nel guidare i risultati desiderati. Viene inoltre descritto come sfruttare queste metodologie per migliorare l'efficienza e l'efficacia di applicazioni specifiche, con particolare attenzione all'ottimizzazione e all'uso di modelli AI per scopi aziendali e tecnici.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	PE6_7 Artificial intelligence, intelligent systems, natural language processing, PE6_10 Web and information systems, data management systems, information retrieval and digital libraries, data fusion	S. Palange								
103	Eva Pietroni, Alessandra Botteon, David Buti, Alessandra Chirivì, Chiara Colombo, Claudia Conti, Anna Letizia Di Carlo, Donata Magrini, Fulvio Mercuri, Noemi Orazi, Marco Reatini	"Codex 4D" Project: Interdisciplinary Investigations on Materials and Colors of De Balneis Puteolanis (Angelica Library, Rome, Ms. 1474)	OU10 ISPC-LE, OU12-ISPC-RM, OU04 ISPC-FI, OU11 ISPC-MI	articolo in rivista	Scientific	https://www.mdpi.com/2571-9408/7/6/131	The paper sheds light on the manufacturing processes, techniques, and materials used in the splendid illuminations of the oldest surviving copy of De Balneis Puteolanis, preserved at the Angelica Library in Rome (Ms. 1474). The findings result from the interdisciplinary study conducted in 2021–2023 in the framework of "Codex 4D: journey in four dimensions into the manuscript". The considerations we present aim at increasing the knowledge of book artefacts while respecting their extraordinary complexity; data from non-invasive diagnostic investigations (X-ray fluorescence, Vis-NIR reflectance and Raman spectroscopies, hyperspectral imaging, and multi-band imaging techniques such as ultraviolet, reflectography, and thermography), carried out in situ with portable in- instruments on the book, have been integrated with observations resulting from the historical-artistic study, and the reading of some ancient treatises on the production and use of the pigments and dyes employed in illumination.	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOSC project is mentioned	SH8_10 Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage									
104	Irene Rossi, Erica Scarpa, Riccardo Valente, Alberto Bucciero, Alessandra Chirivì, Matteo Greco, Andrea Pandurino	Workflow and requirements to ensure interoperability for Cultural Heritage Resources (Interim report)	OU10 - ISPC-LE, OU11 ISPC-MI	Project deliverable 4.10	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15007236	Task 4.10 focused on "Resources Interoperability: DIGILAB Resources (E-RHIS)" as part of Work Package 4 (WP4). This task emphasizes the mapping of formats, standards, and ontologies essential for Heritage Science, aiming for cross-domain integration and semantic interoperability through DIGILAB—a collaborative platform for data sharing and virtual research in Heritage Science. Key outputs include a semantic mapping of resources and the development of a specialized Heritage Science ontology compatible with international standards like CIDOC CRM.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH8_10 Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage	Erica Scarpa, Riccardo Valente, Matteo Greco, Andrea Pandurino								
105	Alberto Bucciero, Alessandra Chirivì, Andrea Pandurino, Martin Critelli, Emiliano Degl'Innocenti, Federica Spinelli, Silvestro Caligiuri, Lisa Reggiani	Guidelines for data, services, software platform policy implementation (draft)	OU10 ISPC-LE, OU01 OVI-FI, ILIESI-RM, UO 08 ILC,	Project deliverable 3.1	Scientific		Deliverable 3.1 "Guidelines for data, services, software platform policy implementation" is dedicated to the main challenges regarding the research activities to the consolidation and overall alignment of RIs and priority resources, according to the project proposal. About its structure, the deliverable is arranged in the following paragraphs. The deliverable describes the methodological approach adopted in the project activities focusing on the main issues such DATA POLICY IMPLEMENTATION, QUALITY ASSESSMENT OF REPOSITORIES, DATA AND METADATA, GUIDELINES FOR COMMON POLICIES IMPLEMENTATION.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH8_10 Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage	Andrea Pandurino, Martin Critelli, Federica Spinelli								

106	Bucciero A., Chirivì A., Cotella R., Critelli M., Greco M., Pandurino A., Spinelli F., Taurino F., Zecca D., Caligiuri S., Reggiani L.	Consolidating national repositories (draft 1st stage)	OU10 ISPC-LE, UO01 OVI-FI, ILIESI-RM, UO08 ILC	Project deliverable 3.2	Scientific		Deliverable 3.2 "Consolidating national repositories" (draft 1st stage) describes the activities relating to the consolidation and general alignment of both the RI and the priority resources for creating the Italian Cloud Network for research in humanities, linguistics and heritage science. The document provides a brief description of the current status of each IRs regarding technology, ICT and science issues. The Chapter "Alignment Operational Plan," describes the actions that each IRs has already implemented or will implement to align internal systems with the H2IOOSC cloud network. The final part is oriented on the design and development descriptions of the main services and tools from each IRs.	Publications with H2IOOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH8_10 Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage	Cotella Riccardo, Critelli Martin, Greco Matteo, Pandurino Andrea, Spinelli Federica, Taurino Francesco, Zecca Davide									
107		D5.1 CLARIN/OPERAS/DARIAH/ERIHs and the H2IOOSC MarketPlace	OU ILIESI-RM	Project deliverable 5.1	Scientific		Deliverable D.5.1 CLARIN/OPERAS/DARIAH/ERIHs and the H2IOOSC MarketPlace briefly describes the procedures for connecting the four participating IRs and the H2IOOSC MarketPlace, addressing structural interconnections, integration and interoperability between the systems. Strong links are highlighted with the development of WP4, which focuses on multi-level interoperability, and in particular the definition and development of the Common Semantic Framework. The Deliverable first describes the harvesting and providing procedures through which exchange and integration between systems will essentially take place, underlining the key role of the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) for interoperability. It then illustrates the data model used for the H2IOOSC MarketPlace, concentrating on the typological classification of items and their hierarchical categorisation. Furthermore, the usefulness of ontologies and controlled vocabularies is emphasised, both to facilitate and optimise the identification and search of resources in the H2IOOSC platform, and to support interoperability with other platforms and systems. Finally, since the H2IOOSC MarketPlace will ensure data exchange, interoperability and alignment not only with the four IRs and their respective catalogues, but also with other European infrastructures such as EOSC and SSHOC and their catalogues, the SSH Open Marketplace model, a European and international reference for the management of metadata and controlled vocabularies, is examined in detail.	Publications with H2IOOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere	Vittoria Fabiani, Pietro Sichera (ILIESI); Lucia Francalanci (OVI)									
108	L. Baggiani, M. Baggicchi, L. Mancini, L. Reggiani, A. Russo, P. Sichera, F. Silvestri, M. Stefani, E. Pasini (ILIESI); S. Cristofaro (ISTC); L. C. Colomba, M. Minetti, A. Panico (Links)	D4.11 Workflow and requirements to ensure interoperability for Open Science and Open Publishing Resources (interim report)	OU ILIESI-RM	Project deliverable 4.11	Scientific		Deliverable D 4.11 provides a description of the workflow and requirements to ensure interoperability for Open Science and Open Publishing Resources, focusing on the FAIRification process in all its aspects. During the definition and refinement of the workflow and requirements, close collaboration with the development of the Common Semantic Framework within WP4 and the design of the H2IOOSC MarketPlace (WP5) has, as expected, been essential. Strong links have also emerged and been consolidated with the development of the Pilots within WP7 for the centrality of the FAIRification process. The workflow, consisting of five phases, is illustrated together with the requirements specified for each phase. The main results of the workflow and the associated requirements are the construction of the data model with a FAIR approach and the design and implementation of the prototype software for the FAIRification of resources, to be integrated with the H2IOOSC MarketPlace. Typically, the workflow also includes functional and performance testing of the developed software prototype and its roll-out, monitoring and fine-tuning. In parallel, a system for building native FAIR resources and data is being designed and implemented, to be fully integrated with the aforementioned prototype software to ensure effective interoperability and smooth data exchange.	Publications with H2IOOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere	Laura Baggiani, Marco Baggicchi, Pietro Sichera, Federico Silvestri, Marta Stefani (ILIESI); Salvatore Cristofaro (ISTC)									
109	L. Mancini, L. Reggiani, A. Russo, P. Sichera, E. Pasini (ILIESI); P. R. Spagni (E4 Computer Engineering)	D4.12 OPERAS data facility design and development description	OU ILIESI-RM	Project deliverable 4.12	Scientific		Deliverable D4.12 OPERAS data facility design and development description illustrates the delivery and implementation of the Data Facility solutions for OPERAS, by examining the main features of the infrastructure and its essential components, the work plan for activating the service delivery and, finally, the next steps to be taken in the short term. In addition, the deliverable highlights the importance of the combination of advanced software solutions and hardware infrastructure, and the direction towards the full integration of the OPERAS Data Facility into the H2IOOSC system.	Publications with H2IOOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	PE6_10 Web and information systems, data management systems, information retrieval and digital libraries, data fusion; SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere	Pietro Sichera (ILIESI)									
110	G. Pedonese	H2IOOSC Training Environment - User Manual	OU ILC-PI	Manual	Technical	Pedonese, G., & Frontini, F. (2025). H2IOOSC Training Environment: User Manual. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14872004	courses available on the training utilisation platform called H2IOOSC Training Environment. The platform allows access to self-paced courses and training modules and offers interactive features for carrying out exercises and creating an online community. The platform was developed within the framework of the PNRR H2IOOSC	Publications with H2IOOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere	Giulia pedonese (ILC)									
111	G. Pedonese	H2IOOSC Training Library - User Manual	OU ILC-PI	Manual	Technical	Pedonese, G. (2025). H2IOOSC Training Library: User Manual. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15639323		Publications with H2IOOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere	Giulia Pedonese (ILC)									
112	Pedonese, G., Francesca, F., Ottaviani, R., Boschetti, F., Spadi, A., Francalanci, L., Scognamiglio, A., Restaneo, P., Chaban, A., Striova, J., & Benassi, L.	Dai Materiali Didattici alle Piattaforme FAIR: Costruire un'Infrastruttura di Training in H2IOOSC.	OU ILC-PI	Poster	Scientific	10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8380	Questo contributo si propone di illustrare la progettazione e lo sviluppo di un'inf	Publications with H2IOOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere	Giulia pedonese (ILC), Alessia Spadi (CNR-OVI), Lucia Francalanci (CNR-OVI), Roberta Ottaviani (CNR-ILC), Antonia Chaban (CNR-ILC), Alessia Spadi (CNR-OVI), Lucia Francalanci (CNR-OVI), Tommaso Falini (CNR-OVI), Giulia Pedonese (ILC), Alessia Spadi (CNR-OVI), Lucia Francalanci (CNR-OVI), Roberta Ottaviani (CNR-ILC)									
113	Francalanci, L., Scognamiglio, A., Restaneo, P., Falini, L., Pedonese, G., Spadi, A.	Il Glossario delle Infrastrutture di Ricerca (GIR)	OU OVI-FI	Article	Scientific	10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8380	Italian Open Science Cloud" del CNR, che mira a creare una federazione di Infrastrutture di Ricerca (IR) coinvolgendo i nodi italiani di quattro infrastrutture che fanno parte della roadmap dell'European Strategy Forum on	Publications with H2IOOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere										
114	Pedonese, G., Francesca, F., Ottavi	Materiali didattici come oggetti digit	OU ILC-PI	Article	Scientific	(ISSN): 2532-8816	L'articolo dettaglia la progettazione dell'infrastruttura di training H2IOOSC	Publications with H2IOOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere										
115	Scarpa, E., Valente, R., Rossi, I.	Modelling an Ontology for Heritage Science: Challenges and Key Strategies	UO11 ISPC-MI	Proceedings	Scientific	Heritage Science: Challenges and Key Strategies, in S. Rebera, M. Rospocher, S. Bazzaco (eds), Diversità, Equità e Inclusion: Sfide e Opportunità per l'Informatica Umanistica nell'Era dell'Intelligenza Artificiale. Proceedings del XIV Convegno Annuale AIUCD2025, Quaderni di Umanistica Digitale Verona.	This paper presents the authors' contributions to the Humanities and Cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud (H2IOOSC) project, in particular the development of an ontology for Heritage Science. Given the inherently multidisciplinary nature of Heritage Science, defining precise boundaries for the domain is a complex task that can hinder effective data organization and limit research potential. After providing a brief overview of the H2IOOSC project, the paper delves into the key challenges faced in the	Publications, from the scientific community, in which the H2IOOSC project is mentioned		Scarpa, E., Valente, R.									

116	Caravale, A., Moscati, P., Rossi, I.	Advancements of the H2IOSC Project: introduction to the special section and key results	U012-ISPC-RM; U011-ISPC-MI	Article	Scientific	Caravale A., Moscati P., Rossi I. 2025. Advancements of the H2IOSC Project: introduction to the special section and key results. In A. Caravale, P. Moscati, I. Rossi (eds.), The H2IOSC Project and its impact on digital antiquity within the E-RHIS infrastructure – III. «Archeologia e Calcolatori», 36.1, 431-434. https://doi.org/10.19282/ac.36.1.2025.25	Introduction to the Special Section for the H2IOSC Project	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement			
117	Caravale, A.	Diamond open access and research infrastructures: the involvement of «Archeologia e Calcolatori» in the H2IOSC Project	U012-ISPC-RM	Article	Scientific	Caravale A. 2025. Diamond open access and research infrastructures: the involvement of «Archeologia e Calcolatori» in the H2IOSC Project. In A. Caravale, P. Moscati, I. Rossi (eds.), The H2IOSC Project and its impact on digital antiquity within the E-RHIS infrastructure – III. «Archeologia e Calcolatori», 36.1, 435-443. https://doi.org/10.19282/ac.36.1.2025.23	«Archeologia e Calcolatori» (A&C) is an open access scientific journal that follows the Diamond Open Access model, ensuring free access to its content without any charges for authors or readers. One of the main challenges of this model is ensuring the long-term sustainability of the journals that adopt it. The consolidation and growth of A&C over the past two years have been supported by the involvement of the multidisciplinary research group surrounding the journal within the H2IOSC project, through various forms of collaboration and engagement. This synergy has contributed to strengthening the editorial initiative and its related activities, expanding its scope and potential scientific impact through the enhancement of its textual, bibliographic, and visual resources.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement			
118	Mancuso, G.	Beyond monitoring. Reimagining DHeLO as a Linked Open Data Infrastructure for Cultural Heritage research	U012-ISPC-RM	Article	Scientific	Mancuso G. 2025. Beyond monitoring. Reimagining DHeLO as a Linked Open Data Infrastructure for Cultural Heritage research. In A. Caravale, P. Moscati, I. Rossi (eds.), The H2IOSC Project and its impact on digital antiquity within the E-RHIS infrastructure – III. «Archeologia e Calcolatori», 36.1, 443-454. https://doi.org/10.19282/ac.36.1.2025.24	This article presents the transformation of DHeLO (Digital Heritage Landscaping Platform) from a relational database into a Linked Open Data (LOD) infrastructure, designed to enhance the discoverability, interoperability, and reuse of digital resources within Cultural Heritage (CH), Heritage Science (HS), and Digital Archaeology (DA) research. Initially conceived within the H2IOSC project as a virtual observatory for cataloguing digital products, tools, and research projects, DHeLO has been restructured as a service-oriented system in response to emerging community needs and a broader reflection on its role. The transition was guided by insights gained from landscaping activities conducted within Work Package 2, including questionnaires and interviews with members of the DH, DA, and HS communities. The new configuration of DHeLO integrates metadata on research outputs, projects, people, and bibliographic references, laying the foundation for a knowledge graph that mirrors the research landscape. A key step in this evolution was the adoption of Omeka S as the core platform, chosen for its modularity, semantic interoperability, and synergy with Zotero, which supports the integration of the BIDA bibliographic database. In this form DHeLO aspires to become an active research resource, moving beyond mere monitoring to foster exploratory analysis and linked knowledge networks.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement		Mancuso, G.	
119	Caravale A., D'Eredità A., Mancuso, G., Moscati P.	An Open System for Textual, Visual, and Bibliographic Resources: the Open Digital Archaeology Hub	U012-ISPC-RM	paper	Scientific	Caravale A., D'Eredità A., Mancuso G., Moscati P. 2025. An Open System for Textual, Visual, and Bibliographic Resources: the Open Digital Archaeology Hub. In A. Caravale, P. Moscati, I. Rossi (eds.), The H2IOSC Project and its impact on digital antiquity within the E-RHIS infrastructure – III. «Archeologia e Calcolatori», 36.1, 455-468. https://doi.org/10.19282/ac.36.1.2025.25	The Open Digital Archaeology Hub (ArchaeoHub) is a modular and extensible platform developed within the H2IOSC project to support the aggregation and dissemination of digital archaeological resources. Conceived as a metadata aggregator rather than a repository, it integrates textual, visual, and bibliographic data from diverse sources, including the journal «Archeologia e Calcolatori» the BIDA bibliographic platform, and the DHeLO web app. Its structure is based on a hub-and-spoke model, designed to enable thematic collections organized around geographic entities, using Pleiades identifiers and WebGIS technologies to enhance discovery and contextualization. ArchaeoHub promotes interoperability through standards such as RDF, Dublin Core, and JSON-LD, and supports linked data connections with external resources. It offers scholars and institutions a lightweight, FAIR-compliant environment to access and cross-reference data. A key feature is its integration with BIDA, a curated bibliography of digital archaeology structured through Zotero, enabling citation tracking and semantic classification. The platform exemplifies a shift from static repositories to dynamic, research-oriented infrastructures aligned with national and international best practices. Positioned within the broader landscape of digital heritage infrastructures, ArchaeoHub serves as both a scholarly resource and a methodological prototype for managing complex archaeological information in a collaborative, open-access framework.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement		D'Eredità A., Mancuso, G.	
120	Rossi I.	Building an Ecosystem of Digital Resources on the Written Heritage of Ancient Arabia	U011-ISPC-MI	paper	Scientific	Rossi I. 2025. Building an ecosystem of digital resources on the written heritage of Ancient Arabia. In A. Caravale, P. Moscati, I. Rossi (eds.), The H2IOSC Project and its impact on digital antiquity within the E-RHIS infrastructure – III. «Archeologia e Calcolatori», 36.1, 469-480. https://doi.org/10.19282/ac.36.1.2025.26	The Digital Archive for the Study of pre-Islamic Arabian Inscriptions (DASI, https://dasi.cnr.it/) currently provides open access to the digital editions of nearly 8800 ancient epigraphic texts from the Arabian Peninsula. After presenting an outline of DASI ecosystem through its 25-year history, this paper focuses on the recent enrichment of its data model, carried out within a pilot project of the E-RHIS infrastructure under the H2IOSC programme. The aim was to optimise DASI as an up-to-date tool for the digital critical edition of a broad spectrum of epigraphic sources from ancient Arabia, including graffiti, instrumenta inscripta, coins, and inscribed sticks, alongside 'monumental' inscriptions. Most of the interventions targeted the description of the visual aspect of writing and related contextual information, enhancing the digital representation of the material dimension of written heritage, which is often overlooked in philological studies. Ongoing work is targeting the FAIRification of DASI data, which has so far resulted in the shaping of an extensive bibliography of 1800 records through Zotero .	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; digital approaches to literary studies and philosophy SH6_8 Ancient history, medieval history		
121	Scarpa, E.	Demystifying the CIDOC CRM: a lightweight introduction	U011-ISPC-MI	paper	Scientific	Scarpa E. 2025. Demystifying the CIDOC CRM: a lightweight introduction. In A. Caravale, P. Moscati, I. Rossi (eds.), The H2IOSC Project and its impact on digital antiquity within the E-RHIS infrastructure – III. «Archeologia e Calcolatori», 36.1, 481-492. https://doi.org/10.19282/ac.36.1.2025.27	This paper provides a concise overview of the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC CRM). The CIDOC CRM is a formal ontology initially developed for museums and cultural institutions to describe and organize their data. It serves as the ISO standard for representing museum and cultural heritage knowledge. The paper outlines the model's core principles, advantages, challenges, and implications for its use, touching upon the CIDOC CRM's relationship with the Semantic Web and challenges in implementing it with technologies like RDFS and OWL. It also highlights challenges in querying CIDOC-based knowledge graphs and integrating pre-existing heterogeneous data.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; digital approaches to literary studies and philosophy	Scarpa, E.	
122	Valente, R.	A preliminary analysis of ARIADNE's administrative metadata	U011-ISPC-MI	paper	Scientific	Valente R. 2025. A preliminary analysis of ARIADNE's administrative metadata. In A. Caravale, P. Moscati, I. Rossi (eds.), The H2IOSC Project and its impact on digital antiquity within the E-RHIS infrastructure – III. «Archeologia e Calcolatori», 36.1, 493-504. https://doi.org/10.19282/ac.36.1.2025.28	This article provides a preliminary analysis of the administrative metadata of the ARIADNE resources. ARIADNE, an acronym for Advanced Research Infrastructure for Archaeological Dataset Networking in Europe, is a European archaeological infrastructure that supports research. The presented analyses were performed accessing the ARIADNE Knowledge Base via its SPARQL Endpoint. The distribution of available resources per publishers' country, of archival resources, of combinations of ARIADNE subjects and of combinations of agents (publishers, creators, contributors, owners, scientific responsibilities) were estimated and commented, tracing an up-to-date profile of the infrastructure.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH6_6 Digital, computational, virtual and geospatial archaeologies	Valente, R.	
123	Mancuso, G.	Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) in Cultural Heritage Information Systems	U012-ISPC-RM	paper	Scientific	Mancuso, G. 2025. Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) in Cultural Heritage Information Systems. In A. Caravale, P. Moscati, I. Rossi (eds.), The H2IOSC Project and its impact on digital antiquity within the E-RHIS infrastructure – III. «Archeologia e Calcolatori», 36.1, 505-509. https://doi.org/10.19282/ac.36.1.2025.29		Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement		Mancuso, G.	
124	Scarpa, E., Valente, R., Rossi, I.	«IRADIOSA»: Recommended Approaches for the Development of Interoperable Open Semantic Artefacts in the Heritage Domain	U011-ISPC-MI	Proceedings	Scientific	DIGITAL HERITAGE 2025 8 – 13 September 2025 Siena, Italy, ed. by Campana Stefano, Ferdani Daniele, Graf Holger, Guidi Gabriele, Hegarty Zackary, Pescarin Sofia, Remondino Fabio. https://doi.org/10.2312/dh.20253041	The paper offers actionable recommendations and best practices for developing semantic artefacts in the Heritage field. Aimed at both experts and non-specialists, it highlights the importance of adopting FAIR and Linked Data principles. Drawing on a survey of existing tools and a review of relevant literature, the «IRADIOSA» initiative proposes guidelines to bridge the gap between domain-specific needs and technical standards. These recommendations serve as a call to action for researchers and practitioners to foster the creation of high-quality, interoperable semantic artefacts	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere	Scarpa, E., Valente, R.	
125	Fanini, B.; Andrucci, F.; Amadei, C.F.; Gosti, G.; De Luca, D.; Imboden, S.; Guidazzoli, A.	Developing interactive web-based virtual environments using ATON and Godot	U012-ISPC-RM	Proceedings	Scientific	DIGITAL HERITAGE 2025 8 – 13 September 2025 Siena, Italy, ed. by Campana Stefano, Ferdani Daniele, Graf Holger, Guidi Gabriele, Hegarty Zackary, Pescarin Sofia, Remondino Fabio. https://doi.org/10.2312/dh.20253293	Creating Interactive Online Virtual Spaces with Open-Source Tools. Among the available options, the tutorial will focus on two solutions: ATON and Godot, evaluating them also in light of their strengths and weaknesses. Both frameworks support 3D environments ranging from the smallest scale to large ones, such as a city. ATON and Godot can also be used in interaction with each other.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	PE6_8 Computer graphics, computer vision, multimedia, computer games; SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere	Amadei, C.F.; Gosti, G.	
126	Amadei, C.F.; Massidda, M.; Menconero, S.; Gosti, G.; Fanini, B.	Early Stage of Community-Driven UI/UX Refactoring of the Open-Source ATON Framework	U012-ISPC-RM, U04-ISPC-FI	Proceedings	Scientific	DIGITAL HERITAGE 2025 8 – 13 September 2025 Siena, Italy, ed. by Campana Stefano, Ferdani Daniele, Graf Holger, Guidi Gabriele, Hegarty Zackary, Pescarin Sofia, Remondino Fabio. https://doi.org/10.2312/dh.20253115	The digitisation of cultural heritage has become a central practice in recent years, responding to the needs for the preservation, enhancement and study of cultural assets. The increasing production of digital resources has seen the development of online platforms for visualising and sharing 3D models and 360 panoramas, also facilitating access and management of this type of data. The democratisation of these tools, coupled with their increasing user-friendliness, has expanded and diversified the scientific communities involved, widening the catchment area from a single audience of experts to general users. This has led to the emergence of new needs on the part of the users involved, necessitating a re-evaluation of the logic underpinning the consumption of digital services. This paper analyses the case study of ATON: an open-source framework design for creating Web3D/WebXR apps interacting with CH objects and 3D scenes on the Web, which underwent a complete refactoring of the User Experience (UX) and User Interface (UI) through the H2IOSC project. Starting with the analysis of the recent spread of metaeas technologies has propelled the digitalization of cultural heritage, particularly the production of 3D models of historical artifacts and sites. This context presents new challenges and opportunities, among these arises the possibility of investigating the design of public engagement and cultural dissemination initiatives through the analytical study of user behavior. With this objective, we developed Procezo, a modular data analysis suite that facilitates the processing and aggregation of user experience data via an easy-to-use web interface, specifically engineered for cultural heritage applications. Indeed, with immersive XR devices, motion-tracking tools, sensors, and online web applications, we can easily record users' experiences in virtual or real environments. From these recorded experiences, with Procezo's specifically developed web-based analytics, we may obtain crucial insights into user interaction patterns. Procezo is part of a larger pilot developed under the H2IOSC project named "Interium". The pilot is divided into three stages: data capture (Kanto)	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	PE6_9 Human computer interaction and interface, visualisation; Science and technologies for cultural heritage	Amadei, C.F.; Gosti, G.; Massidda, M.; Menconero, S.	
127	Gosti, G.; Menconero, S.; Amadei, C.F.; Fanini, B.	Procezo: Data Processing Services for 3D Analytics	U012-ISPC-RM	Proceedings	Scientific	DIGITAL HERITAGE 2025 8 – 13 September 2025 Siena, Italy, ed. by Campana Stefano, Ferdani Daniele, Graf Holger, Guidi Gabriele, Hegarty Zackary, Pescarin Sofia, Remondino Fabio. https://doi.org/10.2312/dh.20253099		Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	PE6_9 Human computer interaction and interface, visualisation; PE6_11 Machine learning, statistical data processing and applications using signal processing (e.g. speech, image, video)	Amadei, C.F.; Gosti, G.; Menconero, S.	

142	A. Botteon, M. Botticelli, D. Buti, C. Calliri, L. Carcechini, A. C. Muncichia, C. Conti, V. Di Tullio, E. Ferraris, M. Giugni, L. Luvdi, D. Magrini, L. Monico, E. L. Ravan, A. Romani, F. P. Romano, F. Rosi, G. Santagati, S. Töpfer	Advanced investigation of the Book of the Dead of Kha at the Museo Egizio of Turin: A MOLAB E-RHS in-situ study	UO9 ISPC-CT	Poster	Scientific	TECHNART 2025 - International Conference on Analytical Techniques for Heritage Studies and Conservation, Hotel Gio, Perugia Centro Congressi, Via Ruggero D'Andreotto, 19 06124 Perugia, https://technart2025.com/conference	In February 2024, a comprehensive MOLAB E-RHS study was conducted at the Egyptian Museum of Turin to investigate the painting materials, techniques, and conservation state of the Book of the Dead of Kha, a rare and remarkably well-preserved funerary papyrus from the 18th Dynasty. The study employed a multi-analytical approach, integrating advanced portable and non-invasive imaging and single-point techniques, including scanning Macro X-ray Fluorescence (MAXRF), UV-IR imaging, VIS-NIR hyperspectral imaging, high-resolution digital microscopy, mapping X-ray Diffraction (MAXRD), Raman spectroscopy, micro-SORS, and VIS-NIR and IR external reflection spectroscopy. The synergy of these techniques provided an in-depth characterization of the papyrus's pigments, binders, and overall conservation state. Imaging and scanning analytical methods allowed for a macro-scale depiction of the pigment palette and artistic techniques, highlighting key areas for further investigation using single-point methods. High-resolution microscopy offered valuable insights into surface morphology, painting texture and application, as well as the physical condition of the papyrus. MAXRF revealed the elemental composition of various inorganic pigments, which were molecularly identified through vibrational and electronic spectroscopy, as well as MAXRD. Egyptian blue was found in both blue and black paints, while Egyptian green was used alongside a possible organic copper-based green. Different types of ochre paints, as well as arsenic-based yellow and red pigments, were detected. Huntite and carbon black were identified as white and black pigments, respectively. Micro-SORS enabled depth-profiling of arsenic-based pigments, providing insights into their alteration mechanisms. Meanwhile, FTIR spectroscopy facilitated the analysis of organic materials, including binders, restoration materials, and degradation products.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SHB - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Botticelli, M.	Ravan, E.L.	
143	G. Santagati, M. Botticelli, T. Arcidiacono, C. Calliri, F. Falcone, C. Miliani, E. L. Ravan, F. P. Romano	Lab-based XAS spectroscopy in the study of pigment materials serving the FIXLAB platform of E-RHS	UO9 ISPC-CT	Poster	Scientific	TECHNART 2025 - International Conference on Analytical Techniques for Heritage Studies and Conservation, Hotel Gio, Perugia Centro Congressi, Via Ruggero D'Andreotto, 19 06124 Perugia, https://technart2025.com/conference	X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy (XAS) is a well-established technique for chemical speciation, widely applied at synchrotron facilities for pigment analysis. Being highly sensitive to the local atomic structure, it provides unique insights into oxidation states, bond types, bond lengths, and coordination environments, even in amorphous or poorly crystalline phases [1]. In particular, the XANES (X-ray Absorption Near Edge Structure) region is especially sensitive to local coordination and oxidation states in transition metal ions [2]. The EXAFS (Extended X-ray Absorption Fine Structure) region, extending beyond the absorption edge, reveals interatomic distances, coordination numbers, and structural disorder [2]. When used together in painting investigation, XANES and EXAFS provide a comprehensive view of both the electronic and geometric factors influencing the pigment stability or its degradation due to aging, environmental factors or pigment-binder interaction. Recent improvements in X-ray sources and detectors now enable XAS measurements in laboratory environments, reducing reliance on large-scale facilities. In this work we present a novel lab-based XAS system recently installed at XRAYLab of ISPC-CNR in Catania, accessible through the FIXLAB platform of E-RHS. We demonstrate the feasibility of using this instrument to characterize ancient and modern pigments, both in the form of compressed pellets or thin paint fragments, typically obtained from the sampling often performed during the restoration procedures of real artworks. Specifically, we have developed a dedicated protocol for the instrument to analyze real samples, incorporating guidelines for sample preparation that include the minimum quantity of pigment required and the minimum detection time needed for obtaining reliable spectra. Preliminary results showcase the ability of lab-based XAS system to 1) reproduce XAS spectra obtained at synchrotron facilities for reference standards and specific pigment materials; 2) detect subtle spectral shifts and features indicative of phase transformations in pictorial pigments.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SHB - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Botticelli, M., Santagati, G., Preisler, Z.	Ravan, E.L.	
144	S. Longo, R. Andolina, M. Botticelli, S. Bottura Scardina, F. Falcone, M. Fera, G. Ghiara, C. Miliani, E.L. Ravan, F.P. Romano, M. Mödinger and C. Calliri	The doors of the Basilica di San Marco: a scientific examination through MA-XRF	UO9 ISPC-CT	Poster	Scientific	TECHNART 2025 - International Conference on Analytical Techniques for Heritage Studies and Conservation, Hotel Gio, Perugia Centro Congressi, Via Ruggero D'Andreotto, 19 06124 Perugia, https://technart2025.com/conference	This study focuses on the copper alloy doors of the Basilica di San Marco in Venice, renowned for their artistic and historical value, with particular attention to their chemical composition, production methods, and detailed inlays. Dating back to the 11th and 12th centuries, these doors exemplify a blend of Byzantine, Gothic, and Renaissance styles, featuring decorative motifs, biblical scenes, and depictions of saints, as well as the distinctive use of a variety of different inlays. Macro X-ray Fluorescence (MA-XRF) analysis, carried out during the GAPAMET MOLAB E-RHS campaign, was employed to evaluate the elemental distribution and identify key materials present across the doors. For the first time, this advanced MA-XRF technology was utilized to reveal the elemental composition of the materials used as inlay on these historic bronze doors, providing new insights into their manufacture. The analysis uncovered a broad range of elements, including copper (Cu), silver (Ag), gold (Au), mercury (Hg), tin (Sn), lead (Pb), and zinc (Zn), with notable compositional differences between the Main Door (MD) and the San Clemente Door (SC). These variations imply that the doors were likely created in separate workshops or at different times, possibly utilizing different alloys. The ability to identify and map the distribution of these elements with high precision allows for a deeper understanding of the materials and techniques used by the craftsmen of the time, shedding light on the historical processes behind these iconic doors.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SHB - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Botticelli, M.	Ravan, E.L.	
145	Eva Luna Ravan, Silvia Bottura-Scardina, Rosario Andolina, Irene Barba Castagnaro, Nichola Botticelli, Sveva Longo, Marco Maulu, Costanza Miliani, Gianluca Santagati, Francesco Paolo Romano, Claudia Calliri	Illegible writings recovered in carbonized fire-damaged manuscripts with high lateral resolution and high chemical sensitivity MA-XRF scanning: the case of the Torino, BNU, L.II.14	UO9 ISPC-CT	Poster	Scientific	TECHNART 2025 - International Conference on Analytical Techniques for Heritage Studies and Conservation, Hotel Gio, Perugia Centro Congressi, Via Ruggero D'Andreotto, 19 06124 Perugia, https://technart2025.com/conference	The legibility of ancient fire-damaged manuscripts remains a significant challenge, even after substantial restoration work. Direct or indirect contact with fire causes a series of extreme, complex, and irreversible material and structural changes, including uneven thermal contraction of the support and denaturation of the parchment, resulting in the shrinkage of the textual parts. Moreover, such damage may add to previous degradation phenomena occurring in medieval manuscripts, such as oxidation and the migration of inorganic compounds in the writing ink across the support. Even after restoration, ancient fire-damaged manuscripts may show an unrecoverable loss of optical contrast between the writing and the support, particularly in highly carbonised pages, making it impossible to access their literary content. Optical methodologies, such as UV-fluorescence photography, either alone or in combination with contrast enhancement techniques, have been tested in the past [1] but can be insufficient for severely damaged items. Mobile μ -XRF scanning techniques offer a promising alternative, as they can generate 2-D elemental distribution maps of the materials used in ink in a completely non-invasive and contact-free manner. Considering the above, this paper presents the work towards the development of an analytical methodology for writing recovery in severely fire-damaged parchment manuscripts using a mobile μ -XRF scanning system with real-time imaging capabilities developed by CNR-ISPC (Catania) and featuring an innovative hodoscopic detection system based on 4-SDDs, enabling high chemical sensitivity. The methodology has been applied to the French-Picard manuscript L.I.14 (dating back to 1311) of the Biblioteca Nazionale Universitaria (BNU), Turin. A fire that broke out in 1904 affected the BNU and damaged Ms L.II.14, along with a large part of the entire manuscript collection, posing significant challenges for legibility and conservation [2]. The results of μ -XRF imaging of the manuscript conducted at various lateral resolutions to accommodate the morphological irregularities of individual folios and combined with advanced data post-processing techniques, enabled the recovery of textual portions that were previously completely inaccessible to the naked eye.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SHB - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Botticelli, M., Santagati, G.	Ravan, E.L.	
146	Mohamed Emara, Noushin Najafiragheb, Mohamed Ali Jaziri, Riccardo Colella, Andrea Pandurino, Francesco Taurino, Davide Zecca, Alberto Bucciero	SENSE IoT Platform for Real-Time Monitoring: Network Design and Hardware Implementation	OU10 ISPC-LE	Proceedings	Scientific	2025 10th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies (SpliTech) - IEEE DOI: 10.23919/SpliTech65624.2025.11091689	The rise of the Internet of Things (IoT) has revolutionised environmental monitoring, enhancing comfort, energy efficiency, and sustainability across indoor and outdoor spaces. However, preventive conservation in cultural heritage still lacks real-time monitoring and predictive capabilities. This paper presents SENSE, an IoT-driven platform designed to support the monitoring, management, and preservation of cultural heritage sites and artefacts. SENSE integrates wireless sensor networks with cloud-based analytics to enable real-time data collection, processing, and automated environmental control. The platform's architecture spans multiple network layers, from sensing hardware to cloud support proactive heritage management.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SHB - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage;	Mohamed Emara, Riccardo Colella, Andrea Pandurino, Francesco Taurino, Davide Zecca	Noushin Najafiragheb, Mohamed Ali Jaziri,	
147	Alberto Bucciero, Marta Castellini, Alessandra Chirivì, Riccardo Colella, Alessandro Conti, Mohamed Emara, Lidia Fiorini, Matteo Greco, Mohamed Ali Jaziri, Mariacristina Metrangolo, Irene Muci, Noushin Najafiragheb, Andrea Pandurino, Cristiano Riminesi, Stefano Santo Sabato, Francesco Valentino Taurino, Grazia Tucci, Davide Zecca	Real-time environmental monitoring in historical semiconfined spaces: a case study of the sense IoT deployment in florence	OU10 ISPC-LE	Proceedings	Scientific	33rd International Conference on Software, Telecommunications, and Computer Networks (SoftCOM 2025) - IEEE Accepted in press	This paper presents the deployment and evaluation of the SENSE platform, an IoT-based solution combining distributed environmental sensors and 3D digital twin integration. SENSE was implemented in the Grotta degli Animali, a semiconfined 16th-century grotto in Florence, Italy. The platform continuously monitored temperature, humidity, enabling spatially contextualized data analysis through immersive visualization. Exploratory analysis revealed zone-specific microclimatic responses, and there were remarkable humidity responses to water activation in the Lion tub, emphasizing the need for adaptive, localized conservation measures. SENSE demonstrates how real-time sensing, linked to interactive spatial models, can enhance conservation decision-making and support proactive heritage management.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SHB - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage;	Riccardo Colella, Mohamed Emara, Matteo Greco, Andrea Pandurino, Francesco Valentino Taurino, Davide Zecca	Noushin Najafiragheb, Mariacristina Metrangolo	Irene Muci
148	Davide Zecca, Irene Muci, Francesco Valentino Taurino, Mohamed Ali Jaziri, Alberto Bucciero	Digital Heritage Conservation: The SENSE IoT Platform as a Structured Approach for Cultural Heritage Monitoring Projects	OU10 ISPC-LE	Proceedings	Scientific	2025 IMEKO TC-26 INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON Metrology for Archaeology and Cultural Heritage Accepted in press	The care of tangible heritage is a relevant aspect in the field of cultural heritage (CH). New systems have been developed to monitor and protect cultural assets such as buildings, monuments, archaeological sites and artifacts preserved in museums. IoT technologies play a key role in the design and implementation of CH monitoring services. This paper proposes the design of the workflow for the planning of a Monitoring Project (MP) in the context of the implementation of a software platform called SENSE (Spatial hERitage science Online Sensor Environment) based on IoT technologies, which aims to create an online system for sharing, managing and processing data coming from acquisitions in the CH field. The workflow is planned to assist the user in adopting a scientific approach, from the design to the installation of a sensor network in indoor and outdoor locations	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SHB - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage;	Davide Zecca, Francesco Valentino Taurino	Mohamed Ali Jaziri	Irene Muci
149	Francesco Valentino Taurino, Irene Muci, Davide Zecca, Cristiano Riminesi, Grazia Tucci Alberto Bucciero	Environmental monitoring of The Grotto of the Animals: a case study for the SENSE IoT platform	OU10 ISPC-LE	Proceedings	Scientific	2025 IMEKO TC-26 INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON Metrology for Archaeology and Cultural Heritage Accepted in press	The care of tangible heritage is a relevant aspect in the field of cultural heritage (CH). New systems have been developed to monitor and protect cultural assets such as buildings, monuments, archaeological sites and artifacts preserved in museums. IoT technologies play a key role in the design and implementation of CH monitoring services. This paper proposes the design of the workflow for the planning of a Monitoring Project (MP) in the context of the implementation of a software platform called SENSE (Spatial hERitage science Online Sensor Environment) based on IoT technologies, which aims to create an online system for sharing, managing and processing data coming from acquisitions in the CH field. The workflow is planned to assist the user in adopting a scientific approach, from the design to the installation of a sensor network in indoor and outdoor locations	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SHB - Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage;	Francesco Valentino Taurino, Davide Zecca,	Irene Muci	

150	Eva Pietroni, Alessandra Chirivì, Matteo Greco, Andrea Pandurino, Alberto Bucciero, Alessandro Lupinacci, Romano Aloisi, Marco Cozza	The Illuminated Manuscripts pilot project: a hub dedicated to the interdisciplinary study of ancient codices, integrated into the Digilab-IT platform	OU10 ISPC-LE	Proceedings	Scientific	Digital Heritage 2025 – 4th International Congress & Expo https://doi.org/10.2312/dh.20253210	The "Illuminated Manuscripts Hub" provides innovative digital services, tools, and VR environments aiming to increase the knowledge of handwritten and decorated ancient codices. A new cross-disciplinary approach is introduced in the study, digital representation, and knowledge transmission of these complex artefacts, going beyond the traditional 2D digitisation and digital catalogues. Manuscripts are presented in their tangible and intangible aspects, including invisible features hidden beneath the surface. A knowledge graph, as well as 2D representations, 3D and 4D virtual models integrate and contextualise information related to decorative apparatus, text and writing, structure, execution techniques, materials, state of conservation. These contents adopt standard formats and frameworks such as IIIF and GLTF, and the collections are accessible through the Digilab-IT, aiming to be the digital access platform to the Italian node of the European Infrastructure for Heritage Science	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SHB_Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage;	Matteo Greco, Andrea Pandurino		
151	Irene Muci, Alberto Bucciero, Alessandra Chirivì, Matteo Greco,	Explora: research data exploration and discovery	OU10 ISPC-LE	Proceedings	Scientific	XLI Convegno Scienza e Beni Culturali Bressanone, 30 giugno - 3 luglio 2026 ISBN: 978-88-95409-28-3	There is a strong need throughout the scientific community for effective tools for analyzing, transforming, and correlating information from different sources. Despite this, in the vast cultural heritage community, heterogeneous information (be it the result of diagnostic investigations or humanistic research) is often managed independently within individual research groups and, over the years, stratified in a series of extremely heterogeneous paper and digital repositories. ReXplora project aims to overcome this fragmentation by providing scientists to access, explore and visualize scientific data	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SHB_Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage;	Matteo Greco		Irene Muci
152	Matteo Greco, Alessandra Chirivì, Andrea Pandurino, Alberto Bucciero	Mobile diagnostic data manager: a collaborative environment for the heritage science community	OU10 ISPC-LE	conference presentation	Scientific	"TECHNART 2025 - International Conference on Analytical Techniques for Heritage Studies and Conservation, Hotel Gio, Perugia Centro Congressi, Via Ruggero D'Andreatto, 19 https://technart2025.com/assets/book-of-abstract_def.pdf	Heritage science operations are increasingly data-intensive. In this context, research data is typically stored in isolated repositories, often inaccessible to others in the field. Furthermore, the diagnostic studies applied to Cultural Heritage are characterized by a plethora of tools, protocols, settings, and data formats; at the same time, the scientific investigation process itself is not always adequately documented, often making its replication impossible. This fragmentation creates a significant challenge and generates a strong need throughout the scientific community for effective tools capable of analyzing, transforming, and correlating information from these disparate sources. To address these needs, we are developing a new digital application for the collaborative management of data derived from multi-technique non-invasive	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SHB_Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage;	Matteo Greco, Andrea Pandurino		Irene Muci
153	Valeria Minisini, Irene Muci	Linee guida per una cultura open del patrimonio digitale italiano	OU10 ISPC-LE	Poster	Scientific	1° Congresso Nazionale sull'Integrità nella Ricerca https://www.ethics.cnr.it/galleria-poster-congresso/#	Nel medesimo anno della Dichiarazione di Messina, in Italia entra in vigore il Codice dei Beni culturali e del paesaggio (D. Lgs. 42/2004) improntato su una visione tradizionale dei beni definiti all'art. 2, co. 2, "testimonianze aventi valore di civiltà". Principale fonte normativa per il settore, nonostante diversi	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SHB_Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage;			Irene Muci
154	Mohamed Emara; Alberto Bucciero; Luca Catarinucci; Giuseppe Grassi; Riccardo Colella	SPICE-Based Circuit Modelling and Validation of an NFC Energy-Harvesting Strain Sensor for Structural Health Monitoring	OU10 ISPC-LE	paper in rivista	Scientific	IEEE Sensors Journal DOI: 10.1109/ISEN.2025.3607401	Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) demands advanced and reliable systems and circuits capable of continuously detecting environmental and mechanical stressors that may impair the integrity, durability, and stability of critical infrastructure. This study introduces an innovative, untethered, and battery-free solution that combines Near Field Communication (NFC)-powered circuits with flexible strain gauge (SG) sensors for non-invasive SHM, specifically targeting surface-level cracks and deformations. The system is based on a specially designed NFC circuit that handles both energy	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SHB_Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage;	Mohamed Emara, Riccardo Colella		
155	Alessandra Chirivì, Eva Pietroni, Matteo Greco, Andrea Pandurino, Alberto Bucciero	An evolving scenario in the study of illuminated manuscripts: innovative approaches to research questions	OU10 ISPC-LE; UO12 ISPC-RM	paper in rivista	Scientific	under peer review - DAACH Special issue Innovative digital methodologies to enhance documentation, knowledge and accessibility to manuscripts	The paper provides an overview of the innovative digital services and tools implemented within three research projects aimed at increasing knowledge and promoting the enhancement of illuminated manuscripts: Codex 4D, DataSpace-ISPC and Illuminated Manuscripts Hub. These very fragile and complex artefacts are contemplated in their dual role as physical objects and carriers of symbolic content. They are investigated and presented in their multiple tangible and intangible elements	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SHB_Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage;	Matteo Greco, Andrea Pandurino		
156	Righetti, V., Pezzati, L., Quintero Baibas, D., Chaban, A., Innocenti, S., & Striova, J.	Multimodal optical approach for cultural he	UO15 INO-F1	paper	scientific	Conference "Optics for Arts, Architecture, and Archaeology X", 23-25 June 2025, in SPIE Proceedings, 2025 (O3A) X 13569, 1356903. https://doi.org/10.1117/12.3063578	This study presents a novel platform for the non-invasive analysis of painted surfaces, integrating sequentially shifted excitation (SSE) TM Raman spectroscopy with 3D scanning. Designed for hardware	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SHB_Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Quintero Baibas D., Chaban A.		Innocenti S.
157	Chaban A., Tornari V., Andrianakis M., Lanfranchi M.R., Striova J.	Optimising DHSPi-SIRT diagnostics: combined thermal & humidity excitation on fresco mock-ups	UO15 INO-F1	paper	scientific	Conference "Optics for Arts, Architecture, and Archaeology X", 23-25 June 2025, in SPIE Proceedings, 2025 (O3A) X 13569, 1356903. https://doi.org/10.1117/12.3067951	mosaic conservation problems, induced by external factors, are related to temperature and humidity variations, which may result in moisture, salt crystallization and accelerated material deterioration within the underlying layers. Though such deterioration in the subsurface is not immediately visible, it can strongly affect the preservation of the entire structure and the decoration layer in the short or long-term future. In this paper, we present and discuss laboratory experimental results of Digital Holographic Speckle Pattern Interferometry (DHSPi), applied to the subsurface diagnostic of a mosaic model after artificially induced thermal change and under simulated environmental conditions in climate chamber. The tests were performed on a custom-built wall mosaic model with known construction and known defects, which are simulating voids, detachments and deteriorated, restored or reshuffled areas. Two types of induced stress were used: 1) low thermal excitation emitted by IR lamps directly to the surface; 2) simulated environmental conditions inside the climate chamber. In regards of the in-situ diagnostic investigation any structural alteration occurs as a natural reaction to the surrounding environment and monitoring of surface reactions and defect detection under natural fluctuations it could be considered as a very important aspect of implementation to optimize range of applicability for non-destructive remote portable instrumentation. The obtained DHSPi results on the detection of known defects in the mosaic under artificially induced thermal alteration and under simulated environmental conditions are compared and discussed.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SHB_Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Chaban A.		
158	Chaban A., Benassi L., Pedonese G., Frontini F., Ottaviani R., Boschetti F., Spadi A., Francalanci L., Scognamiglio A., Restaneo P., Striova J.	Bridging Disciplines for Heritage Professionals: The H2IOSC Digital Training Platform (by CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RHS and OPERAS)	UO15 INO-F1; ILIESI; ILC, OV, ISPF	paper	scientific	DIGITAL HERITAGE 2025 8 – 13 September 2025 Siena, Italy, ed. by Campana Stefano, Ferdani Daniele, Graf Holger, Guidi Gabriele, Hegarty Zackary, Pescarin Sofia, Remondino Fabio, https://doi.org/10.2312/dh.20253036	skills and to collaborate across diverse disciplines, from social sciences and digital humanities to preservation of cultural heritage, archaeology and beyond. As digital and interactive tools become increasingly integrated into heritage studies, the training in the field is undergoing a significant transformation. The H2IOSC (Heritage and Humanities Italian Open Science Cloud) project has developed an innovative digital training infrastructure aimed at providing access to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) courses and training materials. In this abstract we focus on the H2IOSC training platform, aimed to address the evolving training needs of our disciplinary communities. Created by H2IOSC WP8 (Work Package 8: Training, Engagement and Capacity Building) in collaboration with the E.T.T. S.p.A., it is maintained and hosted by CNR-ILC (Institute of Computational Linguistics "A. Zampelli"), host institution of CLARIN-IT, with the participation of the national nodes of DARIAH, E-RHS, and OPERAS. The platform provides a flexible, customizable learning environment designed to support interdisciplinary education and continuous professional development in the Social Sciences, Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage sectors. The platform features a comprehensive course catalogue containing training courses and modules developed or adapted by the four infrastructures within the H2IOSC project as FAIR training materials, designed for various target knowledge levels, from beginners to advanced learners in heritage and humanities fields. An intuitive dashboard allows users to access materials, track progress and use collaborative tools, including forums, chats, and virtual working groups for networking and communication. The platform incorporates quizzes, simulations, hands-on exercises, and gamification tools, making learning more interactive. Designed for accessibility and inclusivity, it is fully compatible with both desktop and mobile devices, enabling individual	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SHB_Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; SH5_11 Digital humanities; digital approaches to literary studies and philosophy	Chaban A., Pedonese G., Ottaviani R.		
159	Quintero Baibas, D., Maestro-Guijarro, L., Carmona-Quiroga, P. M., Oujja, M., Castillejo, M., Cattaneo, B., Bernardoni, A., Santagostino Barbone, A., Cagnini, A., Striova, J.	Insights into the stratigraphy of gelatin-based emulsion in historical dry plate photographic negatives: A multi-analytical approach	UO15 INO-F1	paper in rivista ISI	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microc.2025.113379	This research investigates historical gelatin dry plate negatives' chemical composition and stratigraphic structure through a comprehensive multi-analytical approach. Our methodology integrated optical and laser-based techniques, with microscopies, including Optical and Scanning Electron Microscopy - Backscattered Electrons (SEM-BSE) and Non-linear Optical Microscopy (NLOM) in its Multi-photon Excitation Fluorescence (MPEF) modality to analyze stratigraphy. MPEF enabled us to overcome the limitations associated with light absorption encountered in other optical techniques. Chemical analysis using Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy (LIBS), Scanning Electron Microscopy - Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (SEM-EDS), and micro-Raman spectroscopy allowed for the classification of negative types based on specific compositional materials, such as synthetic dyes. Our findings contribute to the knowledge of dry plate negative composition and stratigraphy, the aspects that have seldom been investigated. The information retrieved is crucial for understanding the realization and degradation mechanisms of these valuable artifacts, often prone to delamination and flaking, and can inform conservators to better treat historical dry plate photographic negatives.	Publication with H2IOSC logo/or acknowledgement	SHB_Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Quintero Baibas, D.		

160	Quintero Baibas, D., Dimitroulaki, E., Melessanaki, K., Cattaneo, B., Cagnini, A., Bartoli, L., Verga Falzacappa, E., Scopece, P., Pouli, P., Striova, J.	Setting up a methodology for restoring degraded daguerreotypes using UV lasers and atmospheric non-thermal plasma cleaning techniques	UO15 INO-FI	paper in rivista ISI	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2025.06.021	Cleaning daguerreotypes is challenging, and conventional mechanical methods are either too slow or prove impractical, especially for hand-colored plates. In recent decades, advanced techniques, such as laser and plasma cleaning, have been optimized for tarnish removal. However, their effectiveness in removing other substances, such as by-products of previous cleaning treatments, has not been evaluated. To address this issue, we investigated the efficacy of laser and atmospheric non-thermal plasma cleaning on two 19th-century daguerreotypes exhibiting two different degradation conditions: one with typical tarnish, and the other with a complex layer composed of cyanides, calcium carbonate, and an organic compound, likely produced during a previous cleaning attempt. This work reports systematic tests using visible (VIS) and ultraviolet (UV) lasers emitting at four different wavelengths: Nd:YAG (532 nm, 355 nm), KrF excimer (248 nm), and ArF excimer (193 nm). All the lasers operated in the nanosecond regime, except for the KrF excimer laser, which was also tested with femtosecond (500 fs) pulse duration. This is the first report of results using the 248 nm wavelength in both ns and fs regimes for daguerreotype restoration. For comparison, we also applied atmospheric non-thermal plasma cleaning to both types of degradation. The experiments allowed us to assess the advantages and limitations of both techniques, showing that both are suitable depending on the specific surface condition. Additionally, we evaluated a combined cleaning strategy that involved laser and wet cleaning with two different substances—distilled water and an EDTA solution to optimize the cleaning outcomes. To make an informed selection of the parameters and evaluate treatment efficacy, we characterized the chemical composition and morphology of the daguerreotypes and their degradation products before and after cleaning using optical microscopy, <i>i</i> -Raman spectroscopy, and SEM-EDS.	Publication with H2IOSC logo/or acknowledgement	SH8_Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Quintero Baibas, D.
161	Emma Vannini, Silvia Belardi, Irene Lunghi, Alice Dal Fovo, Raffaella Fontana	Exploring the Effects of Support Restoration on Pictorial Layers Through Multi-Resolution 3D Survey	UO15 INO-FI	paper in rivista ISI	Scientific	https://doi.org/10.3390/rs17142487	Three-dimensional (3D) reproduction of artworks has advanced significantly, offering valuable insights for conservation by documenting the objects' conservative state at both macroscopic and microscopic scales. This paper presents the 3D survey of an earthquake-damaged panel painting, whose wooden support suffered severe deformation during a seismic event, posing unique restoration challenges. Our work focuses on quantifying how shape variations in the support—induced during restoration—affect the surface morphology of the pictorial layers. To this end, we conducted measurements before and after support consolidation using two complementary 3D techniques: structured-light projection to generate 3D models of the painting, tracking global shape changes in the panel, and laser-scanning microprofilometry to produce high-resolution models of localized areas, capturing surface morphology, superficial cracks, and pictorial detachments. By processing and cross-comparing 3D point cloud data from both techniques, we quantified shape variations and evaluated their impact on the pictorial layers. This approach demonstrates the utility of multi-scale 3D documentation in guiding complex restoration interventions.	Publication with H2IOSC logo/or acknowledgement	SH8_Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE3_16 Physics for cultural heritage and environment	Alice Dal Fovo
162	Sara Mattana, Alice Dal Fovo, Enrico Baria, Raffaella Fontana, Riccardo Cicchi	Evaluation of safe exposure time for two-photon microscopy imaging of acrylic-painted mock-ups	UO15 INO-FI	paper in rivista ISI	Scientific	https://opscience.lap.org/article/10.1088/2515-7647/ad9598/meta	Nonlinear optical microscopies are widely used in the biological and biomedical fields, as they are non-invasive techniques that permit the safe structural and morphological characterisation of cells and tissues. They are increasingly being used in the Cultural Heritage field because of their ability to overcome some limits of the well-established optical techniques. However, since nonlinear optical microscopies use pulsed laser sources with high peak power, their application in Cultural Heritage raises concerns due to artworks' unique, priceless, and delicate nature. In this paper, we present a new method for evaluating the photo-induced damage when using a near-infrared femtosecond pulsed laser to perform two-photon excited fluorescence imaging of acrylic-painted mock-ups. In particular, we explore herein several irradiation conditions, varying the exposure time and excitation power, in order to provide useful experimental indications for safely imaging acrylic paints with two-photon microscopy.	Publication with H2IOSC logo/or acknowledgement	SH8_Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques; PE2_12 Optics, non-linear optics and nano-optics	Alice Dal Fovo
163	Porcu D., Innocenti S., Striova J., Carretti E., Fontana R.	Mapping Bronze Disease Onset by Multispectral Reflectography	UO 15 INO	paper	Scientific	Mapping Bronze Disease Onset by Multispectral Reflectography / Porcu, Daniela; Innocenti, Silvia; Striova, Jana; Carretti, Emiliano; Fontana, Raffaella. - In: MINERALS. - ISSN 2075-162X. - ELETTRONICO. - 15(2025), pp. 252-0-252.0. [10.3390/min15030252]	The early detection of bronze disease is a significant challenge not only in conservation science but also in various industrial fields that utilize copper alloys (i.e., shipbuilding and construction). Due to the aggressive nature of this corrosion pathway, developing methods for its early detection is pivotal. The presence of copper trihydroxychlorides is the main key indicator of the ongoing autocatalytic process. Commonly used for pigment identification, reflectance imaging spectroscopy (RIS) or fiber optics reflectance spectroscopy (FORS) was recently employed for mapping atacamite distribution in extended bronze corrosion patinas. In this work, we detected the onset of bronze disease using visible-near-infrared (VIS-NIR) multispectral reflectography, which allowed for disclosing features that were poorly detectable to the naked eye. The image cube was analyzed using the spectral correlation mapper (SCM) algorithm to map the distribution of copper trihydroxychlorides. FORS and Raman spectroscopy were employed to characterize the patina composition and validate RIS data. A set of bronze samples, representative of Florentine Renaissance workshops, was specifically realized for the present study and artificially aged at different corrosion stages.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH8_Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Innocenti S.
164	Striova, S Innocenti, A Ingrassia, M Bertaso, S	Spectroscopic Investigations of a Vandalized Contemporary Acrylic Painting on Canvas. Using Model Paintings and Chemometrics	UO 15 INO	paper	Scientific	Spectroscopic Investigations of a Vandalized Contemporary Acrylic Painting on Canvas. Using Model Paintings and Chemometrics	Sequentially shifted excitation (SSE) Raman results on artificially aged acrylic-based model paints and Tela (1973) canvas painting by Griffa suggest the surface enrichment in surfactant. Vandalic trait, with an orange felt-tip pen, consists of an acrylic binder and azo-dyes. Spectral markers, FTIR (1731 cm ⁻¹), and Raman (1600, 1502 cm ⁻¹), have been identified to support the monitoring of the vandalic trait removal.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH8_Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Innocenti S.
165	Cuzman, O.A., Raio A., Galeotti M., Striova J., Chaban A., Innocenti S., Penoni S., De Luca F., Cantini B., Petrocchi D.,	Pink discoloration due to pigmented Archaea on the walls of the so-called Michelangelo's "secret room" (Medici Chapel, Florence, Italy)	UO 15 INO	paper	Scientific	Cuzman O. A., Raio A., Galeotti M., Striova J., Chaban A., Innocenti S., Penoni S., De Luca F., Cantini B., Petrocchi D., van den Heuvel, H., Draxler, C., Frontini, F., Pedonese, G., & van der Lek, I. (2025, settembre 23). Introduction alla Gestione dei Dati Orali. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17183052	Pink discolorations are often observed on heritage buildings mainly in areas affected by salt weathering, where the development of halotolerant and halophilic microorganisms is favored. Part of these extremophilic microorganisms contains carotenoids, reason for which their colonization becomes visible by naked eye on large surfaces. This work investigates the pink alteration of the walls with drawings attributed to Michelangelo, located in the basement room of the Medici Chapel (Florence, Italy). The results of in-depth multidisciplinary investigations are discussed in the context of a thorough literature review on pink alterations of heritage buildings. For the first time, we combined culture-based approaches with metagenomic analyses that revealed the pink pigmented archaea <i>Halalkalicoccus</i> sp. as dominant, pointing their role in the pink discoloration present on the wall. Raman spectroscopy was exploited for the characterization of the biogenic pigments and Fourier Transform infrared spectroscopy and scanning electron microscopy to analyze the salt formations present on the walls.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH8_Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage; PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	Chaban A.
166	van den Heuvel, H., Draxler, C., Frontini, F., Pedonese, G., & van der Lek, I.	Introduzione alla Gestione dei Dati Orali	UO 08 ILC	Training material	Educational	van den Heuvel, H., Draxler, C., Frontini, F., Pedonese, G., & van der Lek, I. (2025, settembre 23). Introduzione alla Gestione dei Dati Orali. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17183052	Il corso affronta le tematiche legate alla gestione dei dati linguistici orali. Dopo un'introduzione generale	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches	Pedonese, G.
167	van der Lek, I., Fišer, D., Frontini, F., & Pedonese	Introduzione ai Dati Linguistici: Standard e Archivi Digitali.	UO 08 ILC	Training material	Educational	van der Lek, I., Fišer, D., Frontini, F., & Pedonese, G. (2024, agosto 31). Introduzione ai Dati Linguistici: Standard e Archivi Digitali. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13911935	Il corso "Introduzione ai Dati Linguistici: Standard e Archivi Digitali" introduce gli insegnanti e gli studenti all'uso degli archivi digitali di dati della ricerca e al loro ruolo nel ciclo di vita dei dati linguistici nel contesto degli principi FAIR e delle buone pratiche della Scienza Aperta. I materiali del corso sono suddivisi in unità e sono intesi come contenuti didattici per i docenti che insegnano a livello di laurea triennale o laurea magistrale, che sono invitati a sfogliare i materiali, esportarli per l'uso nel Learning Management System della loro istituzione e adattarli ai propri scopi come ritengono opportuno.	Publications with H2IOSC logo ai SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital ap	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches	Pedonese, G.
168	Khan, A. F., Pedonese, G., Mallia, M., Frontini, F., Quochi, V., & Squadrito, E. (2024, luglio 5).	Linguistic Linked Open Data for Humanists	UO 08 ILC	Training material	Educational	Khan, A. F., Pedonese, G., Mallia, M., Frontini, F., Quochi, V., & Squadrito, E. (2024, luglio 5). Linguistic Linked Open Data for Humanists. Lisbon Summer School in Linguistics, Lisbon. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13897931	Questo corso traduce in italiano e aggiorna i materiali di:	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH5_11 Digital humanities; computational and digital ap	Pedonese, G. Mallia, M.
169	Melaccio D., Boschetti F., Monachini M.	Interfacing CLARIN with H2IOSC: Metadata Interoperability through Ontology-based Mediation	UO 08 ILC	Paper	Scientific	Melaccio D., Boschetti F., Monachini M. (2025): Interfacing CLARIN with H2IOSC: Metadata Interoperability through Ontology-based Mediation, in CLARIN Annual Conference Proceedings, 2025, ISSN 2773-2177, Grisot & Kontino eds., Vienna.	We present an ontology-based approach for integrating CLARIN language resources into the H2IOSC semantic framework, promoting interoperability across the Social Sciences and Humanities. Building on CMDI and the CLARIN Concept Registry, our work extends CMD2RDF beyond syntactic conversion to formal semantic integration. CMDI metadata is mapped to CIDOC CRM and SSHOCro, with extensions for CLARIN-specific needs.	Publications with H2IOSC logo and/or acknowledgement	SH4_9 Theoretical linguistics; computational linguistics	Melaccio D.

Annex 3 – List of H2IOSC training activities carried out and foreseen

UO N. & Acronym	RI	Other UO Involved (if any)	Organized by	Date	Venue	Type of activities (workshop, webinar, course, etc.)	Internal or external training	Target	Number of participants	Number of training hours	Title	Description	Link
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH		DARIAH.IT	12/01/2023	In person & online	Florence	Workshop	Accademia, Ricercatori	20		I giovedì di DARIAH	Presentazione del progetto RESTORE, prossime proposte di sviluppo.	
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH		DARIAH.IT	09/02/2023	In person & online	Florence	Workshop	Accademia, Ricercatori	20		I giovedì di DARIAH	Presentazione progetti di ricerca in ambito "Heritage Science" (SSHOC, iPERION-HS). Introduzione al nuovo sistema per l'interrogazione dei corpora OVI.	
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH		DARIAH.IT	02/03/2023	In person & online	Florence	Workshop	Accademia, Ricercatori	20		I giovedì di DARIAH	Presentazione del progetto PNRH H2IOSC (WP1-WP).	
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH		DARIAH.IT	06/04/2023	In person & online	Florence	Workshop	Accademia, Ricercatori	20		I giovedì di DARIAH	Presentazione dello stato di avanzamento dei lavori per il nuovo sistema per l'interrogazione dei corpora OVI.	
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH		DARIAH.IT	04/05/2023	In person & online	Florence	Workshop	Accademia, Ricercatori	20		I giovedì di DARIAH	Presentazione della fine dei lavori sul nuovo sistema per l'interrogazione dei corpora OVI: motore di ricerca, output dei risultati dei risultati di ricerca sul prototipo dell'interfaccia di visualizzazione.	
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN			12-13/06/23	In person	Modena, Italy	Summer school				Summer School Digital Humanities and Digital Communication: AI and (new) literacies	https://www.clarin-it.it/sites/default/files/documents/UniMoRe_Summer-School-in-Digital-Humanities-2023_Locandina.pdf	
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR-ILC and Unive-DSU-VeDPH under the aegis of DiPText-KC and CLARIN-IT.	21-22/09/2023 3 19-20/10/2023	In person & online	Ca' Foscari University of Venice	Training School	PhD students	8	12	Digital Text Processing 2023	1) Python-Based Processing of Plain Text Documents 2) Processing of XML Documents	https://diptext-kc.clarin-it.it/digital-text-processing-2023/
OU15 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		CNR-INO (Firenze, Italia), University of Ljubljana (Slovenia)	26/10/2023	Online		Webinar	External	Researchers, practitioners, PhD, Master and Bachelor students specialized or interested in different topics of heritage science	82	1	Optical Coherence Tomography for examination of artworks	Introduction to the method and instruments of Optical Coherence Tomography, explaining how the OCT technique may be used to examine the structure of various artworks, trace former conservation attempts, and help monitor some restoration procedures.
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR-ILC and Unive-DSU-VeDPH under the aegis of DiPText-KC and CLARIN-IT	7-11-13/12/23	In person & online	Ca' Foscari University of Venice	Training School	PhD students	8	9	Allographic Texts Processing 2023	1) String manipulation 2) Transcoding and transliteration 3) Graphemic and phonemic analysis	https://diptext-kc.clarin-it.it/allographic-texts-processing-2023/
OU15 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		CNR-INO (Firenze, Italia), University of Ljubljana (Slovenia)	30/11/2023	Online		Webinar	External	Researchers, practitioners, PhD, Master and Bachelor students specialized or interested in different topics of heritage science	128	1	AI in the Loop: Enhancing Cultural Property Protection Activities through Intelligent Methods	The lecture about Artificial Intelligence (AI) – powered methods, employed to monitor online platforms, enabling the identification, tracking, and reporting of illegal sales and transactions, ensuring the safety and preservation of invaluable cultural assets for future generations
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH		DARIAH.IT	07/12/2023	In person & online	Florence	Workshop	Accademia, Ricercatori	30		I giovedì di DARIAH	Ultimo incontro anno 2023, oltre a presentare una sintesi dei risultati più promettenti raggiunti nei mesi scorsi, presentazione del programma scientifico e tecnico per il 2024 sui progetti PNRH H2IOSC e CHANGES.	
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN			07/12/2023 11/12/2023 13/12/2023	In person & online	Venezia	Training School	Students and researchers			Allographic Texts Processing 2023		https://diptext-kc.clarin-it.it/allographic-texts-processing-2023/
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		Realized under the patronage of CNR-ILC, Unive-DSU-VeDPH, WikiMedia, CLARIN-IT, DiPText-KC and H2IOSC	12/12/2023	-	-	Tutorial				Introduction to Wikidata and the importation of Bibliographic Elements from Zotero	https://diptext-kc.clarin-it.it/knowledge/knowledge-pills/introduction-to-wikidata-and-the-importation-of-bibliographic-elements-from-zotero/	
OU15 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		CNR-INO (Firenze, Italia), University of Ljubljana (Slovenia)	15/12/2023	Online		Webinar	External	Researchers, practitioners, PhD, Master and Bachelor students specialized or interested in different topics of heritage science	58	1	Chronological Tools: Dating Human Evolutionary History	General introduction to the most advanced state-of-the-art techniques, including Optically Stimulated Luminescence (OSL), Electron Spin Resonance (ESR), and in detail Uranium-Thorium (U-Th) dating; the whole process from sample collection, and methodological considerations, to the associated instrumental analyses
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH		DARIAH.IT	11/01/2024	In person & online	Florence	Workshop	Accademia, Ricercatori	25		I giovedì di H2IOSC	Un anno del progetto H2IOSC + Lemmatizzazione semiautomatica dell'italiano antico (relatori: Emiliano Degl'Innocenti, Lucia Francalanci, Francesco Coradeschi)	
OU13 - IAC-NA	E-RIHS			27/28/29 maggio 2025 3/4/5 giugno 2025	In person & online	IAC Rome	Course	Ricercatori arruolati sul progetto o coinvolti in H2IOSC e ai potenziali interessati	12		Sviluppo e gestione di sistemi modellistici	Lo scopo del corso è fornire ai ricercatori gli strumenti per ideare l'architettura e sviluppare l'implementazione software di sistemi a servizio sia della modellistica che dell'utente finale. Nel corso verranno utilizzati esempi basati sul linguaggio C#, ma i concetti base potranno essere declinati in qualsiasi altro linguaggio di programmazione.	
OU15 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		CNR-INO (Firenze, Italia), University of Ljubljana (Slovenia)	25/01/2024	Online		Webinar	External	Researchers, practitioners, PhD, Master and Bachelor students specialized or interested in different topics of heritage science	53	1	Open and FAIR Science with a case study from the FAIR Phyloliths project	Main practices of open science and why it is important for all researcher to start moving towards more open working in archaeology; the benefits of practising open science, barriers to overcome; a case study about the FAIR Phyloliths project – a project that aimed to assess phylolith data in terms of the FAIR data principles and has formed an open community to tackle implementation of open science practices
OU15 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		CNR-INO (Firenze, Italia)	25-26/01/2024	In person & online		Workshop / working group meeting	External	Research and teaching staff involved in heritage science education; PhD, Master and Bachelor students, pursuing a degree in various disciplines of heritage science	99	9	Research Infrastructures and heritage science career paths	Presentations on the topic of current provision of heritage science education, the skills necessary for employment in different heritage science sectors and employers, as well as the typical heritage science career paths
OU15 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		ONECA	05-07/02/2024	Online		Course, in-kind (self-funded) autonomous professional update by temporary H2IOSC staff	Researchers and programmers	20		Introduction to Python programming	This course aims to introduce the student to the key topics of the language in order to give a solid basis for further investigations that will be required according to the specific field of application. The exposition of the topics uses	Giornata 1: Giornata introduttiva sugli aspetti tecnico-legali relativi alla brevettabilità. Giornata 2: Brevettabilità del software con riferimento alle invenzioni che utilizzano le IA. Giornata 3: Protezione internazionale e prova pratica con ricerca nella letteratura brevettuale.
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH		DARIAH.IT	08/02/2024	In person & online	Florence	Workshop	Accademia, Ricercatori	30		I giovedì di H2IOSC	Incontro tra i Ricercatori OVI e i dottorandi di FROID. Definizione del Digital Philology Hub (relatori: Emiliano Degl'Innocenti e Lino Leonardi)	
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		Venice Centre of Digital and Public Humanities of the Department of Humanities of the Ca' Foscari University of Venice (Unive-DSU VeDPH) and the University of Saskatchewan (Canada) under the patronage of CLARIN-IT, DiPText-KC, CNR-ILC, the PNRH IR H2IOSC project and AIUCD.	19-20/02/24	In person & online	Ca' Foscari University of Venice, DSU, VeDPH	Training course	MA Students and PhD students	10	11	Lessons on Digital Ecoties	The opening and closing lessons by Franz Fischer (Unive-DSU VeDPH Director DiPText-KC) and Federico Boschetti (CNR-ILC CoPhLab Leader Unive-DSU VeDPH DiPText-KC CLARIN-IT H2IOSC). 1) Introduction to Digital Scientific Editions (DSE/ESD). 2) Two case studies: the digital editions of Dante's "Commedia" and Boccaccio's "Teseida".	https://www.clarin-it.it/sites/default/files/documents/Unive-DSU-VeDPH_Lezioni-di-Ecologia-Digitale_19-20.02.2024_Locandina.pdf
OU15 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		CNR-INO (Firenze, Italia), University of Ljubljana (Slovenia)	22/02/2024	Online		Webinar	External	Researchers, practitioners, PhD, Master and Bachelor students specialized or interested in different topics of heritage science	120	1	Portable NMR for structural diagnostic in heritage science	General introduction to nondestructive methods of analysis, focusing on portable NMR technique. The lecture was about how portable NMR works and how the instrument is operated will be explained, and its use in analyzing objects of cultural heritage was illustrated in three case studies: 1) Comparative investigation of the mortar-layer stratigraphy of Roman frescoes; 2) the preservation state of master violins; and 3) the effect of solvent in varnish removal of easel paintings.
OU12 - ISPC-RM	E-RIHS		DTC Lazio	24/02/2024	In person & online	Florence	Workshop	Generic		2	NUOVI ORIZZONTI DELLA VALORIZZAZIONE Tra tecnologie digitali, territori e comunità	General introduction to generative AI tools and services, and their integration with the WebXR application "Imagine" (CNR ISPC) developed on top of ATON framework (H2IOSC task 6.3) on display in TourismA 2024	
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH		DARIAH.IT	05/03/2024	Online		Workshop	Accademia, Ricercatori	7		Seminario sulla collazione semi-automatica	Incontro tra i Ricercatori OVI e i dottorandi di FROID. Definizione del Digital Philology Hub - modulo Collazione semi-automatica	
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR-ILC	08/03/2024	Online		Webinar	Train the trainers event, individual webinar organised to train a researcher of the University of Ferrara in order to implement CLARIN resources and services in his BA and MA courses (Cdt. Operatore del Turismo Culturale)	1	2	Formazione iniziale UniFe	General introduction to the use of CLARIN core services for trainers; focus on resources for students of translation studies (English to Italian)	
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH		DARIAH.IT	11/03/2024	Online		Workshop	Accademia, Ricercatori	8		Seminario su Tipologia e codifica	Incontro tra i Ricercatori OVI e i dottorandi di FROID. Definizione del Digital Philology Hub - modulo Tipologia e Codifica	
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH		DARIAH.IT	11/03/2024	Online		Workshop	Accademia, Ricercatori	8		Seminario su HTR	Incontro tra i Ricercatori OVI e i dottorandi di FROID. Definizione del Digital Philology Hub - modulo HTR	
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH		DARIAH.IT	12/03/2024	In person	Florence	Workshop	Accademia, Ricercatori	15		Seminario congiunto su moduli: Lemmatizzazione, Collazione, HTR	Incontro tra i Ricercatori OVI e i dottorandi di FROID. Definizione del Digital Philology Hub - modulo Lemmatizzazione semi-automatica e Glossario, modulo Collazione semi-automatica e modulo HTR	
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH		DARIAH.IT	12/03/2024	In person & online	Florence	Workshop	Accademia, Ricercatori	30		Seminario congiunto tra i Ricercatori OVI e i dottorandi di FROID	Incontro di aggiornamento tra i Ricercatori OVI e i dottorandi di FROID sullo stato dell'arte del Digital Philology Hub	
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		Department of Asian and North African Studies of the Ca' Foscari University of Venice under the patronage of DiPText-KC, CLARIN-IT and H2IOSC	12-13/03/24	In person & online	Ca' Foscari University of Venice, DSAM	Workshop	Post-doc fellows, PhD students, BA and MA students who wish to acquire cutting-edge skills and methodologies for data collection, analysis and interpretation.	20	11	A digital turn in the Humanities: Methodologies and issues	Focus on the use of digital tools for advanced research in the Humanities	https://diptext-kc.clarin-it.it/workshop-on-digital-humanities/
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH		DARIAH.IT	14/03/2024	In person & online	Florence	Workshop	Accademia, Ricercatori	26		I giovedì di H2IOSC	Gestione di repertori filologici e di immagini (relatore: Gennaro Ferrante)	
OU8 - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR-ILC	20/03/2024	Online		Webinar	Project team formation: researchers, university professors and doctoral students involved in the ITSEER project	28	2	CLARIN per le Lingue Antiche	General introduction to the CLARIN infrastructure, its national consortium CLARIN-IT and the H2IOSC project; focus on how to access CLARIN resources, how to use the core service to discover, annotate and analyse texts in Ancient Greek, Latin and Hebrew	Note: the webinar involves the Research Infrastructure RESILIENCE
OU1 - OVI-FI	DARIAH		DARIAH.IT	21/03/2024	In person & online	Florence	Workshop	Accademia, Ricercatori	12		Seminario sulla lemmatizzazione semi-automatica dell'italiano antico	Seminario sulla lemmatizzazione semi-automatica dell'italiano antico con partecipazione di ricercatori OVI e dottorandi FROID	

OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		Educatando Statale Agli Angeli	22/03/2024	Online		Corso aggiornamento			Formazione agli studenti del corso di Text Encoding, laurea triennale Informatica Umanistica	20	2	Corso di aggiornamento sulle Digital Humanities	General introduction to the CLARIN infrastructure, its national consortium CLARIN-IT and the H2IOSC project; focus on how to access CLARIN resources, how to use the core service to discover, annotate and analyse texts	https://diptext-ke.clarin-it.it/updating-course-on-digital-humanities/
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR-ILC, Università di Pisa	27/03/2024	In person		Lezione						Introduzione ai Core Services		
OUI5 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		CNR-INO (Firenze, Italia), University of Ljubljana (Slovenia)	18/04/2024	Online		Webinar	External		Researchers, practitioners, PhD, Master and Bachelor students specialized or interested in different topics of heritage science	125	1	Digitalization of cultural heritage: HBIM and OpenBIM	Digitalization procedures for the efficient management, preservation, and enhancement of cultural heritage through the use of advanced technologies such as Heritage Building Information Modeling (HBIM). This is complemented by the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI), scan-to-BIM technologies, virtual and augmented reality (VR/AR) representations, holograms, and massive data analysis, which enable detailed and accurate documentation and analysis of cultural heritage sites.	
OUI2 - ISPC-RM	E-RIHS		DHDK master (Bologna University)	18/04/2024	In person & online	Bologna	Course			Researchers, students part of DHDK (Digital Humanities and Digital Knowledge) master at Bologna University		3	Open-source Web3D/WebXR applications and 3D standards for Cultural Heritage: ATON framework	Current state of the art related to Web3D/WebXR technologies and interoperable open standards for online 3D presentation targeting Cultural Heritage. Second part of the course is focused on practical hands-on to use ATON framework (H2IOSC task 6.3) with introduction to new plug&play model evolved under H2IOSC	
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR-ILC	15/04/2024	Online		Webinar			Trainees of the Department	2	2	Formazione tirocinanti ILC	Introduzione ai principi FAIR, Open Science e ai servizi CLARIN funzionali ai compiti di traduzione, metadattazione e in generale alla gestione dei materiali di training come oggetti digitali FAIR coerenti con il lavoro dei tirocinanti entro l'attività 8.2 del progetto H2IOSC	
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR-ILC	02/05/2024	Online		Webinar / workshop	External		Studenti del Master di secondo livello InfoTest dell'Università di Siena	15	6	CLARIN per la ricerca linguistica: servizi infrastrutturali per l'analisi del testo	Workshop di introduzione ai servizi CLARIN e approfondimento laboratoriale sulle pratiche di NLP: lavoro con Risorse XML/TEI mediante XPath, XSLT, XQuery	
OUI6 - ISPF-NA	OPERAS		CNR-ISPF NAPOLI	08/05/2024	In person & online	Napoli	Workshop / working group meeting			Ricercatori arruolati sul progetto o coinvolti in H2IOSC e ai potenziali interessati				Workshop finalizzato ad individuare gli aspetti funzionali della piattaforma sviluppata per ospitare edizione critica	
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR-ILC e Università di Ferrara	09/05/2024	In person	Ferrara	Course	External		Studenti del corso di Lingua Inglese per Lettere, Arti e archeologia (CdL triennale) dell'Università di Ferrara	10	2	Risorse Linguistiche in CLARIN: Deposito, Scoperta ed Elaborazione attraverso i Core Services	Introduzione ai principi FAIR e Open Science; Deposito, Scoperta ed Elaborazione dati attraverso i core services di CLARIN	
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR-ILC e Università di Ferrara	10/05/2024	In person	Ferrara	Course	External		Studenti del corso di Lingua Inglese per il Turismo (CdL triennale) dell'Università di Ferrara	10	2	Risorse Linguistiche in CLARIN: Deposito, Scoperta ed Elaborazione	Introduzione ai principi FAIR e Open Science; Deposito, Scoperta ed Elaborazione dati attraverso i core services di CLARIN	
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR-ILC	13/05/2024	Online		Webinar	External		Studenti e ricercatori dell'Università di Napoli l'Oriente	25	2	CLARIN per la gestione FAIR dei dati linguistici: Introduzione ai Core Services e ai vocabolari in Skosmos	Introduzione alla struttura di CLARIN ERIC e del consorzio nazionale CLARIN-IT e del progetto H2IOSC. Approfondimento dei concetti Open Science e dei principi FAIR con dimostrazione della loro realizzazione in CLARIN con esempi di ricerche integrate dal Virtual Language Observatory, Language Resource Switchboard, Federated Content Search e Virtual Collection Registry. Approfondimento tecnico sul funzionamento dei vocabolari controllati in Skosmos e loro modalità di consultazione	
OUI5 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		CNR-INO (Firenze, Italia), University of Ljubljana (Slovenia)	23/05/2024	Online		Webinar	External		Researchers, practitioners, PhD, Master and Bachelor students specialized or interested in different topics of heritage science	145	1	Electrochemical techniques for studying metal corrosion on heritage objects	The lecture about fundamentals of the technique and the applications to cultural heritage will be presented, with special focus on the specific technique of Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) and its application for non-destructive in-situ studies.	
OUI5 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		Fondazione Scuola Beni Attività Culturali, Ministero della Cultura (MIC)	1/06/2024-5/07/2024	Online		Corso (partecipazione dello staff H2IOSC)	Internal		H2IOSC staff (TD PNRR)	1	4	Il Ciclo di vita degli oggetti digitali	On-demand course focused on the digitization of cultural heritage from the planning of a campaign to data management.	
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR-ILC e Università di Pisa	03/06/2024	In person & online	Pisa	Webinar / workshop	External		Studenti della Summer School Digital Tools for Humanists del LabCD dell'Università di Pisa	40	4	CLARIN for FAIR linguistic data: Working with XML/TEI resources through XPath, XSLT, XQuery	Illustrazione dei principali concetti di Open Science e dei principi FAIR, con esempio di Data Management Plan. Presentazione della struttura di CLARIN ERIC, del consorzio CLARIN-IT e del progetto H2IOSC. Esempificazione dei principi FAIR applicati in CLARIN attraverso l'uso dei core services. Sessione laboratoriale con casi di studio per il trattamento di risorse TEI attraverso XPath, XSLT, XQuery	
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR-ILC, progetto ITSERR (RESILIENCE)	06/06/2024	Online		Webinar	External		Evento train the trainers con due dei ricercatori per concordare un tutorial su Weblight da presentare al resto del team di progetto ITSERR (IR di riferimento: RESILIENCE). Dopo una mezz'ora di domande e risposte volte a capire i bisogni formativi dei docenti e a fornire loro materiale utile, il tutorial è stato registrato per essere riprodotto nelle giornate di formazione del 10 e 11 giugno.	2	2	Le funzionalità del servizio CLARIN Weblight	Dimostrazione pratica dell'uso di strumenti NLP interoperabili attraverso il servizio CLARIN Weblight: uso di testi di prova e dimostrazione dell'elaborazione di un testo in arabo fornito dai richiedenti	
OUI5 - INO-FI	E-RIHS	OU00 (Roma e Napoli)	Kinetikon	06/06/2024-17/06/2024	Online		Corso	Internal		H2IOSC staff (TD PNRR)	3	16	Database MySQL - CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE (CNR Napoli)		
OUI5 - INO-FI	E-RIHS	OU00 (Roma e Napoli)	Kinetikon	06/06/2024-17/06/2024	Online		Corso (partecipazione dello staff H2IOSC)	Internal		H2IOSC staff (TD PNRR)	3	16	Database MySQL - CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE (CNR Napoli)		
OUI5 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		CLARIN	14/06/2024	Online		Webinar (partecipazione dello staff H2IOSC)	External		Educators, researchers, and research infrastructure professionals	1		CLARIN Café - Translation Technologies & Workflows for SSH Researchers	This CLARIN Café is designed to share knowledge and expertise on translation technologies from a train-the-trainer perspective. It aims to provide an overview of available open educational resources that can be used in translation technology teaching and learning. After an introduction to translation and translation technology, the invited speakers will share their experience with teaching data literacy in the context of (machine) translation based on the data lifecycle of a typical (machine) translation project, including data context, planning, collection, production, evaluation, and use. The presentations will also include references to CLARIN language resources and technologies which can be used in the translation classroom.	
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR-ILC	20/06/2024	Online		Workshop	External		Ricercatori e dottorandi del Laboratorio Sperimentale, Dipartimento di Lingue e Culture Moderne dell'Università di Bologna	10	2	CLARIN per la gestione FAIR dei dati linguistici	Dimostrazione dei principali servizi CLARIN e dell'infrastruttura tecnica che rende possibile l'interoperabilità dei dati. Presentazione del progetto ParlaMint e delle possibilità di interrogazione su diverse interfacce web. Interrogazione del corpus tramite Corpus Query Language su SketchEngine ed ampliamento della ricerca tramite ulteriori concordancers che supportano lo stesso linguaggio di interrogazione attraverso la Federated Content Search e le CLARIN Resource Families.	
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR-ILC, progetto ITSERR (RESILIENCE)	21/06/2024	Online		Workshop	External		Il workshop è stato calibrato sulle necessità dei ricercatori del progetto ITSERR, ma è stato aperto anche al resto della comunità, in particolare al resto della compagine H2IOSC e ad altri enti e associazioni interessati, come INDIRE	10	2	Utilizzare i Voyant Tools - Tutorial a cura di Rachele Sprugnoli	Tutorial tenuto da Rachele Sprugnoli, parte della CLARIN Trainers' Network. Prima introduzione al distant reading e dimostrazione delle funzionalità del tool tramite testi esemplificativi in italiano. Parte laboratoriale in cui i partecipanti hanno provato ad utilizzare i tool su testi di loro interesse.	
OUI5 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		CNR-INO (Firenze, Italia), University of Ljubljana (Slovenia)	27/06/2024	Online		Webinar	External		Researchers, practitioners, PhD, Master and Bachelor students specialized or interested in different topics of heritage science	67	1	The illusion of non-destructive analysis in Palaeoanthropology. To what extent high resolution mCT scanning of hominin fossils remains may impact ESR and Radiocarbon dating results?	The lecture about limitations of scientific analysis on the systematic mCT scanning of human fossils should not be regarded as a non-destructive technique, but may instead significantly impact fossil preservation and associated dating results.	
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR - ILC, CLUJL - Centro Linguistica da Universidade NOVA de Lisboa	1-5/07/2024	In person		Corso	External		Dottorandi e ricercatori di provenienza europea ed extraeuropea interessati all'applicazione del Linked Open Data ai loro progetti di ricerca in ambito umanistico.	25	15	Linguistic Linked Open Data for humanists	Having achieved popularity as a way of publishing and accessing data in different fields of the sciences and for sharing large encyclopaedic datasets such as DBpedia (derived from Wikipedia), linked data is becoming more and more popular in different areas of the humanities. In this course we will present a comprehensive introduction to the creation, publication, and use of linked open data for anyone who wants to work with linguistic datasets – such as lexicons and corpora – and especially for those who come from a linguistic or humanist background. We will look at the basics of linked data and the Semantic Web and introduce the various different standards technologies that make up the Semantic Web stack before focusing on the particular case of linked data language resources. During the course we will study the most important tools, vocabularies, and resources available in the Semantic Web and provide hands-on training for the creation and querying of linguistic linked data. We will look at how Semantic Web technologies can contribute to the creation of FAIR language resources as well as how to publish your resource on the linked open data cloud. We will also show how the Semantic Web query language SPARQL can be a powerful tool for data exploration.	
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR - ILC	10/07/2024	Online		Corso	External		Ricercatori e dottorandi che lavorano al progetto Corpus SIM (Senectus Ipsa Morbus) – Spontaneous speech in healthy ageing coordinato dalla prof.ssa Dovetto	15	4	CLARIN per la gestione FAIR delle risorse linguistiche: introduzione ai servizi di base	Il modulo ha compreso una panoramica dei servizi essenziali e una parte interattiva dedicata alle risorse CLARIN contenenti dati linguistici orali.	
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR - ILC	16/09/2024	In person & online		Corso	External		Ricercatori e dottorandi che lavorano al progetto Corpus SIM (Senectus Ipsa Morbus) – Spontaneous speech in healthy ageing coordinato dalla prof.ssa Dovetto	25	4	Introduzione alla Gestione dei Dati Orali	In questa prima parte, il modulo ha approfondito le questioni etiche e legali relative alla gestione di dati linguistici orali. Dopo una lezione frontale da parte di uno dei membri della CLARIN Trainers' Network, i partecipanti sono stati guidati attraverso l'analisi di un caso d'uso interattivo, tagliato sulle loro esigenze di progetto.	
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR - ILC	17/09/2024	In person & online		Corso	External		Ricercatori e dottorandi che lavorano al progetto Corpus SIM (Senectus Ipsa Morbus) – Spontaneous speech in healthy ageing coordinato dalla prof.ssa Dovetto	25	4	Introduzione alla Gestione dei Dati Orali	La seconda parte del modulo sulla gestione dei dati orali ha previsto un gioco di ruolo interattivo durante il quale i partecipanti hanno simulato le applicazioni del GDPR secondo diversi possibili scenari.	
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR - ILC	17/09/2024	In person & online		Corso	External		Ricercatori e dottorandi che lavorano al progetto Corpus SIM (Senectus Ipsa Morbus) – Spontaneous speech in healthy ageing coordinato dalla prof.ssa Dovetto	25	4	Introduzione alla Gestione dei Dati Orali	Questo modulo ha affrontato le questioni pratiche riguardanti l'acquisizione di tracce audio funzionali alla trascrizione automatica. Si è poi proseguito proponendo esempi di software utili per la trascrizione automatica, dimostrando le loro applicazioni su tracce d'esempio.	
OUI5 - INO-FI	E-RIHS	OU00 (Roma e Napoli)	Kinetikon	19/09/2024-03/10/2024	Online		Webinar / workshop (partecipazione dello staff H2IOSC)	External		H2IOSC staff (TD PNRR)	2		Javascript	Corso base di Javascript	
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR - ILC	20/09/2024 - 26/09/2024	Online		Modulo didattico	Internal		Compagine di progetto H2IOSC	15	8	Skills4EOSC course on FAIR-by-Design methodology for the CLARIN Community	The training introduces a structured approach to embedding FAIR principles into the instructional design process, ensuring that learning materials are not only well-designed but also discoverable, accessible, and reusable by a broader audience. Participants will explore various stages of the FAIR-by-Design workflow, from preparation and design to publication and continuous improvement.	
OUB - ILC-PI	All RI		CNR - ILC	25/09/2024	Online		Lezione	Internal		Compagine di progetto H2IOSC	21	2	H2IOSC Café - Presenting CLARIN ERIC	The H2IOSC project is promoting a series of training events: H2IOSC Café. These sessions are designed to provide cross-training, collaboration and knowledge sharing between all research infrastructures involved in the project: CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RIHS and OPERAS. The first event will focus on CLARIN ERIC, where CLARIN will present its activities to the other infrastructures involved in the project. The event will be held online in Italian and English.	
OUI5 - INO-FI	E-RIHS	OU00 (Roma e Napoli)	Kinetikon	5/09/2024-27/09/2024	Online		Webinar / workshop (partecipazione dello staff H2IOSC)	External		H2IOSC staff (TD PNRR)	4		Data Science	Corso di Data science	
OUI5 - INO-FI	E-RIHS	OU00 (Roma e Napoli)	Kinetikon	04/10/2024-22/10/2024	Online		Webinar / workshop (partecipazione dello staff H2IOSC)	External		H2IOSC staff (TD PNRR)	4		Data Visualization	Corso di Data Visualization	
OUI5 - INO-FI	E-RIHS	OU00 (Roma e Napoli)	Kinetikon	07/10/2024-17/10/2024	Online		Webinar / workshop (partecipazione dello staff H2IOSC)	External		H2IOSC staff (TD PNRR)	2		Rete neurali	Corso di base di Rete Neurali	
OUI3 - IAC-NA	DARIAH			06/11/2024 13/11/2024 20/11/2024	In person	IAC Rome	Course			Ricercatori arruolati sul progetto o coinvolti in H2IOSC e ai potenziali interessati	8		Corso sul trasferimento tecnologico con particolare riguardo alla tematica della tutela brevettuale	Giornata 1: Giornata introduttiva sugli aspetti tecnico-legali relativi alla brevetazione. Giornata 2: Brevettabilità del software con riferimento alle invenzioni che utilizzano le IA. Giornata 3: Protezione internazionale e prova pratica con ricerca nella letteratura brevettuale.	
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR - ILC, Università di Ferrara	14/11/2024	In person	Università di Ferrara	Lezione	External		Studenti di laurea triennale in Lingua e Traduzione Inglese all'Università di Ferrara	20	2	Risorse e Tecnologie Linguistiche per la Traduzione	Il caso di CLARIN: deposito, scoperta ed elaborazione dei dati linguistici attraverso i servizi di base. Esercitazione pratica sul VLO e su Matecat.	
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR-ILC	11/11/2024	Online		Webinar	Internal		Trainees of the Department	1	2	Formazione tirocinanti ILC	Introduzione ai principi FAIR, Open Science e ai servizi CLARIN funzionali ai compiti di traduzione, metadattazione e in generale alla gestione dei materiali di training come oggetti digitali FAIR coerenti con il lavoro dei tirocinanti entro l'attività 8.2 del progetto H2IOSC	

OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR - ILC, Università di Ferrara	14/11/2024 - 15/11/2024	In person	Università di Ferrara	Lezione	External	Studenti di laurea magistrale in Lingua e Traduzione Inglese dell'Università di Ferrara	15	4	Risorse Linguistiche, principi FAIR e Linked Open Data	Fondamenti di Linked Open Data e tour del Linguistic Linked Open Data Cloud
OUI5 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		CNR-INO, CNR-SPC	04/12/2024-18/12/2024	Online		Webinar / workshop (partecipazione dello staff H2IOSC)	Internal	H2IOSC staff (TD PNRR)	40	9	Training for Service Managers	Training for Service Managers to fill the Services offered by the E-RIHS community in the new CoS
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR-ILC	17/01/2025	Online		Corso	External	Team del progetto PRIN Roads to Oral Archives Development and Sustainability	10	5	Progettazione Didattica FAIR: La Metodologia di Skills4EOISC Applicata a CLARIN-IT	Il corso illustra i primi passi da muovere per implementare la progettazione didattica FAIR-by-Design secondo lo standard raccomandato dal progetto Skills4EOISC. L'adattamento si concentra sulle fasi di preparazione, design e produzione della metodologia in accordo con le necessità della comunità italiana a cui si rivolge, presupponendo un livello di competenza base/intermedio.
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR-ILC	11/02/2025	Online		Webinar	Internal	CNR-ILC Trainee	1	2	Introduzione a CLARIN	Introduzione ai principi FAIR, Open Science e ai servizi CLARIN funzionali ai compiti di traduzione, metadattazione e in generale alla gestione dei materiali di training come oggetti digitali FAIR coerenti con il lavoro dei tirocinanti entro l'attività 8.2 del progetto H2IOSC
OUI5 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		Società Italiana di Ottica e Fotonica (SIOF)	7-21/2/2025	In person	University of Florence	Workshop, course	External	Studenti e professionisti interessati nelle scienza dei dati	circa 21	40	Biophotonics and Artificial Intelligence School	Interdisciplinary course covering AI applications in photonics and life sciences. Topics included machine learning foundations, deep generative models, reinforcement learning, AI framework design, integration of AI with optical biosensing and advanced microscopy (e.g., fluorescence lifetime imaging, photoacoustic imaging), neuromorphic photonics, Large Language Models (LLMs), and ethical considerations of emerging technologies in medicine, robotics, and agriculture. Practical experience with laboratory exercises on biosensing technologies and Internet of Biosensors concepts.
OUI5 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		CNR-INO (Firenze, Italia), University of Ljubljana (Slovenia)	27/02/2025	Online		Webinar	External	Researchers, practitioners, PhD, Master and Bachelor students specialized or interested in different topics of heritage science	154	1	Laser cleaning in restoration	Removing unwanted materials in heritage restoration is a delicate process due to its irreversible nature. In this context, laser ablation presents a unique solution, allowing for high-precision interventions with immediate feedback and control. A safe and well-defined cleaning process can be achieved by fine-tuning the laser characteristics and operational parameters to align with the intrinsic properties of the materials. This presentation will cover the principles of laser cleaning for heritage objects, focusing on the methodology that must be followed to ensure safe interventions. It will highlight successful laser cleaning projects, emphasizing the thorough analytical evaluation of laser-treated surfaces and the careful adaptation of diagnostic approaches to effectively monitor the interventions.
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR - ILC	06/03/2025 13/03/2025 20/03/2025 27/03/2025	Online		Corso	External	Dottorandi	20	16	L'infrastruttura CLARIN per la Gestione FAIR dei Dati Linguistici e Testuali	Questo corso è destinato ad un pubblico di linguisti ma anche filologi e a chiunque debba approfondire la gestione dei dati linguistici e testuali. Al termine del corso gli studenti padroneggeranno nozioni quali quelle di scienza aperta, buona gestione dei dati della ricerca, piano gestione dei dati, e sapranno come rendere i loro corpora e risorse FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, e reusable); inoltre padroneggeranno i principali strumenti dell'infrastruttura CLARIN per le risorse linguistiche. Il corso articola in moduli distinti, pensati per fornire ai partecipanti una solida base teorica, strumenti pratici avanzati e applicazioni specifiche per la gestione dei dati. I 4 moduli di 4 ore ciascuno si svolgeranno i giovedì pomeriggio di marzo 2025, per un totale di 16 ore. La partecipazione al corso sarà da remoto. Il corso è sviluppato nel contesto del progetto H2IOSC che mira a sviluppare i nodi nazionali di quattro infrastrutture di ricerca nel settore delle scienze umane e del patrimonio culturale.
OUI5 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		CNR-INO (Firenze, Italia), University of Ljubljana (Slovenia)	27/03/2025	Online		Webinar	External	Researchers, practitioners, PhD, Master and Bachelor students specialized or interested in different topics of heritage science	174	1	Computational optical microscopy in heritage science	Computational imaging requires the optimization of hardware and software to gain information about a scene that is not accessible using traditional methods. For cultural heritage, this approach opens possibilities for new, non-destructive, yet highly specific means for understanding the chemical composition, structure, and shape of an object, building, or landscape. In this lecture, the speaker will present a brief background on the aims and goals of computationally imaging cultural objects, followed by an overview of his research group's contributions to the field, which started at Northwestern University and is now at the University of Hong Kong. A particular emphasis will be placed on taking the lessons learned from imaging the macroscopic world (things larger than a hand specimen) into the microscopic realm, which is more difficult due to the nonlinear interactions between light and matter at this scale. The last part of the lecture will examine the use of artificial intelligence and, specifically, foundational models (like those employed in OpenAI's ChatGPT) to solve problems in identifying and retrieving microscopic images of pigments, fibers, corrosion products, and other materials relevant to culture.
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN	AIUCD, AICA	AIUCD Scuola, AICA Emilia Romagna e Marche	04/04/2025	Online		Webinar	External	Docenti di scuola secondaria di secondo grado	60	2	Laboratorio sull'uso dell'Intelligenza Artificiale generativa	Introduzione ai concetti base dell'AI generativa: limiti ed opportunità Esempio d'uso nella didattica disciplinare Lavoro per gruppi sulle diverse tipologie di AI generative Discussione: Riflessioni critiche sull'uso dell'AI
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR-ILC, Università di Ferrara	09/04/2025	Online		Lezione	External	Studenti C.d.L. magistrale	20	2	FAIR Principles, Open Science and Data Stewardship	la lezione illustra le modalità di gestione dei dati secondo i principi FAIR, che saranno definiti ed esemplificati attraverso i repository istituzionali resi disponibili dalle Infrastrutture di Ricerca come CLARIN ERIC. A questo scopo si analizzeranno le modalità di deposito e descrizione dei dati con metadati standard. Gli studenti saranno guidati attraverso la redazione di un Data Management Plan per la gestione dei dati secondo le buone pratiche della Scienza Aperta. Infine sarà introdotta la figura del Data Steward proponendo l'esperienza della Comunità Italiana nata in seno al Centro di Competenza ICDC.
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR-ILC	14/04/2025	Online		Lezione	External	Studenti di master di II livello (Master InfoText Siena)	15	3	Interrogazione e Utilizzo di Corpora Annotati: l'Esempio di ParlaMint	La lezione introduce all'uso dei servizi base di CLARIN e alle risorse linguistiche FAIR-by-Design attraverso il caso studio di ParlaMint. La seconda metà della lezione analizza le modalità di interrogazione dei corpora parlamentari compresi in ParlaMint attraverso esempi pratici su SketchEngine e NoSketchEngine
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CNR-ILC	15/04/2025	Online		Lezione	External	Studenti di master di II livello (Master InfoText Siena)	15	3	TEI e ParlaMint: Tecnologie e Strumenti per l'Analisi dei Testi Parlamentari	La lezione approfondisce la ricerca sui corpora parlamentari di ParlaMint in TEI
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN	AIUCD, AICA	AIUCD Scuola, AICA Emilia Romagna e Marche	16/04/2025	Online		Lezione	External	Docenti di scuola secondaria di secondo grado	60	2	Introduzione all'Analisi Automatica dei Testi	Come le tecnologie digitali stanno cambiando il modo in cui studiamo i testi Analisi testuale assistita dal computer: concordanze, analisi delle frequenze, topic modeling Applicazioni pratiche per l'insegnamento della letteratura
OUI5 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		CNR-INO (Firenze, Italia), University of Ljubljana (Slovenia)	24/04/2025	Online		Webinar	External	Researchers, practitioners, PhD, Master and Bachelor students specialized or interested in different topics of heritage science	50	1	Acoustic emissions techniques applied to historical vehicle engines	Acoustic emission is a non-invasive, non-destructive technique, belonging to the NDT class (non-destructive testing), that is used in industry since the 1950s and applied also to the field of cultural heritage since the mid-1990s. It is based on the principle of elastic waves propagation in a material when a sudden release of energy inside the material itself occurs. This release of energy may happen due to a wide range of events taking place inside a solid material, such as the formation of a crack, corrosion phenomena, friction between two surfaces... The energy waves generated by the event travel inside the material and can be captured by piezoelectric sensors placed on the surface of the object. Acoustic emission allows then the detection and monitoring of a series of phenomena. In the field of cultural heritage, it is mainly applied to monitoring of cracks inside different types of objects (wooden objects, metal objects, enamels, built heritage, sculptures, paintings ...) due to environmental conditions changes and to integrated pest management, allowing to detect the activities of insects inside wood. In the field of automotive industry, acoustic emission is used to monitor the performances of newly produced engines. In the ACUME_HV project (Acoustic Emission Monitoring of Historical Vehicles) we have applied Acoustic Emission to historical vehicles' engines in order to perform a diagnosis of the state of conservation of the mechanical parts of the engines, due to wear, friction or corrosion, before their reactivation. During the talk you will learn about the Acoustic Emission techniques and their application to the diagnostic and monitoring of historical engines.
OUI5 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		CNR-INO (Firenze, Italia), University of Ljubljana (Slovenia)	22/05/2025	Online		Webinar	External	Researchers, practitioners, PhD, Master and Bachelor students specialized or interested in different topics of heritage science	120	1	Analysis of indigenous American objects from the V&A collection	Objects made of Indigenous American lacquer have only recently begun to receive the international recognition they truly deserve. The V&A has the largest public collection of these objects in the UK, and is actively researching them using advanced analytical techniques within a multidisciplinary framework. The scientific analysis and technical examination of Indigenous American lacquer objects is being bolstered by curatorial, conservation, anthropological and sociological expertise, and the results are being shared widely to bring the world's lacquer community together, bridging specialism, geography and language divides. From a Heritage Science perspective, what is the best analytical approach for objects which are both rare and not yet fully understood? This lecture will showcase the research carried out so far at the V&A and will highlight the most recent discoveries and conservation approaches.
OUI5 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		CNR-INO (Firenze, Italia), University of Ljubljana (Slovenia)	23/05/2025	Online		Webinar	External	Researchers, practitioners, PhD, Master and Bachelor students specialized or interested in different topics of heritage science	99	1	Emergency Preparedness of Library Collections	Libraries are custodians of irreplaceable cultural and intellectual heritage, making their protection during emergencies critical. There are significant challenges in safeguarding library collections during emergencies. This lecture examines key preparedness strategies, focusing on the development of different types of emergency plans tailored to specific needs and situations (flood, fire, etc.). A case study on flood preparedness will be shown to highlight practical approaches to protect and ensure the resilience of valuable library collections.
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		Università di Pisa	16/06/2025	In person & online	Polo Fibonacci, Pisa PI	Lezione	External	Studenti di laurea triennale e magistrale	30	3	Research Infrastructures supporting FAIR and Open data, tools, practices in the humanities and social sciences. The case of CLARIN	The lecture is designed to provide students with a practical and theoretical introduction to FAIR principles and Open Science, with a focus on the CLARIN research infrastructure. In the first part, through a presentation enriched with interactive quizzes, the fundamentals of proper data management in line with the FAIR principles and the strategic role of CLARIN in supporting the discovery and repository of linguistic resources and data will be explored. The importance of responsible data management will be emphasized, highlighting how a structured approach adhering to the FAIR principles fosters transparency, reproducibility and reuse of data in research. The second part will be dedicated to an interactive laboratory session, during which students will participate in a role-playing game. Randomly choosing a simulated research project, they will work in small groups to develop a draft Data Management Plan. During this activity, students will address practical issues, such as the management of personal data, and identify the necessary releases for the processing of sensitive data. The lesson aims to develop practical skills and raise awareness among students on the importance of ethical and sustainable data management in scientific research.
OUI6 - ISPF-NA	OPERAS		Istituto per la Storia del Pensiero Filosofico e scientifico moderno (ISPF)	16-19/06/2025	In person & online	Istituto per la Storia del Pensiero Filosofico e scientifico moderno (ISPF)	Course	Internal	Compagine H2IOSC	16	28	H2IOSC - GIORNATE DI FORMAZIONE PER CNR - Istituto per la Storia del Pensiero Filosofico e scientifico moderno (ISPF)	Elena Giglia: Open Science, Open Access, FAIR data: principles, practices and tools for humanities research. OPERAS, an infrastructure for Open Science in the humanities; Simone Aliprandi: Copyright, general principles and applications in the field of humanities research; Alfredo Corrao: The basis of the digital object: image files and their characteristics; Marco Scarbaci: Introduction to TEI and Introduction to XML metadata; Margherita Porena: Representation of information, Ontologies for Cultural Heritage; Giovanna Garofalo: Metadata: purposes and types General principles of digital archive management; Margherita Bartoli: Introduction to Digital Libraries: definition and basic concepts; Architecture and infrastructure of Digital Libraries; Conceptual and descriptive models of a Digital Library.
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		Università di Padova, University of Tokyo	19/06/2025	In person	Università di Padova	Workshop	External	Studenti di laurea magistrale, master e dottorato	10	5	Exploring Corpora with Voyant: Digital Tools for Text Analysis	Using Voyant or similar tools to enrich one's research, perhaps with a view to their dissertation
OUI5 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		CNR-INO (Firenze, Italia), University of Ljubljana (Slovenia)	19/06/2025	Online		Webinar	External	Researchers, practitioners, PhD, Master and Bachelor students specialized or interested in different topics of heritage science	130	1	Pyrolysis GC MS for heritage analysis	Pyrolysis-gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (Py-GC-MS) is a technique that offers high sensitivity and specificity in the analysis of polymeric materials. Using thermal energy in an inert atmosphere, the macromolecules are broken apart into smaller, volatile fragments that are separated, ionised and measured. Although the technique is indispensable for the characterisation of polymers, it is also excellent for the analysis of non-polymerised compounds, and mixtures of both. Sample preparation is minimal for Py-GC-MS, and recent advances have made it possible to analyse smaller samples than ever before.
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		University of Birmingham	29/06/2025	In person	University of Birmingham	Workshop	External	Studenti di laurea magistrale, master e dottorato	7	5	Applying FAIR data principles in corpus linguistics	This workshop will show participants how to incorporate the FAIR and CARE (Compared to the more generally applicable FAIR principles, the CARE principles focus specifically on certain research scenarios and will therefore play a less prominent role in the workshop.) principles into their corpus linguistics research projects. The programme will consist of theoretical and hands-on exercises, including services and tools from CLARIN, a European Research Infrastructure for language as social and cultural data. Through a combination of theoretical principles, hands-on activities and case studies, the participants will learn how to identify the requirements for a linguistic resource (e.g. a linguistic corpus) to align with the FAIR and CARE principles and apply them in their research workflow. Finally, the workshop will contain a case study and a roleplay on how to write a Data Management Plan (DMP) for your research.
OUI5 - INO-FI	E-RIHS		University of Malta	4-25/07/2025	In person	University of Malta	Webinar / workshop (partecipazione dello staff H2IOSC)	External	Studenti e professionisti interessati nelle scienza dei dati	circa 20	40	Summer School in Data Science 2025	The summer school is split in two sections, the first part delve into the basics of programming methodologies for Data Science as required in the remaining of the course. The second part of the school focuses on the use of Python for data science. The topics covered during the course are: regression, classification, clustering, machine learning, neural networks and deep learning among others.
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		The Venice Centre for Digital and Public Humanities, Università Ca'Foscari Venezia	22 ottobre - 10 dicembre 2025	In person	Venice	Seminars	External	Students	120	8	Seminars in Digital and Public Humanities	Paleographic analysis, digital textual analysis, archival studies, AI applied to Art
OUB - ILC-PI	CLARIN		CINUM (Centro d'Informatica Umanistica) e dalla Scuola Superiore dell'Università di Catania	29-31 ottobre 2025	In person	Catania	Autumn School	External	Students	150	24	Etnatext - Per una formazione umanistica al digitale	La Autumn School organizzata dal CINUM (Centro d'Informatica Umanistica) e dalla Scuola Superiore dell'Università di Catania è aperta a studenti, ricercatori e docenti che desiderano acquisire conoscenze e competenze nel campo delle Digital Humanities. Etnatext propone un'offerta formativa dedicata alle edizioni scientifiche digitali, all'Intelligenza Artificiale e al LLM, all'impiego del Natural Language Processing e alla didattica digitale.